

IJCSIS Vol. 19 No. 4, April 2021
ISSN 1947-5500

International Journal of Computer Science & Information Security

© IJCSIS PUBLICATION 2021
Pennsylvania, USA

Indexed and technically co-sponsored by :

AUTHOR SERIES

Indexing Service

IJCSIS has been indexed by several world class databases, for more information, please access the following links:

Global Impact Factor

<http://globalimpactfactor.com/>

Google Scholar

<http://scholar.google.com/>

CrossRef

<http://www.crossref.org/>

Microsoft Academic Search

<http://academic.research.microsoft.com/>

IndexCopernicus

<http://journals.indexcopernicus.com/>

IET Inspec

<http://www.theiet.org/resources/inspec/>

EBSCO

<http://www.ebscohost.com/>

JournalSeek

<http://journalseek.net>

Ulrich

<http://ulrichsweb.serialssolutions.com/>

WordCat

<http://www.worldcat.org>

Academic Journals Database

<http://www.journaldatabase.org/>

Stanford University Libraries

<http://searchworks.stanford.edu/>

Harvard Library

<http://discovery.lib.harvard.edu/?itemid=|library/m/aleph|012618581>

UniSA Library

<http://www.library.unisa.edu.au/>

ProQuest

<http://www.proquest.co.uk>

Zeitschriftendatenbank (ZDB)

<http://dispatch.opac.d-nb.de/>

IJCSIS

ISSN (online): 1947-5500

Please consider to contribute to and/or forward to the appropriate groups the following opportunity to submit and publish original scientific results.

CALL FOR PAPERS

International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS) January-December 2021 Issues

The topics suggested by this issue can be discussed in term of concepts, surveys, state of the art, research, standards, implementations, running experiments, applications, and industrial case studies. Authors are invited to submit complete unpublished papers, which are not under review in any other conference or journal in the following, but not limited to, topic areas.

See authors guide for manuscript preparation and submission guidelines.

Indexed by Google Scholar, DBLP, CiteSeerX, Directory for Open Access Journal (DOAJ), Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE), SCIRUS, Scopus Database, Cornell University Library, ScientificCommons, ProQuest, EBSCO and more.

Deadline: see web site

Notification: see web site

Revision: see web site

Publication: see web site

Context-aware systems
Networking technologies
Security in network, systems, and applications
Evolutionary computation
Industrial systems
Evolutionary computation
Autonomic and autonomous systems
Bio-technologies
Knowledge data systems
Mobile and distance education
Intelligent techniques, logics and systems
Knowledge processing
Information technologies
Internet and web technologies, IoT
Digital information processing
Cognitive science and knowledge

Agent-based systems
Mobility and multimedia systems
Systems performance
Networking and telecommunications
Software development and deployment
Knowledge virtualization
Systems and networks on the chip
Knowledge for global defense
Information Systems [IS]
IPv6 Today - Technology and deployment
Modeling
Software Engineering
Optimization
Complexity
Natural Language Processing
Speech Synthesis
Data Mining

For more topics, please see web site <https://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>

For more information, please visit the journal website (<https://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>)

Editorial Message from Editorial Board

It is our great pleasure to present the **April 2021 issue** (Volume 19 Number 4) of the **International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)**. High quality research, survey & review articles are proposed from experts in the field, promoting insight and understanding of the state of the art, and trends in computer science and technology. It especially provides a platform for high-caliber academics, practitioners and PhD/Doctoral graduates to publish completed work and latest research outcomes. According to Google Scholar, up to now papers published in IJCSIS have been cited over **19313 times** and this journal is experiencing steady and healthy growth. Google statistics shows that IJCSIS has established the first step to be an international and prestigious journal in the field of Computer Science and Information Security. There have been many improvements to the processing of papers; we have also witnessed a significant growth in interest through a higher number of submissions as well as through the breadth and quality of those submissions. IJCSIS is indexed in major academic/scientific databases and important repositories, such as: Google Scholar, Thomson Reuters, ArXiv, CiteSeerX, Cornell's University Library, Ei Compendex, ISI Scopus, DBLP, DOAJ, ProQuest, ResearchGate, LinkedIn, Academia.edu and EBSCO among others.

A great journal cannot be made great without a dedicated editorial team of editors and reviewers. On behalf of IJCSIS community and the sponsors, we congratulate the authors and thank the reviewers for their outstanding efforts to review and recommend high quality papers for publication. In particular, we would like to thank the international academia and researchers for continued support by citing papers published in IJCSIS. Without their sustained and unselfish commitments, IJCSIS would not have achieved its current premier status, making sure we deliver high-quality content to our readers in a timely fashion.

"We support researchers to succeed by providing high visibility & impact value, prestige and excellence in research publication." We would like to thank you, the authors and readers, the content providers and consumers, who have made this journal the best possible.

For further questions or other suggestions please do not hesitate to contact us at ijcsiseditor@gmail.com.

A complete list of journals can be found at:
<http://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>

IJCSIS Vol. 19, No. 4, April 2021 Edition

ISSN 1947-5500 © IJCSIS, USA.

Journal Indexed by (among others):

Open Access This Journal is distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source.

Bibliographic Information

ISSN: 1947-5500

Monthly publication (Regular Special Issues)
Commenced Publication since May 2009

Editorial / Paper Submissions:

IJCSIS Managing Editor

(ijcsiseditor@gmail.com)

Pennsylvania, USA

Tel: +1 412 390 5159

IJCSIS EDITORIAL BOARD

IJCSIS Editorial Board	IJCSIS Guest Editors / Associate Editors
Dr. Shimon K. Modi [Profile] Director of Research BSPA Labs, Purdue University, USA	Dr Riktesh Srivastava [Profile] Associate Professor, Information Systems, Skyline University College, Sharjah, PO 1797, UAE
Professor Ying Yang, PhD. [Profile] Computer Science Department, Yale University, USA	Dr. Jianguo Ding [Profile] Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway
Professor Hamid Reza Naji, PhD. [Profile] Department of Computer Enigneering, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran	Dr. Naseer Alquraishi [Profile] University of Wasit, Iraq
Professor Yong Li, PhD. [Profile] School of Electronic and Information Engineering, Beijing Jiaotong University, P. R. China	Dr. Kai Cong [Profile] Intel Corporation, & Computer Science Department, Portland State University, USA
Professor Mokhtar Beldjehem, PhD. [Profile] Sainte-Anne University, Halifax, NS, Canada	Dr. Omar A. Alzubi [Profile] Al-Balqa Applied University (BAU), Jordan
Professor Yousef Farhaoui, PhD. Department of Computer Science, Moulay Ismail University, Morocco	Dr. Jorge A. Ruiz-Vanoye [Profile] Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Morelos, Mexico
Dr. Alex Pappachen James [Profile] Queensland Micro-nanotechnology center, Griffith University, Australia	Prof. Ning Xu, Wuhan University of Technology, China
Professor Sanjay Jasola [Profile] Gautam Buddha University	Dr . Bilal Alatas [Profile] Department of Software Engineering, Firat University, Turkey
Dr. Siddhivinayak Kulkarni [Profile] University of Ballarat, Ballarat, Victoria, Australia	Dr. Ioannis V. Koskosas, University of Western Macedonia, Greece
Dr. Reza Ebrahimi Atani [Profile] University of Guilan, Iran	Dr Venu Kuthadi [Profile] University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg, RSA
Dr. Dong Zhang [Profile] University of Central Florida, USA	Dr. Zhihan Iv [Profile] Chinese Academy of Science, China
Dr. Vahid Esmaeelzadeh [Profile] Iran University of Science and Technology	Prof. Ghulam Qasim [Profile] University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar, Pakistan
Dr. Jiliang Zhang [Profile] Northeastern University, China	Prof. Dr. Maqbool Uddin Shaikh [Profile] Preston University, Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. Jacek M. Czerniak [Profile] Casimir the Great University in Bydgoszcz, Poland	Dr. Musa Peker [Profile] Faculty of Technology, Mugla Sitki Kocman University, Turkey
Dr. Binh P. Nguyen [Profile] National University of Singapore	Dr. Wencan Luo [Profile] University of Pittsburgh, US
Professor Seifeidne Kadry [Profile] American University of the Middle East, Kuwait	Dr. Ijaz Ali Shoukat [Profile] King Saud University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Riccardo Colella [Profile] University of Salento, Italy	Dr. Yilun Shang [Profile] Tongji University, Shanghai, China
Dr. Sedat Akleylek [Profile] Ondokuz Mayıs University, Turkey	Dr. Sachin Kumar [Profile] Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Roorkee

Dr Basit Shahzad [Profile] King Saud University, Riyadh - Saudi Arabia	Dr. Mohd. Muntjir [Profile] Taif University Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Dr. Sherzod Turaev [Profile] International Islamic University Malaysia	Dr. Bohui Wang [Profile] School of Aerospace Science and Technology, Xidian University, P. R. China
Dr. Kelvin LO M. F. [Profile] The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. PaperID 01042101: Operational Technology Threats in Developing Countries and Possible Solution (pp. 1-11)

Faysal A. Ghauri, EC-Council University, USA

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

2. PaperID 01042102: Cybersecurity Frameworks Globally and Saudi Arabia (pp. 12-24)

Faysal A. Ghauri, EC-Council University, USA

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

3. PaperID 01042103: A Noble Cost Effective Distributed Electronic Health System for Patient Data Handling: Bangladesh Perspectives (pp. 25-31)

Uzzal Kumar Prodhan, Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering, Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University, Trishal, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

Md Sadiq Iqbal, Md Nasim Akter, Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Khusbun Nahar Anita, Md. Forhad Alam & Al Amin Hossain, Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering, Bangladesh University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Md. Mazharul Islam, Special Inspector (ICT), Civil Aviation Authority of Bangladesh

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

4. PaperID 01042105: New Approach for Encryption Private key for Sender by using Hill Cipher with GGH Cryptography (pp. 32-35)

Salah AL Bermany, University of Kufa, Faculty of Computer and Mathematics, Computer Science, Iraq, Kufa

Majeed Ismael Sameer, University of Kufa, Faculty of Computer and Mathematics, Computer Science, Iraq, Kufa

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

5. PaperID 01042106: Portfolio Optimization Modeling Through Real-Time Reports and Analytics (pp. 36-42)

PhD (C.) Erarda Vuka, University of Tirana, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Albania

Dr Julian Fezaj, University of Tirana, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Albania

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

6. PaperID 01042107: Analysis of Engineering Students' Mindset Using Data Mining and Pre-Processing Techniques (pp. 43-48)

Safira Begum, Department of Master of Computer Applications, Visvesvaraya Technological University – RRC, Belagavi, Karnataka, India

Dr. Sunita S. Padmannavar, Dept. of Master of Computer Applications, Gogte Institute of Technology, Belagavi, Karnataka, India

Full Text: PDF [Academia.edu | Scopus | Scribd | Archive | DOI | Google Scholar]

7. PaperID 01042108: Forecasting Peak and Appliance Level Demand Using Smart Meter Data (pp. 49-58)

*Bhavya M. R., Vasuprada U., Dr. Azra Nasreen,
Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Rashtreeya Vidyalaya College of Engineering,
Bangalore, Karnataka, India*

Full Text: PDF [Academia.edu | Scopus | Scribd | Archive | DOI | Google Scholar]

8. PaperID 01042110: Machine Learning in Identification and Control of Biological Disasters (pp. 59-63)

*Chen Ling, Xingjian Lyu, Tian Zhenyu, Gabriela Mogos
School of Advanced Technology, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University, Suzhou, China*

Full Text: PDF [Academia.edu | Scopus | Scribd | Archive | DOI | Google Scholar]

OPERATIONAL TECHNOLOGY THREATS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES AND POSSIBLE SOLUTION

Faysal A. Ghauri #1

EC-Council University, USA

¹ iam@faysalghauri.com

Abstract— This particular research will involve proper analysis of several active threats about the operational technology existing within a number of various countries that are developing. The research will be depicting several issues that are mostly faced by some developing countries and will also comprise some recommendations that will help a lot in the mitigation of various recognised threats related to operational technology. The literature review will be comprising several resources that will be directly related to the key topic of research. The study will be capable of bringing out all of the various outcomes that are actually expected. This study will also involve a gap in the literature that will show all of the gaps that will be present in this study. A section of methodology comprises the opted research design, research philosophy, research approach, method of data collection, inclusion and exclusion criteria, analysis of data, and even the associated ethical issues. Lastly, there is a proper conclusion and also some recommendations for this study of research.

I. INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

Background of the Study

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is considered conjunction of all those technologies that blurs the prevalent lines between the physical and the digital worlds that come under cyber-physical systems or networks [1]. The awareness of operational technology and the severe and complicated infrastructure system and its security are rising. The path towards the protection and securing of operational technology systems is quite developed but requires proper watchfulness and understanding of the need to build the security. The very capability for implementing the security solutions that deliver quite a lot of perceptibility and control of the real-world awareness of the circumstance becomes the differentiators that help conduct safer and efficient operations. In a fast-changing world that is highly commercialised, important competitive advantage can be created with improved automation. OT networks operated independently in the past, which was entirely separated from the IT system in the same company [2]. However, data flow across the systems from customers to the manufacturers is essential as the data access in an operational technology network can affect everything from energy production to the output, thereby allowing the organizations to respond to the customer demands with greater efficiency [3].

Problem Statement

With every possible interlinking and the resulting extension of the operating systems comes an added risk to the automated operational technology. Therefore, with the addition of every new function, there comes new risk. Whenever any system goes online, it is bound to become a probable target. Hackers are pretty quick nowadays and are very efficient in finding out all the details by taking advantage of the vulnerabilities. It cannot be denied that new threats evolve as soon as the counter technology for eradicating the previous threats is built [4]. All these issues become more prevalent in the developing countries, which are very new in applying these rules; therefore, how a developed country handles this is far different from a developing country. This implements an active network more complex than ever. However, this is important in bringing about and creating defense against hackers and protecting the systems from any impending structural damage [5].

Research Aims and Objectives

Research Aim:

The research aims at analyzing the threats to operational technology that exists in developing countries. The research will help understand the various issues that the developing countries face and will throw enough light into the recommendations to mitigate the recognized operational technology threats.

Research Objectives:

The research objectives are as follows:

- To identify the operational threats of technology
- To analyze and understand the impact of operational technology threats in the developing countries
- To recommend ways that will help in mitigation of the identified issues about operation and technology

Research Questions

- The research questions are as follows:
- What are the operational threats of technology?

- What is the likely impact of operational technology threats in developing countries?
- What are ways in which the identified issues on operation and technology can be mitigated?

Thesis Statement

Developing countries have different dynamics that can alter the perception and sometimes overlook cybersecurity conveying the attacks' potentials by operational technology. Therefore, this specific document's objective is to comprehend the application of the developing countries' operational technologies and provide an overview of how they can protect themselves from such threats.

Research Rationale

Many of the original operational technology (OT) systems retuning the automotive manufacturing were not built, considering security to be the most important, due to negligible security risk in the past. These systems were said to consist of equipment that is separated initially entirely from all the other networks. However, the intermingling or the unison of IT and OT combined with the newer IoT has yielded new attack vectors previously not present. Thus, total automation aims at running and maintaining structures in various fields. Using systems such as and Industrial Control Systems (ICS) decreases the necessity for human interference. Human participation is required, much of which can be done remotely [6]. Therefore, this research will delve deeper into the threats and suggest remedies that the developing countries can understand and minimize threats.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

The specific chapter of the concerned thesis study accomplishes the predominant background literature on the concerned research topic. The United Nations points out the richest and developed countries with the highest per capita income as the most developed and upgrading countries. There is a massive introduction of the operational technology in the developing countries, which in turn includes some threats to the structure of the developing countries [7].

The review in a systematic way of the specific study has been discriminated in this section of the concerned study, with the theoretical framework's adoption at the end of the study for the proper clarification of the study.

Concept of Operational Technologies

Operational technology has now become the most common word on global parameters. Operational technology simply can be said as the OT. It signifies the plenty of computers and monitors or the alteration of the physical state of a specific

system. This also includes controlling the structure of the system for a control network of a power station for the execution of the rail system [8].

As today the various physical devices become more intelligent day by day, there is seen a rising trend towards adopting operational technologies in most of the fields. The actual concept of OT provides most of the wireless connectivity. This, in turn, provides immense betterment in the field of administrative works. This provides the administrator to control the whole work remotely with the use of operational technologies. The operational technology poses some malware, control of access, identification of the management, and many other security challenges faced by the IT [9]. The critical vulnerabilities that are found in operational technology can dispense the crucial structure at risk. This can cause a life or death situation if it is not addressed at the proper time. The operational technology system manages and monitors the industrial process's assets and the various works regarding the manufacturing of the types of equipment needed for industrial purposes. Operational technology plays a vital role in developing countries. Now the globe's development becomes more dependent on technological tools and techniques [10]. Operation technology is one of these concepts that are highly effective in the administrative workplace. OT concept is highly effective and has various implications in different fields.

Difference between IT and OT

Figure 1: The difference between IT and OT [11]

The operational technology monitors and manages the industrial process assets and helps in the manufacturing purposes of pieces of equipment required in the industrial field. Operational technology in the concept and the implication can last longer than the concept and the implication of information technology or the IT service. Information technology is the concept that can specifically evaluate as the implication of electricity in the various factories, the systems of the transpiration, buildings, and in the utility industry [12]. The critical evaluation of operational

technology is the managing and monitoring ability and the controlling ability of the physical device remotely. There are also some crucial differences between operational technology (OT) and information technology (IT).

Operational technology exists longer in the field of technology than information technology. More precisely, it can be said that information technology is the concept that is used in various fields. On the other hand, operational technology is the concept that keeps on ruining both the software and the hardware. The fundamental concept of operational technology and information technology are separated from each other. IT is always a specific domain of the CIO [13]. Operational technologies have different priorities, and information technology has very different priorities. The vast range of differentiability measured between the concept of information technology and operational technology in the field of cybersecurity. From the IT perspective, data is the king concept whereas, the whole process is the king concept in organizational technology. The IT has gateways everywhere, whereas; in the OT field, there are very few gateways. IT concept is fully dynamic. On the other hand, the OT concept is entirely deterministic. These are the most important differences between the fundamental concept of operational technology and information technology [14].

Available Operational Technologies and Types

The implication of the operational technology is increasing mentioned by the staff and employees of cybersecurity. The new upcoming industries' model's infrastructure system becomes more digitalized and more complex in day-to-day lifestyle. The concept of OT and its various implication is now required in many critical cases [15].

There are various types of operational technologies available in the market structure. One of the primary forms of critical security perspective is the Industrial Control System or ICS. The OT is considered an umbrella that can manage and monitor various forms of systems [16]. It also controls a broad range of industrial processes. The comprehensive control system of operational technology includes SCADA systems. That is Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition and the DCS systems. These all are run based on different programming languages. It also includes PLCs and RTUs. The concept of human-machine interface is also included in this specific study of operational technology.

This also includes several pieces of machinery and the pieces of equipment that are needed for the computing of the firms and various industrial purposes. This also includes the PLM system, the applications of MES, the systems regarding the automation of the safety and security, along with the management system regarding the building constructions [17].

Geopolitical Influence

Emerging the technologies like artificial intelligence and big data, and 5G telecommunication is crucial to financial services. This helps in underpinning new goods and transfer

measures of the operational processes. These primary technologies and different types of equipment, and various systems are used in the monitoring and measurement of the operational technology. The usage of operational technology also depends upon the process of various industries. These innovations are the most fundamental concept for the rising geopolitical rivalry [18].

Political Forecasts

Politics can hugely influence the acceptance of new technologies. The environment regarding the political atmosphere is considered the least predictable among all circumstances. Sometimes the political factor dominates the technological empowerment in the social structure. Operational technology (OT) helps announce the many political factors in the economy [19].

Current Conflicts

Rather than endurance of the significant Security operational technology (OT) breach that affects various confidentiality of the government along with various operations. The companies should consider these required actions to reduce various conflicts and mistrust OT while increasing ICS security at the same time. IT and OT structure have many conflicts.

Solutions

Research and Development

The research and development help in the growth process of the operational technology (OT). The research and development are perfect the process by which the system of Operational technology (OT) works to reach new knowledge that helps the researchers and every person use and create new technology, goods, and services, systems that for using and the selling purposes. The goal is achieved very easily and most often to add to the company's bottom line [20]. It refers to various innovative activities that corporations or governments undertake along with various companies in developing the new services or goods or improving the existing services or goods.

Available Solutions

Get various strategic alignments in operational technology (OT) at the highest levels:

This is an essential concept regarding the solution of the specific happening. This step takes complete responsibility for the issues [21].

Coordination of the joint task force by the researcher in operational technology (OT):

This is the second helpful step to be initiated by the researchers. There must a joint task force for the smooth operation of the concept. This should take place for the structural development.

Develop pilot projects structure in operational technology (OT) and a governing structure:

One of the first things of the joint cyber security task force process can implement to identify various pilot projects that both groups IT and OT can work on together. The researcher's task force can compile a list of various critical ICS assets that must be implemented and begin to assess what needs to be done [22].

Economic Repercussions

The society and the technology: The most critical case study of society's influence and the economic structure in technology. Technology helps in the overall growth of society. This involves the implication of operational technology (OT).

Consumer expectation: The essential part is technology always tries to reach the customer expectation. Technology reaches consumer satisfaction undoubtedly. The man is the inventor of the technology. High expectation causes the change in the technology [23].

Social changes: Some changes happen due to the implication of technology in economic structure. These types of social changes are not even suitable always. The enormous technological implication reduces the animal from the economic construction.

Possible Threats

OT security starts with various assessments of risk factors regarding cybersecurity. Threats are becoming very regular in this particular structure. The three components are there regarding the risk factors. These three steps of the assessment are:

The step regarding collection: This particular step includes the method manual or automated to collate the network data and identify the vulnerable devices. This also includes the various network parameters [24].

The step regarding analysis: The next step is analysis. This denotes the analysis of the collated data for the establishment of an operational technology framework. This would surely help to construct to adhere to maintain the standard of the industry. This is the most critical step of the study.

The step regarding projection: The last step is regarding the Projection of the assessment that includes real-time parameters for alerting. The audit of the policy and the procedure is the most crucial step that involves reviewing and auditing the operational technology (OT) of the cybersecurity policies [25].

Future Outlook

For the future outlook the researcher's concept of some regarding steps of the security in the network system, the

Security in the endpoint system, the Security in clouding, the data security, the intelligence security system, the vulnerable management system, and the continuity in the field of business [26].

Present Threats

Some threats are observed regarding the concept of operational technology (OT) of the cybersecurity policies. The present threats are explained below.

Lack of Test Environments: Operational technologies (OT) have different maturity level in contrast with Information Technology and one of the biggest challenge or threats is absence or lack of test environments. R&D and simulation is expensive in a way that industries still cannot afford to have such environment in place for the test purpose only.

Cultural difference between IT and OT: In the environment, we use culture of Engineers similar to IT and they care most about reliability and safety, fault tolerance, consistency and longevity. Engineers make sure that there is a stability when making changes in the OT environment. We need to define the optimum culture to manage the OT.

Air gapping: Operational technologies (OT) are far more separated from the concept of information technology (IT). This happens in the concept of air gapping. It is foremost essential for the regulation of the audit. Also, it scans these air gaps to maintain operational technology (OT) policies for ensuring connectivity [27].

Training: There is a severe lack in this section. These lacks are often seen in industries. This happens when the employees are not given adequate and proper knowledge for maintaining good OT (operational technology) security practices in the field of cybersecurity [28].

Incident response and planning regarding recovery: The various important Industries often fail to recover the critical document and methods regarding the critical backups. This also structures the happening of the poorest incident in case of the factors regarding outages.

Segmentation in the network: the various important industries need to be utilized the zone of the OT (Operational Technologies) systems and conduit concepts when dealing with OT security in the field of cyber section. They can limit the vulnerable incidents by the imposition of proper plans and controlling the access to specific zones of the OT (Operational Technologies) systems [29].

Awareness lack: There is seen a lack of awareness in the cybersecurity system about the OT security vulnerabilities. This is why companies are not ready to invest in protecting their OT (Operational Technologies) systems and the production of the various devices.

Literature Gap

For this particular case study, the literature review has been executed to be constructed at the extreme depth of the study with utmost possibility. However, this study has specific gaps that could not be filled due to some happenings due to happenings of circumstantial reasons [30]. At the initial stage, there were some problems due to the gathering of sufficient data required for the chosen period regarding the particular topic that has been considered. Besides this, the specific research area posed some aftermath on covering up the required data for the specific study analysis [31]. To avoid the issues regarding the accessibility of the concerning issues of the certain topic were posed in the pathway of gathering the secondary data of the study. The solution of the changing and the modifying title for this particular research is adopted. These are the most fundamental concepts of the literature gap that is faced during the research regarding the concerned topic.

Summary

This particular research provides awareness regarding the availability and the implication of the operational technologies and the specific challenges in the various developing countries. This study covers the different threats from the several developing countries about the structure of operational technologies. As research goes on, it is also found that is even challenging for specific developed countries will take some more time. This study focuses on the political and current conflicts [32]. Along with the available economic solution of the study concept, this study also includes the future outwork and the present threats regarding the implementation of the operational technologies in developing countries. The last section of the study includes the gaps in the literature faced during the research study [33]. This study will surely help as the thesis paper for the upcoming researches regarding this specific topic.

III. METHODOLOGY

Introduction

The research relating to the operational technology threats in developing countries and its possible solution requires a well-defined research methodology that effectively identifies, selects, processes, and analyzes information regarding the topic. The methodology enables the researcher to critically estimate the overall reliability and validity by clearly explain all the necessary steps for data collection and analysis. It constitutes research design, philosophy, approach, data collection method, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data analysis, and ethical issues.

Research Design

The overall strategy chosen to study and analyze the different components in a study is the research design. Primarily, there

are three methodologies in research design such as explanatory, exploratory, and descriptive. Explanatory research significantly connects ideas to understand the case, which requires adequate investigation. Exploratory research studies the previous researches on the topic to develop deeper insights [34]. The descriptive approach defines the characteristics, population and undergoes a critical analysis of the problem, both qualitative and quantitative. The descriptive approach is followed in the paper as critical analysis is effective for finding possible solutions.

Research Philosophy

Data collected in research is based on a particular belief regarding the phenomena is known as research philosophy. Commonly, research philosophy is categorized into four parts, interpretivisms, positivism, realism, and pragmatism. The interpretivism approach is practiced in social science research as it tries to understand the social world and does not involve any actual investigation and analysis [35]. The positivist approach gives shape to individuals by understanding human behavior. The positivism approach believes that society shapes the individual as the social world works objectively. The realism approach is based on the reality of own mind following assumptions in the empirical investigation as real cases follow structures, processes, and entities [36]. Pragmatism is associated with facts and follows a mixed methodology structure. The current research follows the positivism approach for qualitatively study the operational technology threats in developing countries.

Research Approach

The research approach investigates the plans and procedures followed in the research. It is classified under the top-down and the bottom-up approach. The top-down approach studies the research from a broad perspective to a narrow one, and the bottom-down approach follows the opposite manner. The paper follows the top-down approach to broaden the perspective. Accordingly, the paper follows deductive and inductive approaches [37]. The deductive approach aims to develop a theory relating to the topic, and the inductive approach follows existing theories for research. Developing theories are complicated and require adequate research, which may not give effective results. Thus, the paper follows a deductive approach to use existing theories and find a suitable solution for the operational technology threats in developing countries.

Data Collection Method

The method of collecting data in research depends on the type of data to be collected for the research. There are two types of data sources: primary and secondary where primary data is collected by researchers through interviews and surveys; researchers already collect secondary data. As the paper follows the deductive approach, secondary data is more

effective, taken from authentic sources, government websites, and peer-reviewed journal articles. The collected data can be either qualitative or quantitative. Qualitative data are descriptive and immeasurable, and quantities data are about quantities or numbers [38]. To study the operational threats in developing countries, quantitative data is inadequate to explain the causes. As a result, the paper follows qualitative research concerning secondary data sources. Thus, the method of collecting data is peer-reviewed journal articles, authentic websites, and books.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria help select the data sources that need to be chosen, and exclusion criteria help to reject the eliminated data sources. The inclusion criteria for studying the operational technology threats are the data from books, peer-reviewed journal articles, authentic government websites of developing countries from 2010 to 2020 regarding operational technology problems. Exclusion criteria are data sources before 2010 and taken from developed countries. Websites that are inauthentic present quality information and having language, other than English.

Data Analysis

The current research undergoes data analysis in two ways—past literature and case study. Literature available on operational technology in developing countries is critically analyzed concerning the chosen period [39]. The case study takes account of several cases to reveal operational technology threats and analyze the outcomes. Based on outcomes, solutions are to be formed for effective research.

Ethical Issues

The research meets the ethical standards of the university and country. Information is taken from authentic sources that are critically reviewed. Sources are appropriately cited, and information is subjected to plagiarism. No person is harmed during the research, and the research is conducted following all the ethical practices.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

Security in the OT generally covers the controlling of the Security around Process Control Systems (PCS), Distributed Control Systems (DCS), and Supervisory Control and Acquisition of Data (SCADA) environments which are also thus combined referred to as Industrial Control Systems (ICS) perceiving into the environments. An environment involving the ICS can be as simply referring as the workstation of engineering that is being connected with the Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), which is seen to be interfacing with

smaller sets of relays and meters or can be perceived as complexity into the as a high resistant system of distribution and the system that is distributed is thus involved into the commanding center that is managing thousands of devices of Industries across many sites. Thus, here in the assessment, a detailed study of the Security into OT fields has been reviewed, studying the varied aspects of the security in the OT and the varied challenges been faced by the Security of the OT. Beneficiaries have been added to the security fabric and several strategies for the operational methods are implemented

Thematic Analysis

OT Security

OT Security refers to the term that signifies the technological advances and the practicing method implemented to protect the people into the asset's formation and the information gathered. Monitoring and controlling the physical devices that start processing the underlying events. It starts initiation into the changes of the state into the system of OT enterprise. Solutions relating to the OT's Security involve a broader aspect of the relating technologies that could be adopted from the firewalls of the future generation. Information relating to the security and management of the event are thus implemented into the systems to identify the varied notions of accessing and management and various larger aspects [40]. Security of OT to the cyber world, in traditional ways, was not essential into the form as the systems of the OT are not connected with the availability of the internet. They do not incur the exposition of the threats into the outside world. Initiatives into the digital world have increased, and the OT and IT networks are thus made into converged [41]. Organizations are thus perceived to impose varied solutions into some of the specific points to address various specific issues related to the studied detail. Approaches to the OT's Security thus formulates in resulting into the matter of complexity of the network that does not be implemented in finding the solutions that cannot be able to incorporate solutions. Thus, the solutions do not incur the capability of sharing the information and thus be able to provide visibility in a full-fledged way.

Priority of OT Security

Organizations relating to the industries are thus rushing by taking advantage of the IT technologies into the technologies of operation. Working ambiance relating to the subject has been posing competitiveness. In the world of changing, systems that are interconnected and the analytics of the data, ICS, SCADA, sensors being intelligent, and IIOT are made in addition to manufacturing [42]. Increment into the efficiency that has been perceived caters to the addition of benefits into this sector. In the sphere of the infrastructure, risks are observed that are countered by the imposition of the shared data over OT's Security. Thus, the security context paves the

way for offering a portfolio into the sphere of the Operational Technology solutions of security that would help the industries. It would also act as a beneficiary towards building up an intensive environment and thus monitors and provides security to the preferred networks. The also incur the availability of the protecting the endpoints and thus indulge in delivering several services relating to the cybersecurity issues.

Major OT and ICS Concerns

Information Technology refers to the field of study related to computer technology factors, which thus pacifies to involve both the notions of the hardware and the software. The vital distinction between the OT and the IT is that devices involved in the OT control the whole of the world of physical strata, whereas the systems of IT manage the data [43]. Several concerning behaviorisms are being perceived through the OT and ICS, which are elaborated into this specified context.

Several risks are seen to have been imposed on the environment. Risk into the procedures of mitigation strategies and are also supported by several remedial solutions, which are thus perceived with the patching into the limitation [44]. They have been very hard that has been used in the testing procedures in the context of the environment of the production. The lower amount of visibility involved in the assets, analytics procedures, and various data associated with the data thus impose huge risk threats over the environment.

Security Skills are thus seen to perceive with limitation. It is generally conferred that the teams of OT don't support or acquire the knowledge about the security proceedings. Processes that are involved in the system of the IT teams also do not support the view of the operation processes. The gap in the skill critically thus is added in contributing to the vulnerability that has been evolved into security issues.

Disrupted coordination's are evolved into operational procedures. Attacks onto the periphery of the cybercrime on the grounds of SCADA and the ICS can impose influential behavior over the safeties, availability and the several issues of reliability [45]. Prediction about the workers, operations involved, and the chain of value results in the depiction of issues that can be referred to as the environment's catastrophic nature.

Complain against the protection of data is thus involved. Regulatory imposition of the government continuously is paving to grow as the attacks relating to the cyber attacks are on the verge of the increment [46]. Attacks relating to the cyber security issues not been observed that they are only with the frequency, however with the severe condition too. Such dynamic changes that are being perceived over the environment poses to influence in the development of varied changes related to the operational behavior into the studied area.

Benefits of Security Fabric

Security fabric determines three types of beneficiaries in terms of Visibility, Control, and Continuous Monitoring.

In discovering any of the devices found to be attached to the IT- OT network, determining the degree of trust to the specific issue is what is essential. Continuously monitoring it helps bring the level of trust upgraded [47]. Defining the attack's surface, ensuring the active devices, and profiling based on traffic should have to be ensured. Assurances of the visibility of the traffic in respect of the actions that are in action are required. Thus, teams being involved in the OT security allow in dictating traffic, protocols maintained, applications, ports, and the varied services. Points that are enforced into the environment ensure the protection into the north-south and west-east level.

Dependencies upon the system of OT and the various subsystem are to carry out the proceedings of the job. Authentication regarding the varied multi-level factors ensures that the people are assigning to have permissions and access properly. Segmentation into the network and several micro segmenting procedures thus pave a way to layered and approach levelling within the control zones [48]. Quarantine into the automated version helps in preventing internal damage.

Analysis of continuing behaviors into the networks of OT thus helps in providing the teams to gather intelligence about the varied threats that are known or the fact that is not known. Thus, a tool of security paves a way to log out, to report, dependent upon analytically, and thus evaluate the collected activities within the observed system [49]. It provides security of information and management of events and maintains the orchestration into the automated security, and the capabilities of the responses are gathered too. The user's perspective acquires security of the OT insights and the analysis of the behavior is carried out with the procedure of assessing threats that also play a role in ensuring in protecting continuously.

Challenges to OT Security

There has been observed that several challenges are defined within the periphery of the Security of the OT. Risk assessment into the OT infers about a percent of 74 percent. The percentage of the companies that do not have any specification of the policies ranging from the OT incurs about 78% in terms of the policies [50]. Among the respondents, more than one-third that has been reported worries about the following challenges of securities of OT. Third parties thus perceive to incur a lag over security expertise that has been needed in assisting with technology that has been converged and the Internet of Things (IoT) being Sensitive; otherwise, the data of confidentiality would be leaked [51]. Businesses that are developed do not have the recommendation of implementing a security-specified plan of response that is related to the OT. It is none the secret that OT has been producing threatening issues over the development. According to security of latest, Skybox imposes Vulnerability issues and thus claims by threatening the reports that are in trend. There is an increment into the risk that is hampering the growth of surface attacks being brought by the likes of the internet of things (IoT) of industrial issues and OT networks.

Attacks are observed into the OT thus continued to climbing, with an increment of 10% between the year 2017 and 2018 [52]. The attacks have been ranged in the motive and is impacted that, the outbreak of Wanna Cry has hit Taiwanese Semiconductor Company of Manufacturing (TSMC) was a vital example showing how the effectiveness of tool of cybercriminal namely ransomware. Threats all over the nation-state and exposure to several internalities thus create the perfect storm of cyber-attack that is imposing havoc influence over a network and the company's bottom line. Stuxnet Company also faced similar damage in the year 2010.

Strategies for Operation

Assessing the risk is an essential factor. The assessment of the risk starts effectivity into the security program. Visibility should thus be ensured over the OT's environment and must be observing the assets of vulnerability. Operational strategies should also be marking the engagement of the plans and strategies among the prospect of the complaint and assessments of vulnerability. Developmental policies of the government and the requirement must also be fulfilled in the highlighted point.

The operational activities must support protection. Thus, operational activities must be conveyed over in carrying out the efficiency in carrying out the desired objectives into the implementation of the effectiveness of the OT's Security. Discoveries into the data, analyzing and classifying, several networks and designs into the endpoint security and their implementation should have to be introduced into the sector [53]. Deployment of the identity and building it can thus result in accessing the solution to the management issues. The team should also participate in the designing and deploying of an OT SOC that protects the operations.

Operations management must be ensured in order to run the operational management smoothly and efficiently. If there is perceived any of the attacks, it should have been better in reacting to incorporate the plan of response into the specified area of OT. Thus, managing the alerting issues and reducing the positives of falseness is associated with the managed security services [54]. Development of the security service relating to the OT has enormous responses over the land with the playbooks. This thus contributes to helping to focus on the improving paradigm of the operations of the security.

Summary

Security of OT is thus a software or a hardware device that helps in the detection or thus causes to incur a transformation through implementing the directly monitored processor that could be implemented over the controlled devices' procedure [55]. It also evolves several inclusions of the processes and the generated events into the system of the enterprise. The respondents of the raised issue that involves around more than one third of the people who are being worried about the several challenges associated with the Security issues. Parties of the third-order often suffer from the issue of lacking

expertise in the security aspect. They are in the requirement to assist the technology that is converged and the Internet of Things Sensitive. This could be the fact that the secured data could thus be leaked. Priorities of the securities are driven mainly by the responses of the assets that are found in nature. Into the IT realm, the most criticality element and the targeted attacks are thus implemented into the inclusion of equipment and the process [56]. Priorities of Security are thus diversely based upon the basis of the differences.

Thus, the security of the OT is important and is commonly been implemented in protecting the systems of industries and from the attacks of technology in the operation. Operational Security Technology thus paves a way for protecting and controlling the infrastructure that are critical and thus it comprises of the stations at power firms, networks in the transportation and the application into the cities that are smart.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

It can be concluded that Security within the OT generally covers the specific control of security around the PCS, DCS, and even the respective environments of SCADA. Several kinds of risks are found to be countered by imposing the data shared over the OT security. OT or the Operational Technology will offer several security solutions to various industries as it acts like a specific beneficiary towards properly building up a specific environment that will be intensive to several assets and thus can be monitoring and also offering security to the networks are preferred. This will also be incurring the particular availability of the protection of endpoints and thus will be indulging indirectly offering several various services which are directly related to the issues of cybersecurity. Security fabric is possessing several benefits towards the Security of OT.

Linking with Objectives

The research has offered a lot of awareness about the particular implication and the availability of OT or Operational Technologies and different kinds of threats and challenges within several countries that are developing. This research study has covered all of the various kinds of threats from several countries developing about the OT structure. The research has focused more on the various conflicts, which are recent as well as political. It has involved the outwork of the upcoming future and some of the current threats about implementing several operational technologies within all of the countries that are found to be developing. To solve all of the threat-related problems associated with OT, OT security has been significantly prioritized. It has been found that several various benefits are offered by the security fabric, which is known to be determined three kinds of beneficiaries upon the particular terms of visibility, controlling as well as continuous monitoring. Hence, it can be said that the research

is capable of covering all of the key objectives of the study for bringing out appropriate outcomes which are expected.

Recommendation

One must be ensuring the management of various operations for adequately running the operational management smoothly and efficiently. If an attack is perceived, it must be better indirectly reacting to incorporate the response plan into the OT area. There must be proper management of various issues that are alerting. Doing this and reducing all of the positives of falseness is directly associated with various security services that are appropriately managed. It must be remembered that risk assessment is a significant factor. There must be proper security programs, and one must also be ensuring visibility over the particular OT environment and seeing various vulnerability assets. All of the various operational strategies must be marking plans and strategies of engagement among the specific prospect of the vulnerability assessment. These recommendations will be very much helpful for obtaining better OT security.

Future Scopes

Eventually, OT and IT security will be overlapping as both of them will be dealing with the various fundamentals of the encryption of data, authentication, quality, and reliability. This is because it is found that about 80% of the issues related to security that OT faces are almost similar to IT, while 20% are very much unique, not to be anyhow ignored and critical.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1]. HUANG, K., Siegel, M. and Madnick, S., (2018) Systematically understanding the cyber-attack business: A survey. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 51(4), pp.1-36
<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3199674>
- [2]. Hoffman, F., (2019) INDUSTRIAL INTERNET OF THINGS VULNERABILITIES AND THREATS: WHAT STAKEHOLDERS NEED TO CONSIDER. *Issues in Information Systems*, 20(1).
https://www.academia.edu/download/61917850/Industrial_Internet_of_Things_Vulnerabilities_and_Threats20200128-84767-1pl6aqf.pdf
- [3]. Gómez, Á.L.P., Maimó, L.F., Celdran, A.H., Clemente, F.J.G., Sarmiento, C.C., Masa, C.J.D.C. and Nistal, R.M., (2019) On the generation of anomaly detection datasets in industrial control systems. *IEEE Access*, 7, pp.177460-177473.
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8926471/>
- [4]. Assenza, G., Faramondi, L., Oliva, G. and Setola, R., (2020) Cyber threats for operational technologies. *International Journal of System of Systems Engineering*, 10(2), pp.128-142.
<https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/IJSSE.2020.109127>
- [5]. Chandler, R., Hambly, B., Holcomb, J., Ressopoulos, G. and Wharton, M., (2017) Multi-vector threats and the argument for greater convergence. *Cyber Security: A Peer-Reviewed Journal*, 1(1), pp.80-91.
<https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/hsp/jcs/2017/0000001/00000001/art00009>
- [6]. Xu, W., Tao, Y. and Guan, X., (2018, June) The landscape of industrial control systems (ICS) devices on the internet. In *2018 International Conference on Cyber Situational Awareness, Data Analytics and Assessment (Cyber SA)* (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8551422/>
- [7]. Ani, UPD, He, H. and Tiwari, A., (2017) Review of cybersecurity issues in industrial critical infrastructure: manufacturing in perspective. *Journal of Cyber Security Technology*, 1(1), pp.32-74.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/23742917.2016.1252211>
- [8]. Avdeeva, E., Davydova, T., Skripnikova, N. and Kochetova, L., (2019) Human resource development in the implementation of the concept of "smart cities". In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 110, p. 02139). EDP Sciences.
https://www.e3s-conferences.org/articles/e3sconf/abs/2019/36/e3sconf_spbwosce2019_02139/e3sconf_spbwosce2019_02139.html
- [9] [27] [33]. Ferronato, N. and Torretta, V., (2019) Waste mismanagement in developing countries: A review of global issues. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(6), p.1060. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/16/6/1060>
- [10]. Galinec, D., Možnik, D. and Guberina, B., (2017) Cybersecurity and cyber defence: national level strategic approach. *Automatika: časopis za automatiku, mjerenje, elektroniku, računarstvo i komunikacije*, 58(3), pp.273-286.
https://hrcak.srce.hr/index.php?show=clanak&id_clanak_jezik=299324
- [11] [12] [14] [26]. Goos, M., Arntz, M., Zierahn, U., Gregory, T., Gomez, S.C., Vázquez, I.G. and Jonkers, K., (2019) The impact of technological innovation on the future of work (No. 2019/03). *JRC Working Papers Series on Labour, Education and Technology*.
<https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/202320>
- [13] [16]. Gunduz, M.Z. and Das, R., (2020) Cyber-security on smart grid: Threats and potential solutions. *Computer networks*, 169, p.107094.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128619311235>

- [15] [18]. Anand, P., Singh, Y., Selwal, A., Alazab, M., Tanwar, S. and Kumar, N., (2020) IoT vulnerability assessment for sustainable computing: threats, current solutions, and open challenges. *IEEE Access*, 8, pp.168825-168853.
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9189773/>
- [17] [21] [25]. Hettiarachchi, H., Meegoda, J.N. and Ryu, S., (2018) Organic waste buyback as a viable method to enhance sustainable municipal solid waste management in developing countries. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15(11), p.2483. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/15/11/2483>
- [19]. Sharma, R., Sinha, A. and Kautish, P., (2021) Does renewable energy consumption reduce ecological footprint? Evidence from eight developing countries of Asia. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 285, p.124867.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652620349118>
- [20] [22] [24] [29] [32]. Di Vaio, A. and Varriale, L., (2020) Blockchain technology in supply chain management for sustainable performance: Evidence from the airport industry. *International Journal of Information Management*, 52, p.102014.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0268401219304803>
- [23] [30]. El Rassi, M.A.B., (2020) Why one e-business adoption model won't fit all firm sizes: The case of Lebanon's e-service industry. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 86(5), p.e12135.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/isd2.12135>
- [28]. Tukamuhabwa, B., Stevenson, M. and Busby, J., (2017) Supply chain resilience in a developing country context: a case study on the interconnectedness of threats, strategies and outcomes. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*.
<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/SCM-02-2017-0059/full/html>
- [31]. Bhuvaneshwari, S., Hettiarachchi, H. and Meegoda, J.N., (2019) Crop residue burning in India: Policy challenges and potential solutions. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(5), p.832.
<https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/16/5/832>
- [34]. Aithal, P.S. (2017). ABCD Analysis as Research Methodology in Company Case Studies. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), pp.40-54.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3037309
- [35]. Abutabenjeh, S. and Jaradat, R. (2018). Clarification of research design, research methods, and research methodology: A guide for public administration researchers and practitioners. *Teaching Public Administration*, 36(3), pp.237-258.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0144739418775787>
- [36]. Mishra, S.B. and Alok, S. (2017). Handbook of research methodology.
<http://www.nkrgacw.org/nkr%20econtent/nutrition%20and%20dietetics/PG/II.M.Sc%20N&D/BookResearchMethodology.pdf>
- [37]. Kumar, R. (2018). Research methodology: A step-by-step guide for beginners. Sage.
https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=J2J7DwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=research+methodology+types&ots=cvmmJANKIf&sig=8mAm6hC_6HWIAAlqxykJKM8aORM
- [38]. Mohajan, H.K. (2018). Qualitative research methodology in social sciences and related subjects. *Journal of Economic Development, Environment and People*, 7(1), pp.23-48.
<https://www.cceol.com/search/article-detail?id=640546>
- [39]. Kanu, IA (2019). Igwebuikere research methodology: A new trend for scientific and wholistic investigation. *IGWEBUIKE: An African Journal of Arts and Humanities*, pp.95-105.
<https://www.igwebuikeresearchinstitute.org/journal/5.4.7.pdf>
- [40] [44] [52]. Ibm.com. (2021) OT and ICS Security - Operational Technology and Industrial Control Systems Security. [online] Available at: <<https://www.ibm.com/security/operational-technology>> [Accessed 27 March 2021].
- [41]. McIntyre, A., (2018) Developing a Cybersecurity Protocol for Your Operational Environment. *Natural gas & electricity*, 34(9), pp.23-27.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/gas.22048>
- [42]. Parekh, M., Waedt, K. and Tellabi, A., (2021) Aligning with cybersecurity framework by modelling OT security. *INFORMATIK* 2020.
<https://dl.gi.de/handle/20.500.12116/34736>
- [43] [45] [46] [48]. Forcepoint. (2021) Cyber Edu. [online] Available at: <<https://www.forcepoint.com/cyber-edu>> [Accessed 27 March 2021].
- [47]. Brillaulta, V., Cornwallb, L., Diasc, N., Dussad, T., Ferrye, S., Gabriel, S., Groepf, D., Kelseyb, D., Kourilg, D., Krasovech, B. and Neilsonb, I., (2017) Coordinating Operational Security in evolving distributed IT-Infrastructures.
<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/e027/dff2f11d bc09eee3b4e5becfc2d3e5cbfe2e.pdf>

[49] [51]. MicroscopeUK. (2021) The security challenges of OT and how the IT department can help. [online] Available at: <<https://www.computerweekly.com/microscope/opinion/The-security-challenges-of-OT-and-how-the-IT-department-can-help>> [Accessed 27 March 2021].

[50]. Parekh, M., Waedt, K. and Tellabi, A., (2021) Aligning with cybersecurity framework by modelling OT security. INFORMATIK 2020. <https://dl.gi.de/handle/20.500.12116/34736>

[53]. Morelli, U., Nicolodi, L. and Ranise, S., (2019) An open and flexible cybersecurity training laboratory in IT/OT Infrastructures. In Computer Security (pp. 140-155). Springer, Cham. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-42051-2_10

[54]. Tarofder, A.K., Azam, S.F. and Jalal, AN, (2017) Operational or strategic benefits: Empirical investigation of internet adoption in supply chain management. Management Research Review. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/MRR-10-2015-0225/full/html>

[55]. Sezer, S., (2018) September. TIC: IoT Security:-Threats, Security Challenges and IoT Security Research and Technology Trends. In 2018 31st IEEE International System-on-Chip Conference (SOCC) (pp. 1-2). IEEE. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8618571/>

[56]. Fortinet. (2021) What is Operational Technology (OT): An Operational Technology Security Primer. [online] Available at: <<https://www.fortinet.com/solutions/industries/scada-industrial-control-systems/what-is-ot-security>> [Accessed 27 March 2021].

CYBERSECURITY FRAMEWORKS GLOBALLY AND SAUDI ARABIA

Faysal A.Ghauri #1

EC-Council University, USA

¹ iam@faysalghauri.com

Abstract— The history of incremental internet users in Saudi Arabia defined the basis of threats posed to the country and the region. After setting up the aim, objectives, and research questions, I moved to start finding the issue and how it impacts the national economy of Saudi Arabia. Covered several cybersecurity frameworks and practices globally. The benefits and challenges of the cybersecurity framework and its impacts on the IoT and blockchain industry are apparent. Agent-based modeling simulation technique is also used in this report alongside the CIMF framework's importance, which is an essential aspect of cybersecurity.

I. INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

Introduction

The globalized age of modern civilization and industrialization has indeed introduced ample networking opportunities to business entities worldwide. People can now access anything on the internet, and the growth of the internet has reached such a point that almost no business operation could be conducted without it. In Saudi Arabia, the number of internet users is increasing, and simultaneously, the number of cyber threat incidents is also following a rampage of enhancement. This project report will shed light on how Saudi Arabian businesses are suffering due to a lack of cybersecurity frameworks in their business infrastructure.

Research-Background

It has been previously discovered that data security awareness education and training framework is relatively poor in Saudi Arabia. As a result, many eminent business enterprises of the country have been affected due to the cyber threats imposed on them, and their business operations were disrupted in the process. The rate of data breaching reached such a high peak that in 2019 almost 44% of Saudi Arabians were convinced that their professional information would likely be leaked on the internet. In 2018 only, through the Facebook data breach in Saudi Arabia, almost 29 million datasets of users were dumped on the internet, and it hampered the lives of many people [1]. There is no proper training given to the school and university students, colleagues, and office employees on cybersecurity frameworks to learn to remain protected from such threats. It was also discovered that almost 92% of Saudi Arabians never received any data security management training, so they face a high vulnerability rate in such adverse

exposures [2]. Lack of anti-cybercrime law is also smoothening hackers' process to attack the citizens and business firms online, so researching this topic has become quite important.

Figure 1: Saudi Arabians at Risk of Cybersecurity Breaches [3].

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Due to the rise of digital devices, cybersecurity threats in Saudi Arabia are increasing. Lack of information and data security awareness among the end-users has increased cybercrime rates in the country. The hackers have been able to erase the complete hard drive of a computer and destroy any sensitive information that has given rise to more politics and terrorism affairs. The number of internet users in the country was estimated as 22.4 million by the end of 2019. The increasing cybersecurity rate could affect these people and the e-commerce companies who operate entirely virtually with their customers.

In 2016, it was found out that their internal cybersecurity threats impact almost 40% of Saudi Arabian companies, and the most significant single cause of data loss is due to employee negligence only. In 2012, an oil company in Saudi Arabia was affected by an internal Information security incident, and a virus was sent to the computer through a USB drive [4]. Even in 2015, a study conducted by the Kaspersky

Lab revealed that a Middle Eastern espionage firm named Dessert Falcon targeted most Saudi Arabian MNCs. The aim was to use the phishing attack and send ransomware emails to their website to increase their shoulders' malicious payload. As a result, many Saudi Arabian companies and customers' potential data were lost. Even the hard drives of their machines were erased in some cases, making it utterly difficult for them to restart their business operations. The business enterprises and the King Saud University website were hacked recently, and the personal information of 812 students was released on the internet. Therefore, it needs to be fixed so that both human malicious and non-human malicious threats could be reduced in the nation and their business infrastructure could be more trustworthy.

Figure 2: Cybersecurity Awareness in Saudi People [5]

Similar studies have also shown that most Saudi Arabia people are not aware of detailed information of these cybersecurity threats, so most of them only use antivirus software. It has been found out that 74.59% of Saudis use antivirus software, 12.32% use anti-phishing software, and 11.87% use anti-spam software without knowing their utilities and consequences [6]. Since the year 2012, cybersecurity threats had engulfed Saudi Arabia when the Aramco network was attacked for the first time. Almost 30,000 hard drives were erased from the computer, hindering their operational flow.

The cyberattacks must be stopped because it adversely impacts the business enterprises or on the individuals, but it hampers the national economy potentially. In Saudi Arabia only, the entire peninsula's largest economy is the oil economy, which accounts for approximately 60% of their GDP. Since the economic system is so poorly diversified, it is natural that the increasing cyber threats can destroy the national economy notably [7]. Cyberattacks can cause electrical blackouts, cause failure in military equipment, and breach national security secrets. Thus, there is a huge probability that these attacks can cause a lump sum amount of general chaos. The cyberattack boom even increased noticeably in the pandemic period. According to a research report published by Mimecast's Threat Centre, malware

threats increased by 22%, and spam threats increased by 36%. Almost 95% of Saudi Arabian businesses were hit last year by cybersecurity threat incidents when the Covid19 pandemic was at its peak, and the nation was undergoing lockdown restrictions [8]. Since most businesses were operating online during that time, the rate of such attacks increased, which is why to make the e-commerce business platform more credible and trustworthy in Saudi Arabia, these attacks must be stopped.

III. OBJECTIVES

This research aims to identify the credibility of cybersecurity frameworks in Saudi Arabian business organizations.

Its objectives are;

- To identify the concept of cybersecurity framework and the vast array of categories this phenomenon has
- To explore the impact and benefits of cybersecurity framework on Saudi Arabian business infrastructure
- To discover the challenges that companies come across while implementing cybersecurity frameworks
- To recommend some probable mitigation strategies for eliminating the challenges

Thus, the research question would be;

What is the credibility of the cybersecurity framework in Saudi Arabian business companies, and how impactful is it in their existing business infrastructure?

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept and Types of the Cybersecurity Framework

A cybersecurity framework could be defined as the series of documents that denotes the best possible practices for a company to follow to manage its cybersecurity risks to lower the company's vulnerabilities to such exposure. In this age of modernization, companies face immense challenges every day to ensure their critical data and system's security and privacy. To address and mitigate these issues, a firm certainly needs a well-thought and structured cybersecurity plan so that their information technology details could be protected from unauthorized access [9]. There is ample cybersecurity framework guidance available in the business environment. When business leaders look into these, they become more capable of managing the IT security risks in their business infrastructure. Considering an already existing cyber-security framework or developing one internally for solely protecting the company data in the intranet, in both cases, cybersecurity frameworks could be used. There are several kinds of cybersecurity frameworks available in the market, such as;

HIPAA: It is especially applicable for the healthcare industry and those companies who work with the healthcare industries to protect health information in their system to ensure that data's confidentiality.

NIST SP 800-53: This cybersecurity framework is mainly used in federal government agencies. When a substantial

amount of sensitive data flows through the network system, this security framework sheds light on all the required control mechanisms to keep in place for all entities supporting these systems [10].

NIST Cybersecurity Framework: It is the most cost-effective and easy-to-use cybersecurity framework, and due to its flexible nature, it can be used in many sectors. It uses easy language so that business leaders do not need to hire an external specialist and elevate cyber-security standards for companies who do not even know how to begin protecting their datasets.

HITRUST: This is another type of cybersecurity framework applicable only for the healthcare industries and since many IT systems are fragmented. Hence, the cybersecurity measures are not consistently implemented properly, which is why HITRUST can protect those from threats of malware.

ISO 27000 Series: It is primarily used in private sector companies, and there are several standards available for this framework like ISO800-12, ISO800-14, ISO800-26, ISO800-37, and ISO800-53.

NERC1300: This framework is only applicable to bulk power supply companies. Since the power system is an essential phenomenon to modern people, this framework evaluates when the power can be lost and how long it can remain lost.

ANSI/ISA 62443: Industrial automation and control system companies use this security framework. The four-stepped framework helps the organizations check whether they are correctly adhering to the security system's requirements.

NIST Cybersecurity Framework Functions

Almost 30% of the US organizations use the NIST cybersecurity framework, and even for a structured clinical infrastructure in Saudi Arabia, the NIST framework is used. A prominent Saudi Arabian company named Saudi Aramco uses this framework to ensure a high state of governance in the overall cybersecurity approach in all the country's business organizations [11]. The National Institute of Standards and Technology provides a set of guidelines that the private sector companies can abide by for identifying, detecting, and responding to cybersecurity threats. There are five primary functions of this security framework, and they are;

Figure 3: NIST Framework Function

Identification: Business organizations primarily should understand their internal and external environments in order to manage the cybersecurity risks in their assessments, datasets, systems, and capabilities.

Protection: The organizations then need to develop a certain amount of suitable safeguarding frameworks to limit the impact of probable cybersecurity threats.

Detection: Organisations must also apply the proper procedures for identifying and detecting the cybersecurity threats in their network as soon as possible [12].

Response: To contain the response plan of cybersecurity incidents, the companies should also develop response plans.

Recovery: There have to be effective methods for restoring the services or datasets that were hampered in the cyber threat incident.

Benefits of the Cybersecurity Framework

The cybersecurity framework provides a common language that empowers all levels of employees in their supply chain departments to understand a shared language of their cybersecurity risks. The benefits of this framework are;

1. It can protect sensitive information and confidential data from unauthorized access. It is helpful because it can protect both the company's and customers' datasets secure so that the threat to a data breach can never occur in the organization. Thus the threats of ransomware or malware could be avoided.
2. Business continuity management and security could be improved with the help of a cybersecurity framework [13]. When a cyber-threat occurs in a company, their services and datasets are disrupted, at least for a momentary time. So with an appropriate cybersecurity framework, business services would never be ceased.
3. Stakeholder confidence could be improved in the company's information security management. It is an essential spectrum because if stakeholders always fear data breaching, they would not disclose any relevant details to the company managers. So a proper security framework could increase their confidence and decrease their fears of data loss.
4. With proper security controls in place, business infrastructure and company credentials are also improved. It can enable the business to be operated in a much smoother manner, never to disrupt the workflow.
5. In case of a security breach event, the datasets could be recovered faster and efficiently, and thus a greater resilience would be achieved in the cybersecurity landscape. Despite the advanced security frameworks, companies often face malware threats. If the virus can break the firewall, then potential information could be lost, which could be recovered if a cybersecurity framework is put in place.
6. Cybersecurity requirements could be quickly and more efficiently communicated with stakeholders,

and thus a collective understanding could be accomplished of the company's security status [14].

7. An established cybersecurity program could help identify new opportunities for revised security standards. It would help the companies remain updated about the revised standards to obtain new customers and stakeholders through their improved data security management system.
8. It can protect the company from all kinds of threats like fraud, espionage, vandalism, or sabotage, and thus a company could get diverse solutions in their data security platform. Starting from best practice management system to testing physical infrastructure, all could be achieved by implementing a single cybersecurity framework.

Challenges of the Cybersecurity Framework

In a world where everything is accessible through the internet, the biggest challenge, government, business companies, and individuals is to keep their data safe online. There are several types of challenges in the application of cybersecurity framework such as;

Figure 4: Challenges in Data Security

Ransomware Threats

They are the most popular ones in cybersecurity threats. It means hacking into users' data and preventing them from accessing it until a certain amount of ransom is paid anonymously to hackers [15]. More than individuals, the business enterprises face this challenge more, and, in most cases, the hackers do not even release the data even after the ransom is paid to them.

IoT Attacks

According to IoT analytics, IoT devices like laptops, desktop phones, and intelligent security devices can transmit a large amount of data virtually over a network. With the increasing adoption of IoT devices, the rate of IoT attacks has also increased. Since it is easy to access, so the rate is higher than any other cybersecurity threat.

Cloud Attacks

Cloud services are used by many people today for both their personal and professional requirements, and the infamous iCloud attack is the most prevalent cybersecurity threat that has leaked private photos of people and most celebrities. It could pose a massive malicious threat to an organization and could also lead to their untimely collapse [16].

Phishing Attacks

It is a kind of social engineering used by hackers to steal the login credentials or credit card numbers of an individual. In this kind of attack, the hackers exploit the user's credit card until they are made aware of it, and by that time, a lump sum amount of money could get lost in thin air.

Cryptocurrency and Blockchain Attacks

Cryptocurrency and blockchain technology is used in many enterprises nowadays. As mentioned earlier, when hackers conduct the attack, then customer data and business operations could be disrupted significantly. Organizations that use these technologies would have to be more cautious because they have not yet reached their ultimate security stage.

Software Vulnerabilities

Not updating software with its latest available version could cause software vulnerabilities and weaken the system firewall, making it easier for attackers to breach the firewall and steal user data. Even the older software versions often contain lax security patches that developers fix in the newer version [17].

Cybersecurity Framework in the IoT Industry

The Internet of Things (IoT) industry is deployed in the recently developed intelligent grid infrastructure, and as a reason for that cybersecurity framework is growing. The Energy Internet (EI) is an important phenomenon because it inherits all the security vulnerabilities of an existing smart grid. The smart grid's security structure is not quite adequate for meeting the cybersecurity energy needs required by 21st-century citizens. That is why the cybersecurity framework must be so that it can provide ample privacy and security and support the EI in effective energy management [18]. Suppose an identity-based security mechanism (I-ICAAAN) can be used alongside a secured communication protocol and an Intelligent Security System for Energy Management (ISSEM). In that case, privacy and security could be certified in the IoT. In terms of the game theory, it is seen that the Nash equilibrium solution could be applicable in the ISSEM phenomenon in order to evaluate its efficiency regarding the allocations of security events. There is undoubtedly a theoretical analysis and a formal verification applied for providing the required security and data privacy to improve cyber security-based IoT.

With the help of cybersecurity, IoT's omnipresent phenomenon can enable dynamic real-time sensing and spur digital transformation to unlock the digital government's potential. It can also be used for enabling the government to become a data-driven competent government, and the policies and practices beneficial to public value and interest would be easier to provide and monitor [19]. However, the IoT policy is

often filled with challenges that can make the IoT policies and practices questionable. According to IoT cybersecurity policy, it can be found out that some of the major governmental agencies of the world were forwards thinking and strategic in terms of partnering and funding with sub-national governments for eradicating the IoT security challenges.

Agent-Based Modelling in Cybersecurity

To judge complex adaptive systems' behaviours, the Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) simulation technique is used. Some artificial or virtual agents represent the groups or individuals interacting with each other in the complex system, and they follow a predefined set of rules. Cyber systems are the interconnections between two or more software modules, logical circuit wiring, microchip, and between the internet and its users. These actors and interactions could be technically simulated in a model for performing the "what-if" analysis, and thus the impact of changing parameters could be predicted [20]. This model can also be utilized for analyzing the efficiency of response systems to cybersecurity threats by studying user behaviour and application characteristics for a certain period. Since in the real world, an attacker's experience could evolve with experience, so this aspect of agents' behaviour is considered in the genetic engineering algorithms. This phenomenon is helpful because the IT leaders could identify potential attackers' behaviour without evaluating all the use cases and user journeys they have hampered in the past but only through a few mutations and crossovers.

Application of Blockchain Decentralized Cybersecurity Framework

For ages, people have been struggling with exchanging information and transferring cash and other properties via internet web transfers, each of which involves a trustworthy agent. These entities shall ensure a safe exchange and be liable for any errors or violations of confidentiality. During a shift in the web transfer parameter, blockchain technology removes some central authority's need by introducing an immutable and decentralized public ledger. In the process, executing the data transactions and financial transactions becomes easier between multiple parties without any probable cause of security breaches [21]. The transactions are also verified more than once by consensus mechanisms and predefined validation, and that without the affirmation from any central authoritative intermediary. This public directory is a hierarchical database shared between all participants of the network. It guards the manipulation of all transactions between the parties, it is cryptographically safe, and it is a permanent record of the financial or data transactions [22]. One can access the transactions when one wants. However, if they already have authenticated and linked the transactions to a blockchain, it cannot be undone or altered, making the blockchain technology irreversible and immutable. The cost is reduced in this decentralized cybersecurity framework. However, the rate of data loss is

potentially reduced because a singular copy of the information is available in the system network, synchronized among all the participants.

Importance of Cybersecurity Incident Management Framework (CIMF)

There are three major components in the cybersecurity incident management framework: the technological infrastructure, the security operations centre, and the computer emergency response centre. The objectives of CIMF are to eliminate the potential cyber threats before they can occur and minimize the impact of a cybersecurity incident for achieving integrity, confidentiality, and availability of the industry's operations, activities, services, and informative assets. The appropriate implementation of CIMF at the workplace can reduce the danger of a security threat [23]. Cybersecurity incident coordination and management could be better improved in the industry where it is applied. Both direct and indirect costs associated with the cybersecurity incidents could be reduced if a CIMF is put in place. Even the detection of threats and reporting it to the executive management becomes more manageable. Its purpose is to put a consolidated nation mechanism to the management, including the coordination of potential cyber threats with the data security system [24]. It sets out diverse roles and responsibilities to the people who attempt to implement them in the workplace. The business stakeholders and the governmental agencies, critical infrastructure owners, public and private sector partners, and operators any others with whom a company connects are responsible for following the guidelines set by CIMF. Therefore, it is of much significance that the CIMF platform must enable the business enterprises to participate in a coordinated national cyber incident response fully.

V. METHODOLOGY ADOPTED

Methodology in research could be referred to as discussing methods applied systematically by the researcher to collect research data. This chapter occupies a pivotal role in collecting accurate data through the implementation of practical techniques and tools. It is essential to use accurate research methods to reach the desired conclusion and meet pre-identified research objectives.

Research Method

This segment of the current chapter highlights all the tools which have been applied in this study. The table below displays all the research methods used to complete this study

RESEARCH METHODS	TOOLS USED
RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY	Positivism Philosophy
RESEARCH APPROACH	Deductive Approach
RESEARCH DESIGN	Descriptive design

RESEARCH STRATEGY	Thematic analysis
METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION	Qualitative Data Collection
DATA SOURCES	Secondary (books, articles, journals, and websites)
SAMPLING METHOD	Purposive Sampling
SAMPLE SIZE	Ten literary sources, including books, articles, websites

Table 1: Research Methods Used in the Study

Research Onion

Research onion being introduced by Saunders aims to elaborate various stages developing a research study. From the inside of the model to the outside, each layer explains methods adopted for the entire research process. The first and foremost benefit of research onion is that it creates a series of steps under which wide data collection methods can be understood effectively. Different stages depicted in research onion are research philosophy, research design, research approach, data collection method, and others,

Figure 5: Research Onion [25]

Research Philosophy

Research philosophy believes how data about any particular topic or phenomenon shall be collected, analyzed, and applied. From the perceptions of various scholars, research philosophy is all about developing ideas and knowledge in an efficient way that is intense while moving along various stages of the research topic. In addition to this, it also ensures accurate identification of the core research principles. Among the four basic types of research philosophies; Interpretivism, positivism, post-positivism, and realism, the researcher has selected the positivism approach.

The Rationale for Selecting this Philosophy: Positivism philosophy has been chosen by rejecting the remaining paradigms. Positivism allows exploring real-life aspects through a series of critical discussions for investigating and interpreting accumulated data. It has become possible for the researcher to conduct this scientific study of Cyber Security Frameworks through the logical extraction of ideas from relevant sources.

Figure 6: Research Philosophies

Research Approach

Research approaches are procedures and plans for research that span the research steps from broad assumptions to detailed data analysis procedures, collection, and interpretation. Mainly two types of research approaches are used by the researchers while conducting research studies. Under the inductive approach, the premises are viewed through some relevant evidence but without full assurance of the conclusion's truth [26]. On the other hand, the deductive approach revolves around theories, and it involves testing those existing theories.

The Rationale for Selecting this Philosophy: In the current study, the researcher has selected the deductive approach by ignoring the inductive one. Using this, he has become able to reach a logical conclusion. From different analysts' opinions, deductive reasoning goes in the similar pathway as that of the conditionals and connects research premises with a conclusion [27].

Figure 7: Research Approach

Research Design

Research design is a framework of overall research strategies utilized for carrying out research studies. This defines a logical and succinct plan to tackle established research questions and objectives through data accumulation, interpretation, analysis, and discussion. As per research scientists' comments, selecting appropriate research designs helps researchers synchronize various components concerning the topic [28]. In the current study, the researcher has selected an Explanatory research design as it provides a functional explanation and solution to the problem, which demands priorities.

The Rationale for Selecting this Design: The researcher has chosen exploratory design because it has focused on a detailed explanation of various aspects of the topic, Cyber Security framework. By adopting exploratory design, the researcher has gathered a wide range of conceptual information to answer the research questions through requirement fulfillment and suitable solutions.

Figure 8: Research Design

Data Analysis Method

Data analysis methods are specific procedures used to identify, select and analyze information about a given topic. It is the pathway through which the researchers conduct their research and evaluate the research problems. Regarding the research topic, research philosophy, and design, the researcher has developed the paper based on qualitative data analysis. Qualitative research mainly relies on observation, visual or textual analysis. The research has found this method highly effective in demonstrating rich, intuitive secondary data to answer the research question and accomplish the aim. One key advantage of qualitative data collection is that it requires minimum financial resources, whereas the primary disadvantage is that this method raises questions about the research's credibility.

The Rationale for Selecting this Method: The researcher in the current study has chosen the qualitative data analysis method because it contributes to content analysis. As the study has been based on explanatory research design, content analysis from textual or visual sources is exceptionally relevant in this case. Moreover, this method would enable the

researcher to complete the study within the stipulated time frame.

Data Sources

By considering the research topic and objectives, the researcher has selected a secondary data collection method for assimilating accurate information. Insightful secondary data have been gathered from different secondary data sources such as online articles, journals, books, and websites regarding several Cyber Security framework dimensions. In a more detailed manner, the researcher has used various researchers' existing literary works on the current topic to examine the research questions specifically.

Sampling Method

In research, the sample represents a population to ensure that the findings can be generalized from the sample to the entire population. As the present study is based on secondary qualitative data, the researcher has opted for *Purposive sampling* under Non-probability sampling. According to a wide range of research specialists, Purposeful sampling is used in qualitative research papers to select and identify the information-rich cases about the phenomenon of interest. The researcher has used existing judgments of various other experts to analyze the collected data. One of the critical advantages of purposive sampling is that it does not involve real-time data collection procedures. Thus it is one of the most time effective and cost-effective sampling methods.

Ethical Issues

Research ethics mainly govern the necessary standards to conduct scientific studies. Discussion of ethical principles of justice, beneficence, and autonomy are central pillars to the ethical review. It is crucial to adhere to the ethical principles for safeguarding the research components' rights, dignity, and welfare. For the present research study, the knowledge collected from different secondary data sources has not been used commercially. The articles, books, and journals used to jot down relevant data have been accumulated from verified sources. It can be said that the researcher has complied with the standards of the Data Protection Act 1998 in order to avoid social and ethical issues.

Timetable Chart

The research timetable is presented in the form of a Gantt chart.

[Refer to appendix]

Research Limitation

While conducting the research study of Cyber Security Frameworks, the researcher has experienced certain obstacles that have reduced the study's quality and efficiency. There has been a lack of optimum authentic information about the main topic. Apart from these, throughout the entire study, the researcher has faced inadequate financial resources, which is one of the primary reasons for the shortage of information. Additionally, the given time frame has also been inadequate to

complete the topic in a scrutinized way. All these aspects have prohibited the researcher from conducting quantitative data analysis, making the research more feasible.

This chapter mainly exhibits various analytical tools and methods that have enabled the researcher to analyze the topic accurately. By implying practical research philosophy, design, method, and approach, the researcher has developed a logical conclusion. On the contrary, the researcher has come across particular challenges like lack of financial resources and time, which have acted as impediments for successfully elucidating the research topic.

VI. RESULTS – FINDING OF THE PROJECT

The research study's present segment deals with in-depth analysis of the accumulated data using the secondary qualitative data analysis method. In this regard, the researcher has developed perceptive themes on different Cyber Security Frameworks genres through which the information gathered has been elucidated on a critical note. Different textual and visual sources have been utilized to make the data analysis more reliable and credible. Below are presented the data on Cyber Security frameworks in the form of themes:

Cybersecurity is showing emerging importance to the Health Services of Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia is one of the fastest-growing countries in the Middle East in terms of technological progress. It can be found that the health and social care (HSC) system of Saudi Arabia has come across enormous developments over the last ten years, including the use of Information technology (IT). On a detailed note, increasing information technology use has made the healthcare IT infrastructure vulnerable to potential risks like data theft and unauthorized information access. In this aspect, cybersecurity has occupied a pivotal role in the Health and rescue services in Saudi Arabia. By aligning cybersecurity and patient safety initiatives, the Saudi Arabian HSC organizations are promoting patient safety and privacy [29]. In addition to all these, the application of cybersecurity frameworks like HIPAA, GDPR, and FISMA in HSC also ensures continuity in delivering high-quality care services. Some renowned health care organizations in Saudi Arabia, such as King Faisal Specialist Hospital and Research Centre, National Guard Health Affairs, The Public Institution for Social Security, are using application security, antispyware software, firewalls, monitored network access, and two-step authentication system for improving their Cyber Security systems. In addition to this, by providing frequent training to the IT staff, the HSC entities in Saudi Arabia have established a security culture within the health and social care system.

Cybersecurity is Implemented in Smart Grids

To improve reliability and efficiency, Saudi Arabia's government has made a notable investment in developing a more innovative and automated power system using Cyber Security tools. Through Information Communications

Technology (ICT), the power system operators can now control tasks based on data received from remote facilities in the country [30]. Smart grid cybersecurity is a recently developed digital infrastructure that sites above the existing electrical grids. Supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) systems have been introduced in different industries of Saudi Arabia (especially oil and gas industries) to send control commands to the switching devices for online monitoring and operations. However, the energy industries in Saudi Arabia are regulated heavily at multiple levels regarding IT use. Thus, protection circuits, synchronization systems, and control systems are applied to ensure cyber safety, performance, and operational efficiency. Thus, Saudi Arabian Energy industries are indulged in cybersecurity research and development to stabilize smart grids.

Figure 9: Objectives of Cybersecurity in Smart Grid [31]

There exist vulnerabilities in the cybersecurity infrastructures of Saudi Arabian companies

In computer security infrastructures, vulnerability can be recognized as the weakness exploited by threat actors like attackers, malware, or ransomware. The IT sector, energy sector, and healthcare sector in Saudi Arabia have been adopting security measures for protecting their cyber networks from unauthorized access. For a country like Saudi Arabia, potential threats and risks posed to cyberspace mainly revolve around state-sponsored attacks, cybercrimes, cyber terrorism, and digital data interception. Cyber in the country is rising faster because of the increasing use of digital services, lack of optimum information security knowledge, weak cybersecurity infrastructure, and employee errors. Below are highlighted some of the very cybersecurity vulnerabilities prevalent in Saudi Arabia:

- 1. Inaccurate Input Validation:** In cybersecurity networks, input validation is an effective technique to add an extra security layer for preventing attackers' access. However, inaccurate input validation leads to illegitimate data into the cyber system of IT and energy companies in Saudi Arabia.
- 2. Buffer Overflow:** Because of accurate input validation, the system experiences buffer overflow vulnerabilities, which may arise due to programming errors. Moreover, this gives rise to more vulnerabilities like heap-based or stack-based buffer overflow, allowing remote code execution on the host network [32].

3. Lack of Bound Checking: The absence of proper bound checking results in crashed and misbehaving programs. On the other hand, results due to invalid inputs are inserted into the array, causing the programs' interrupted service [33]. This allows the attackers to inject unexpected data and modification of the program execution.

4. Poor Quality of Coding: It has been found that several attacker groups in Saudi Arabia have become successful in penetrating the weak cybersecurity infrastructures of companies because of their poor coding quality. This makes the programs vulnerable because good programming practices and network maintenance practices are not followed. Additionally, the malformed input vulnerabilities caused due to poor coding practices create Null Pointer Dereference where the pointer is NULL, although it is expected to be valid [34].

5. Improper Authentication: Cyber-attacks happen in Saudi Arabian business entities, particularly educational, IT, and energy companies, because of vulnerabilities like faulty authentication mechanisms. The software allows other methods for bypassing authentication, and the attackers exploit this to receive unauthorized access to the network. In this way, vital information and business intellectual properties can be extracted by modifying the client credentials [35].

6. Poor Network Design: A poorly designed network that does not deploy in-depth defense strategies can be regarded as another significant vulnerability to Saudi Arabian companies' poor cyber network infrastructures. These types of networks do not deploy multiple security layers and use relatively flat networks without any zones, perimeters and port security. It widens the pathways for the attackers to invade and steal sensitive data.

7. Firewall issues: Improperly configured firewalls allow unauthorized data to move among multiple networks without proper checks. The attackers use this opportunity and allow the malware to be spread across the networks. Non-existent firewalls cause leakage of confidential business information which unauthorized individuals' access.

Known Cyberattacks in Saudi Arabia

Over recent years, some of the highest numbers of cyber threat incidents have been found in Saudi Arabia. In 2015, over 5500 IT specialists from 26 different countries worldwide had identified that Cybersecurity incidents have severely impacted 40% of companies in Saudi Arabia. On the other hand, in 2012, Saudi Arabian Oil Company's (Saudi Aramco) computer network had been compromised the malware was inserted into the organization's network through a flash drive [36]. This attack had erased the hard drives of the systems and also destroyed enormous essential data. In addition to this, during 2015, Kaspersky Lab discovered cyber espionage named Desert Falcons, whose primary aim was to target Middle East countries with a particular focus on Saudi Arabia to be its activity platforms in Saudi. In this case, phishing attacks via social networks and e-mails were used for sending malicious payloads.

Furthermore, King Saud University's (KSU) official website got hacked by unknown groups of hackers. A robust database of 812 students was hacked at first and then leaked on the internet. The country is becoming a significant target of cyber-attacks, including 'Shamoon Virus', which destroys computers by removing disks. This has posed a significant hit in both the petrochemical firms and government ministries in 2017. Recently, with the Corona Virus boom in 2021, Saudi Arabia has visualized a surge in cyber-attacks due to improper maintenance of computer networks because of company lockdown. There has been a sharp rise in malware (37%) and ransomware (29%) in the Middle East, particularly in Saudi Arabia. According to several IT specialists of the country, the need for scalable and resilient cloud solutions has exponentially increased since March 2020 as several organizations are managing remote work conditions in an unprepared manner. Thus, most Saudi Arabian companies are non-compliant with frameworks like ISO 27001, ISO 27002, SOC2, HIPAA, HITRUST, and NERC1300. It can be commented that with an increase in the numbers of internet users in Saudi Arabia, the chances of cybersecurity threats have been increasing in leaps and bounds.

The chapter is based on qualitative data analysis, where various perspectives of other scholars have been taken into account to analyze the topic. The accumulated qualitative data from different literary sources have been explained in short informative themes for collecting core elements of the research topic. In this way, it has become easier for the researcher to answer the framed research question persuasively.

Figure 10: Common Cybersecurity Vulnerabilities that occur in Saudi Arabia

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

SMART Recommendation 1: Creating Secured Cyber Ecosystem

Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Realistic	Time Bound
This recommendation is specific because it would allow the companies to have a robust cyber-security methodology where the cyber devices will work with each other for preventing future cyber attacks	It is measurable because a robust cyber ecosystem exhibits three symbiotic structures using which the companies can measure their cybersecurity performance; Authentication, Interoperability and Automation	This strategy is easily achieved by implementing advanced security measures like Blockchain technology, solid firewalls, and high-quality coding.	This recommendation is realistic because it is possible to be achieved quickly and would enhance cyber resilience and decision-making procedures.	The time limit for implementing this strategy is two months

Table 2: Recommendation 1

SMART Recommendation 2: Providing Intensive Training to IT Employees of Saudi Arabian Companies

Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Realistic	Time Bound
This recommendation is specific because it would increase the cybersecurity awareness and skills among employees through proper education and mentoring	It is measurable because the post-optimized skills and increased efficiency gained by employees after training in developing advanced security methods will strengthen the existing cybersecurity strategies.	It is achievable by frequent coaching sessions with peers and leaders, information sharing, in-depth learning, and continuous monitoring	It is a hyper-realistic strategy because providing cybersecurity training to employees is feasible to prevent a data breach, intellectual property disclosure, and information leakage.	The time limit for implementing this strategy is three months

Table 3: Recommendation 2

SMART Recommendation 3: Strengthening Regulatory Strategies

Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Realistic	Time Bound
This strategy is specific because it directly impacts compliance with regulatory standards (ISO 27001, ISO 27002, SOC2, HIPAA, HITRUST, and NERC1300) by addressing the non-compliances in various entities.	It is measurable because by ensuring cyber regulatory strategies, the business entities can comply with the necessary cybersecurity frameworks.	This strategy can be efficiently achieved by introducing inter-business policies, standards, and governing rules	It is realistic because companies can formulate rules and regulations concerning cybersecurity frameworks for achieving resilient cyber programs	The time limit for implementing this strategy is 1.5 month

Table 4: Recommendation 3

VIII. CONCLUSION

From the study above, it could be concluded that ensuring a robust Cyber Security Framework is a highly essential business practice that contemporary organizations need to follow for managing cyber threats. It has been found that such frameworks (ISO 27001, ISO 27002, SOC2, HIPAA, HITRUST, NERC1300) upgrade the ethical standards of a business entity by reducing the exposure to series of vulnerabilities. In a country like Saudi Arabia, where the use of information technology has become prevalent in almost all aspects of life and with the growth of companies has tripled, Saudi Regulatory bodies (SAMA, NCA, MCIT & CMA) came up with regulatory and cybersecurity frameworks which are an abstract of NIST & CIS to address several threats. It can be identified that the internet security awareness among the IT employees of Saudi Arabian companies is considerably low but better than most of the other nations, and thus they lack organized threats. Some specific sectors in the country, including energy, education, financial, and healthcare, can be identified as top-notch targets for the attackers. In this context, various cybersecurity threats that need to be addressed

immediately are phishing, cloud attacks, IoT attacks, ransomware threats, and software crashes. Through secondary qualitative data analysis, it can be known that the prevailing vulnerabilities to the Cyberinfrastructure of Saudi Arabian entities are inauthentic input validation, poor coding practices, weak network designs, firewall issues, buffer overflow, and others. The COVID 19 scenario was challenging across the globe for almost all companies to accommodate work from home securely. This has uplifted the cybersecurity attacks because of un-strategic working conditions in some companies, thereby leading to the disclosure of credential information, intellectual properties, confidential data to unknown groups. Continuous training, regulatory strategies, and the cyber ecosystem can upgrade the cybersecurity performance of companies efficaciously.

IX. REFERENCES

- [1]. Alassafi, M. O., Alharthi, A., Walters, R. J., & Wills, G. B. (2017). A framework for critical security factors that influence the decision of cloud adoption by Saudi government agencies. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(7), 996-1010.
Retrieved From:
https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/412432/1/A_framework_for_critical_security_factors_that_influence_the_decision_of_cloud_adoption_by_Saudi_government_agencies_003.pdf
- [2]. Statista (2021) *Respondents in risk of data loss*
Retrieved From:
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1041552/saudi-arabia-likelihood-breach-personal-data>
- [3]. Statista (2021) *Respondents in risk of data loss*
Retrieved from:
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1041552/saudi-arabia-likelihood-breach-personal-data>
- [4]. Research gate (2021) *Saudi Aramco cyber-attacks*
Retrieved from:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326975373_Cyber_Attack_on_Saudi_Aramco
- [5]. IJCSI (2021) *Cyber security detailed knowledge in Saudi Arabians*
Retrieved from:
<https://www.ijcsi.org/papers/IJCSI-13-6-129-135.pdf>
- [6]. Core (2021) *Cybersecurity incidents in Saudi Arabia*
Retrieved from:
<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/322474772.pdf>
- [7]. Mawgoud, A. A., Taha, M. H. N., Khalifa, N. E. M., & Loey, M. (2019, October). Cyber security risks in MENA region: threats, challenges and countermeasures. In *International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Systems and Informatics* (pp. 912-921). Springer, Cham.
Retrieved from:
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ahmed_A_Mawgoud/publication/336219647_Cyber_Security_Risks_in_MENA_Region_on_Threats_Challenges_and_Countermeasures/links/5fb379fe299bf10c3686141a/Cyber-Security-Risks-in-MENA-Region-Threats-Challenges-and-Countermeasures.pdf
- [8]. Computer Weekly (2021) *Cybersecurity attacks increase during pandemic*
Retrieved from:
<https://www.computerweekly.com/news/252489175/Saudi-Arabia-sees-cyber-security-boom-as-coronavirus-bites#:~:text=As%20the%20virus%20ramped%20up,started%20spreading%20in%20the%20region>
- [9]. Sohal, A. S., Sandhu, R., Sood, S. K., & Chang, V. (2018). A cybersecurity framework to identify malicious edge device in fog computing and cloud-of-things environments. *Computers & Security*, 74, 340-354.
Retrieved from:
https://research.tees.ac.uk/ws/files/16202354/cybersecurity_C_andS_accepted.pdf
- [10]. Srinivas, J., Das, A. K., & Kumar, N. (2019). Government regulations in cyber security: Framework, standards and recommendations. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 92, 178-188.
Retrieved from:
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Srinivas_Jangirala/publication/328183318_Government_regulations_in_cyber_security_Framework_standards_and_recommendations/links/5c1d53d892851c22a33d339e/Government-regulations-in-cyber-security-Framework-standards-and-recommendations.pdf
- [11]. Barrett, M. P. (2018). Framework for improving critical infrastructure cybersecurity. *National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, USA, Tech. Rep.*
Retrieved from:
http://isawaterwastewater.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/WWAC-2018-NIST-Barrett_final.pdf
- [12]. Ibrahim, A., Valli, C., McAteer, I., & Chaudhry, J. (2018). A security review of local government using NIST CSF: a case study. *The Journal of Supercomputing*, 74(10), 5171-5186.
Retrieved from:
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11227-018-2479-2>
- [13]. Gordon, L. A., Loeb, M. P., & Zhou, L. (2020). Information Segmentation and Investing in Cybersecurity. *Journal of Information Security*, 12(1), 115-136.
Retrieved from:
<https://academic.oup.com/cybersecurity/article-pdf/6/1/tyaa005/32979473/tyaa005.pdf>

- [14]. Zhang, Z. J., He, W., Li, W., & Abdous, M. H. (2021). Cybersecurity awareness training programs: a cost-benefit analysis framework. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*. Retrieved from: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IMDS-08-2020-0462/full/html>
- [15]. Ghafur, S., Grass, E., Jennings, N. R., & Darzi, A. (2019). The challenges of cybersecurity in health care: the UK National Health Service as a case study. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 1(1), e10-e12. Retrieved from: [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/article/PIIS2589-7500\(19\)30005-6/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/article/PIIS2589-7500(19)30005-6/fulltext)
- [16]. Mantha, B. R., & de Soto, B. G. (2019). Cyber security challenges and vulnerability assessment in the construction industry. In *Creative Construction Conference 2019* (pp. 29-37). Budapest University of Technology and Economics. Retrieved from: <https://repozitorium.omikk.bme.hu/bitstream/handle/10890/13197/CCC2019-005.pdf?sequence=1>
- [17]. Mendhurwar, S., & Mishra, R. (2019). Integration of social and IoT technologies: architectural framework for digital transformation and cyber security challenges. *Enterprise Information Systems*, 1-20. Retrieved from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/17517575.2019.1600041>
- [18]. Mozzaquatro, B. A., Agostinho, C., Goncalves, D., Martins, J., & Jardim-Goncalves, R. (2018). An ontology-based cybersecurity framework for the internet of things. *Sensors*, 18(9), 3053. Retrieved from: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/18/9/3053/pdf>
- [19]. Radanliev, P., Montalvo, R. M., Cannady, S., Nicolescu, R., De Roure, D., Nurse, J. R., & Huth, M. (2019). Cyber Security Framework for the Internet-of-Things in Industry 4.0. Retrieved from: https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/201903.0111/download/final_file
- [20]. Thompson, B., & Morris-King, J. (2018). An agent-based modeling framework for cybersecurity in mobile tactical networks. *The Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation*, 15(2), 205-218. Retrieved from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/1548512917738858>
- [21]. Han, Y., Wang, Z., Ruan, Q., & Fang, B. (2018). Sapiens chain: a blockchain-based cybersecurity framework. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1811.10868*. Retrieved from: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.10868>
- [22]. Puthal, D., Malik, N., Mohanty, S. P., Kougianos, E., & Yang, C. (2018). The blockchain as a decentralized security framework [future directions]. *IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine*, 7(2), 18-21. Retrieved from: http://www.smohanty.org/Publications_Journals/2018/Mohanty_IEEE-CEM_2018-Mar_The-Blockchain.pdf
- [23]. Onwubiko, C., & Ouazzane, K. (2020). SOTER: A playbook for cybersecurity incident management. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*. Retrieved from: http://repository.londonmet.ac.uk/5358/1/TEM%20paper%20on%20SOTER_Camera_Ready%20Version_1.5_Nov2019.pdf
- [24]. Naseer, H., Maynard, S. B., & Desouza, K. C. (2021). Demystifying analytical information processing capability: The case of cybersecurity incident response. *Decision Support Systems*, 143, 113476. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923620302311>
- [25]. Saunders, M. N., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A., & Bristow, A. (2015). Understanding research philosophy and approaches to theory development. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: <http://oro.open.ac.uk/53393>
- [26]. Ørngreen, R., & Levinsen, K. (2017). Workshops as a Research Methodology. *Electronic Journal of E-learning*, 15(1), 70-81. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1140102.pdf>
- [27]. da Silva, C. S. R. (2017). Research design-the new perspective of research methodology. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 1-12. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: <http://journaljesbs.com/index.php/JESBS/article/download/16285/30216>
- [28]. Cuervo-Cazurra, A., Mudambi, R., Pedersen, T., & Piscitello, L. (2017). Research methodology in global strategy research. *Global Strategy Journal*, 7(3), 233-240. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: http://centaur.reading.ac.uk/84151/3/CuervoMudambiPedersenPiscitello_Method_23May.pdf
- [29]. Shafqat, N., & Masood, A. (2016). Comparative analysis of various national cyber security strategies. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, 14(1), 129. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: https://www.academia.edu/21451805/Comparative_Analysis_of_Various_National_Cyber_Security_Strategies

[30]. Sun, C. C., Hahn, A., & Liu, C. C. (2018). Cyber security of a power grid: State-of-the-art. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, 99, 45-56. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: http://credc.com/sites/default/files/papers/2017_Q4_ContMonitor_published.pdf

[31]. Bîrleanu F.G., Angheliescu P., Bizon N., & Pricop E. (2019). Cyber Security Objectives and Requirements for Smart Grid. In: Kabalci E., Kabalci Y. (eds) Smart Grids and Their Communication Systems. Energy Systems in Electrical Engineering. Springer, Singapore. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-1768-2_17

[32]. Ani, U. P. D., He, H., & Tiwari, A. (2017). Review of cybersecurity issues in industrial critical infrastructure: manufacturing in perspective. *Journal of Cyber Security Technology*, 1(1), 32-74. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/23742917.2016.1252211>

[33]. Khan, S. R., & Gouvia, L. B. (2017). Cybersecurity attacks: Common vulnerabilities in the critical infrastructure. *PASJ International Journal of Computer Science (IIJCS)*, 5(6), 7-14. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Luis_Borges_Gouveia/publication/319800931_Cybersecurity_Attacks_Common_Vulnerabilities_in_the_Critical_Infrastructure/links/5db861154585151435d15c7b/Cybersecurity-Attacks-Common-Vulnerabilities-in-the-Critical-Infrastructure.pdf

[34]. Ogie, R. I. (2017, February). Cyber security incidents on critical infrastructure and industrial networks. In *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Computer and Automation Engineering* (pp. 254-258). Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: <http://ro.uow.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1217&context=smartpapers>

[35]. Khan, S. R., & Gouvia, L. B. (2017). Cybersecurity attacks: Common vulnerabilities in the critical infrastructure. *PASJ International Journal of Computer Science (IIJCS)*, 5(6), 7-14. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Luis_Borges_Gouveia/publication/319800931_Cybersecurity_Attacks_Common_Vulnerabilities_in_the_Critical_Infrastructure/links/5db861154585151435d15c7b/Cybersecurity-Attacks-Common-Vulnerabilities-in-the-Critical-Infrastructure.pdf

[36]. Alzahrani, A. and Alomar, K., 2016. Information security issues and threats in Saudi Arabia: A research survey. *International Journal of Computer Science Issues (IJCSI)*, 13(6), p.129. Retrieved on 18th March 2021 from: <https://www.ijcsi.org/papers/IJCSI-13-6-129-135.pdf>

X. APPENDIX

Research Timeline

Activities	1st to 2nd week	3rd to 4th weeks	5th to 6th weeks	7th to 8th week	9th to 10th week	11th week
Topic selection						
Research structure						
Literature review						
Primary/Secondary data collection						
Formation of the research plan						
Recognition of the research technique						
Data analysis						
Conclusion and recommendation						
Submission of the research report						

A Noble Cost Effective Distributed Electronic Health System for Patient Data Handling: Bangladesh Perspectives

Uzzal Kumar Prodhan
Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering
Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University
Trishal, Mymensingh, Bangladesh
uzzal_bagerhat@yahoo.com

Md Sadiq Iqbal, Md Nasim Akter
Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering
Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
sadiq.iqbal@bu.edu.bd

Khusbun Nahar Anita, Md. Forhad Alam, Al Amin
Hossain
Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering
Bangladesh University
Dhaka, Bangladesh
khusbunnaharanita@gmail.com

Md. Mazharul Islam
Special Inspector (ICT)
Civil Aviation Authority of Bangladesh
rohitalislam@gmail.com

Abstract—Health system is one of the vital components for the people of any country. The use of electronic health in Bangladesh is very limited. As a result, health cost is increasing day by day and the poor people of Bangladesh could not bear the increased health cost. In this study, we are going to propose and develop a cost effective distributed electronic health system for patient data handling considering Bangladesh perspectives. By using this model, both patients and doctors will be connected through our developed system. We have used open source electronic health system, business process diagram and distributed characteristics of health system in this research. We have successfully shown from the result section that this model works as a distributed electronic health system. Our developed system is interoperable and cost effective which are the noble characteristics. Health data of patients are easily distributed and managed through the developed system. Finally, we can conclude that the developed system will change the current health system of Bangladesh and bring a new dimension for the healthcare sector.

Keywords- *Interoperable; business process diagram; electronic health system; electronic health record; directorate general of health service*

I. INTRODUCTION

A health system refers a number of health professionals providing health services to people individually or with the help of institutions and combination of various medical resources. At present, for the blessing of information and communication technology into electronic health system where health services can be provided and taken by electronic medium that is more accessible, secure and cost-effective. Most of the developed countries initiated distributed electronic health system to make the system more worthy. On the other hand, developing countries are also trying to introduce this kind of

distributed electronic health system. Very unfortunately, they are still struggling because of the complexity of the system.

For any nation, a well-organized health system is must which ensures proper health services to the people. As we know, healthy people are blessing for any nation, they are more productive and evaluated the economic growth for the country. Electronic health system plays a vital role for ensuring a well program health service for the people of developing countries. When people meet any medical issues, they can seek help from electronic health system. Like the developing countries, Bangladesh also needs electronic health system and it will be more effective if we introduce distributed electronic health system.

Medical data are increasing rapidly day by day and it is necessary to deal with large amounts of Electronic Health Record (EHR). For dealing with these problems, a hybrid approach that combines the advantages of static and dynamic approaches are generated [1]. Haridimos Kondylakis and other researchers worked on the implementation of a data management infrastructure for big health-care data in 2018. Authors introduced an effective and efficient method of patient data handling [2].

Bangladesh is a small country with huge number of populations. The ratio of population and doctor in Bangladesh is very low. The financial status of the major people of Bangladesh is very critical. It is very difficult to give healthcare to people in rural and remote communities of the developing world [3]. Health cost of the people is also very high. Maintaining a proper health system has become a great challenge for Bangladesh. As the health system of Bangladesh

is not proper to meet the needs of its people in comparison with other developed and developing countries.

TABLE I. POPULATION HEALTH WORKFORCE OF BANGLADESH

S.N	Description of the facilities	Ratio	Year
1	Physicians per 1000 people	0.581	2018
2	Nurses and Midwives per 1000 people	0.412	2018
3	Specialist surgical workforce per 1000 people	2.91	2018
4	Community Health worker per 1000 people	0.476	2012
5	Hospital beds per 1000 people	0.8	2015

Table 1 shows the current statistics of health worker with respect of the population in Bangladesh. From the figure, we can see that there are less numbers of doctors than patients, less numbers of well-trained medical professionals in Bangladesh. If we want to serve the medical treatment to huge number of patients, we need to develop an electronic health system in such a way so that we can minimize the health cost and manage health data efficiently.

According to the directorate general of health service (DGHS) of Bangladesh, health facilities are distributed in Bangladesh for the population of Bangladesh as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Health system structure of Bangladesh

Ward, Union and Upazila level hospitals of Bangladesh provides the primary health care facilities. District, divisional and national level hospitals of Bangladesh provides the secondary health care facilities to the people. Special health care facilities are given to the people have provided by the secondary level hospitals.

In order to ensure the health care facilities for the people of Bangladesh, government has taken different initiatives for the people though telemedicine service. Figure 2 shows a scenario of these types of arrangements in Union level.

Figure 2. Telemedicine services of Union level hospitals of Bangladesh

According to figure 2, government has provided laptop with camera and internet to the Union level hospitals. Local doctors register patients and get primary signs from them and send these to the expert doctors. Expert doctors communicate with the local patients through a video conferencing system. Based on the conversation and the provided data from the local doctors, expert doctors provide a medication plan and it is then delivered to the patients from the Union level hospital. This telemedicine service saves time and money for the local patients of Bangladesh.

Figure 3. Telemedicine services model through Mobile

The government of Bangladesh has also created 24 hours health-care facility though mobile as shown in figure 4. Through this model, people can talk directly with the doctors in 24 hours for emergency health service though mobile calls. This initiative enables patient to be connected with the doctors through mobile and they are getting a minimum emergency health service from a doctor.

Bangladesh government taken many initiatives for improving their health system using electronic health system and this system will be more effective if Bangladesh government introduce distributed electronic health system. Electronic health system provides us the facilities of managing health data efficiently. Patients sometime change their geographical positions for a variety of reasons. If they are unable to produce their health record in the changed position, they will have to do the health check-up again and their health cost increases. So, there is necessity to initiate some form of health system to meet these problems. Distributed electronic health system will create the path to overcome the challenges. This research proposes and implemented distributed electronic health system to offer most advanced health system for Bangladesh and also prelude for future.

This paper is organized into five sections. Section one presents the introduction of the research, section two highlights the literature review where recent related literatures were critically reviewed, section three depicts the materials and methods section, section four shows the results of the research and section five finally concludes with the conclusion section.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In this section, we have reviewed some of the recently published literatures and conference papers with a view to find out the recent advancement on distributed electronic health system. Literature review helps us to address the current advancement, technology used, and future direction. The limitations are addressed and overcome in the proposed research.

Md. Rakibul Hoque, Md. Fahim Ahsan Mazmun and Yukun Bao describe and evaluate the current status of e-health in Bangladesh. In this paper, they also describe the initiatives taken by the government of Bangladesh in e-health system. Bangladesh government and private organizations have taken different initiatives on health system using ICT [5].

Uzzal Kumar Prodhon, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman and Israt Jahan conducted a survey on the telemedicine services in Bangladesh and they found that 66.23% doctors in hospital are not connected with telemedicine system. 94.80% doctors and 91.42% patients want to introduce this system. This paper proposed that telemedicine operating cost in the range of 201-300 tk. Author conducted the survey through questionnaires they made for local people, local doctors and expert doctors [6].

Tanvir Ahmed, Henry Lucas, Azfar Sadun Khan, Rubana Islam, Abbas Bhuiy and Mohammad Iqbal had explored 26 ehealth and mhealth initiatives in Bangladesh. The most initiatives are performed in private sector. The common initiatives include tele-consultation, prescription and referral [7].

Uzzal Kumar Prodhon, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman, Israt Jahan, Ahsin Abid, Mohtasim Bellah developed a portable telemedicine tool kit for remote diagnosis of patients which is low cost and easily accessible. Because of their tool kit and the developed system, a rural person does not need to travel to the urban area hospital. Their low cost portable tool kit can collect seven vital signs of patients through sensor. Their developed system is able to show the real time data of patients to the doctor [8].

A low cost security system for telemedicine service is developed by Toufik Ahmed, Uzzal Kumar Prodhon, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman and Israt Jahan considering the cost and efficient in performance. The system follows the recommendation of HL7 and FHIR also consider the HIPPA and NEHTA for security and privacy of a health system. In this paper they have included five sections where security measures are implemented. Bluetooth connection, Mobile Application user authentication, Mobile Application security, Sensor Data security, Server securities are applied in their system [9].

Md. Sadiq Iqbal, Md. Nasim Akter, Md. Imran Hossain, Shaikh Imran Hossain, Md. Aminul Reza Siam, Uzzal Kumar

Prodhon reviewed eight different models of patient data handling. They suggested distributed data can be an alternate choice for region-wise health data will be stored in the local database. This paper proposed Raspberry Pi based client model for the patient data handling [10].

Saroj Kanta Mishra, Indra Pratap Singh, Repu Daman Chand bring out the current status of telemedicine network in India and also visualize the future perspective. They describe the initiatives taken by the government of India, the state government and also some of private sectors. The government of India launched some pilot projects such as SAARC (South Asian Association of Regional Co-operation) telemedicine network, Pan-African e-network project [11].

Richard Wootton found that telemedicine brings clinical benefit in a cost effective way. In this paper, he reviewed the present evidence and also brought the need of telemedicine in future [12].

Niamat Ullah, Pervez Khan, Najnin Sultana and Kyung Sup Kwak describe the past and present health care system of Pakistan and also discuss about present telemedicine project taken by the government and private hospitals. In this paper, they propose a remote telemedicine system for rural area. They proposed a star networking central controlling model which is connected to the service center in rural area. According to their model, rural people can also take service from specialized doctor from urban areas and it's a store and forward base model [13].

In this research, Rashid L. Bashshur, Timothy G. Reardor and Gary W. Shannon describe the brief history of telemedicine from where telemedicine came out. Researcher added that, telemedicine service should be cost effective, accessible and ensure quality health service [14].

In this article, Shengnan Chen, Alice Cheng and Khanjan Mehta discuss about telemedicine business model. Researcher has chosen Alexander Osterwalder's "Business Model Canvas" which is composed of nine building blocks. Here they selected eight telemedicine ventures and divide the venture into two categories like developed and developing countries. The developed world mainly targets the organization and companies and on the other hand developing countries mainly target individual because of poor economical state [15].

Sapal Techkra, X.H. Wang, Robert S.H. Istepanian and Y.H. Song briefly described the mobile e-health. Mobile telecommunication technology is improved day by day and researcher explains it here with full description. To provide emergency treatment mobile telemedicine system need to implement [16].

IEEE 802.11 wireless standard to QoS (Quality of Service) support within wireless e-health services was investigated by PhD Anna Zvikhachevskaya, Prof. Garik Markarian and Dr.

Lyudmila Mihaylova. In this paper, they discussed about different types of handoff in digital system like hard handoff, soft handoff and softer handoff. Handoff is a complex function which introduces the uninterrupted communication of an ongoing call. This approach was used to save life of critical patients [17].

From the literature review section, we have found that there are scopes to introduce distributed electronic health system for Bangladesh. The introduction of this approach is very limited and if we want to deliver a cost effective efficient health service to the people of Bangladesh we should introduce distributed electronic health system.

III. METATERIALS AND METHODS

To develop a successful distributed electronic health system for Bangladesh, three modules were introduced in this research. The modules are based on patients, doctors and administrator activities where each module interconnected to each other. The distributed electronic health system has been developed following a mesh connectivity system where each health system will be distributed to different servers and each server will be connected to each other so that they can pass data frequently. Following figure 4 is the developed mesh connectivity diagram of the system. The developed system shows only the connectivity with the four divisions. We can easily extend the developed system to more divisions as needed.

Figure 4. Block diagram of developed distributed electronic health system

Figure 5 shows a Business Process Diagram (BPD) diagram of distributed electronic health system has been developed. Based on the figure 4, there are three main processes in the BPD diagram. These are patient module, doctor module and administrator module. The system activities start from the registration of patients. As soon as, a patient gets registered and apply for an appointment to any specific doctors, the request will be forwarded to the doctor. Patients will get proper treatment according their report and health information. The administrator will validate all kinds of data and update any data if necessary. Further details of the module are discussed in the following section.

Figure 5. BPD diagram of developed distributed electronic health system

A. Patient's Module

In order to get any service from the developed distributed electronic health system, patients will have to get registered first. A unique ID is generated to any patient. Registered patients will have to login to the electronic health system and apply for an appointment to any doctor they want. After getting the appointment, the patient will have to provide some of the other health information as per demand of the patient and communicate with the doctor if needed. The patient and doctor must validate their information through the system. Patients can get the prescription from the system and they will make the payment of the service through this module.

B. Doctor's Module

Doctors are one of the most vital components of the developed system. Patients get connected with the doctor through the system. In order to give telemedicine service to the patients, doctors will have to register first. When any patient is registered with the doctor, registered doctor will be notified for new appointments through the system. Doctor can approve or decline the appointment. After successful log-in with the system, doctors can get the history of patients by using unique patient ID. After communicate with the patient, doctor prepares a medication plan and delivers the medication plan to the patients.

C. Administrator Module

In order to run and maintain the system, administrator will validate all the necessary information of the patient and doctor for registration and provide unique ID and password. Administrator manages the system and also updates the patient

and the doctor profile if necessary. Administrator is responsible for smooth functioning of the system.

D. Augmented Activity Diagram of Developed Model

Figure 6 show agents interaction of the developed distributed electronic health system. There are three agents in the model such as patient, doctor and admin. Every agent is interacted with each other according to the goal of the research. The activities of patient and doctor are presented in the figure 6. Patients have to register with their valid information and login to the system. Then request for appointment and get notify for service. After that process the payment, communicate with doctor and received the prescription. Doctor also registers with their valid information and login to the system. Approved appointment and received patient history. Then review patients and generate prescription for the patient. Distributed electronic health system admin manage and maintain the whole system for proper functioning.

Figure 6. Augmented activity diagram of developed distributed electronic health system

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We have implemented our system as per the design of the block diagram and BPD diagram. We have successfully used an open source electronic health system for our research work and connected our health systems according to design. We have customized the health system according to our need which is suitable for Bangladesh. We have distributed our health system and successfully connected the health module and get the health service. We have also checked for the case of geographical change patients and got correct results. This approach removes the dependency of the centralized health system and offers the benefits of distributed system. If any health system fails, it is easy to deliver the health service to

the patients of the failed node. As a result, we can continue our health services for any rural people of Bangladesh.

Now, we are going to present some of the section-wise output here for the acceptance of the system. At first, users need to register in the distributed electronic health system with their valid information. Figure 7 shows the registration of user as output. The users may be patient or doctor.

Figure 7. Registration status of new users of the developed system

After registering into the system, the user gets a username and password for log-in into the system. Every user can enter the system with user login password. Figure 8 shows the log-in status of user from the developed system.

Figure 8. Login window of the user from the system

User interface of the developed system is shown in figure 9. From this interface, every service is initiated from window. Patients, doctors, payment, report, maintenance and other services are initiated from here.

Figure 9. User interface of the developed system

Both doctors and patients are registered into the system first to get or deliver healthcare service. Our system can successfully register the user as shown in the figure 10. Doctors can use their patients detail from this list and prescribe medicine for them. Patients can also select category-

wise doctors from the doctors list and get medical treatment from the respective doctors.

Figure 10. Doctors and patients list from the developed system

Most of the doctors want to know the patients history for the proper treatment of the patients. In traditional system, patients need to carry health record manually or patient's record is kept in the server of a particular hospital. In Bangladesh health data are not interoperable among the hospitals. We have overcome this problem through the use of open source distributed electronic health system. Now, patient's health history is now interoperable with other health system and can be used from any node as shown in the figure 11.

Figure 11. Interoperable patients health record from the developed system

When a patient is registered into the system, the administrator assigns a specific doctor for the treatment of the patient. After completing the registration system, the doctor can see the appointment status for his patients and patient is also get information from the system about the appointment confirmation. Figure 12 shows the appointment status of the patient with the doctor.

Figure 12. Appointment request status of a patient to a specific doctor

After successful appointment, consultation is made by using our developed system. Here both patient and doctor interacts each other for the treatment of the patient. Administrator helps both parties for the successful completion of the consultation. Figure 13 shows the patient's document and final report.

Figure 13. Patients documents and report section

We have made our system distributed in nature. As a result, we can access our system from any node any time. System failure of any node would not hamper to the whole health system. If any patient changes their geographical position, he/she can get the medical service from the changed position easily. Patient's history of one node can be easily accessed from other node. We can easily find the patients information through our system. Doctors can easily get the patients diagnostic information from our system. So, they can provide quality and efficient care to the patients. Figure 14 shows the accessibility status from any device.

Figure 14. Accessibility status of the system from anywhere

After successful consultation is completed, doctors will give a medication plan to the patient. The medication plan is printed from the service delivery point. System administrator will assist to the patient for getting the prescription. Figure 15 shows the prescription generated from our developed system.

Figure 15. Prescription of the patients from the system

We have also included the billing section in our model. By using our system, each patient can easily get the financial status easily and can pay the bill. Collected amount is automatically distributed to the concerned parties. Figure 16 shows the billing section from the developed system.

Figure 16. Patients billing system from the system

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have successfully designed and developed a noble distributed electronic health system for patient data handling. In this study, we have used four nodes as a distributed environment where our customized electronic health system is running. According to the design of our system, we have registered patients in one node and he/she is able to get his medical service from any other node. We have made our design in a cost effective way so that this model is effective for the rural general people of any country of the world including Bangladesh. We have the health system which is more flexible and efficient. Billing, medication plan, accessibility, inter-operability and usefulness are the key characteristics of the developed health system. Finally, we can say that our developed distributed electronic health system will play a great role for the advancement of the health system of Bangladesh.

REFERENCES

[1] Bernhard G. Humm and Paul Walsh “Flexible yet Efficient Management of Electronic Health Records,” International Conference on Computational Science and Computational Intelligence, pp. 771-775, 7-9 Dec. 2015.

[2] Haridimos Kondylakis, Lefteris Koumakis, Manolis Tsiknakis and Kostas Marias, “Implementing a Data Management Infrastructure for Big HealthCare Data,” 2018 IEEE EMBS International Conference on Biomedical & Health Informatics (BHI), pp. 361-364, 4-7 March 2018.

[3] W. R, H. K, P. NG, and S. RE, “Telehealth in the developing world” Journal of Health Informatics in Developing Countries, Vol. 2, Issue 3, pp. 1-5, 2009.

[4] DGHS, Health Bulletin 2018, Online Available at (<http://www.dghs.gov.bd/index.php/en/publications/health-bulletin/dghs-health-bulletin>, 2018).

[5] Md. Rakibul Hoque, Md. Fahami Ahsan Mazmum and Yukun Bao, “e-Health in Bangladesh: Current Status, Challenges, and Future Direction”, International Technology Management Review, Vol. 4, No. 2, pp. 87-96, 2014.

[6] Uzzal Kumar Proadhan, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman and Israt Jahan, “A survey on the assessment of the present states and opportunities of telemedicine in Bangladesh”, International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, Vol. 15, No. 1, January 2017.

[7] Tanvir Ahmed, Henry Lucas, Azfar Sadun Khan, Rubana Islam, Abbas Bhuiya and Mohammad Iqbal, “eHealth and mHealth initiatives in Bangladesh: A scoping study”, Ahmed et al. BMC Health Services Research 2014.

[8] Uzzal Kumar Proadhan, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman, Israt Jahan, Ahsin Abid and Mohtasim Bellah, “Development of a portable telemedicine tool for remote diagnosis of telemedicine application”, International Conference on Computing Communication and Automation, 2017.

[9] Toufik Ahmed Emon, Uzzal Kumar Proadhan, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman and Israt Jahan, “Improving security of the telemedicine system for the rural people of Bangladesh”, (IJACSA) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol. 9, No. 1, 2018.

[10] Md. Sadiq Iqbal, Md. Nasim Akter, Md. Imran Hossain, Shaikh Imran Hossain and Md. Aminur Reza Siam and Uzzal Kumar Proadhan, “A Study on the Status of Patient Data Handling: Current Scenario and Future Recommendations”, International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, Vol. 17, No. 2, February 2019.

[11] Saroj Kanta Mishra, Indra Pratap Singh and Repu Daman Chand, “Current Status of Telemedicine Network in India and Future Perspective”, Proceedings of the Asia-Pacific Advanced Network, Volume 32, pages 151-163, 2012.

[12] Richard Wootton, “Recent advances Telemedicine”, BMJ, Volume 323, 8 September 2001.

[13] Niamat Ullah, Pervez Khan, Najnin Sultana and Kyung Sup Kwak, “A Telemedicine Network Model for Health Applications in Pakistan: Current Status and Future Prospects”, International Journal of Digital Content Technology and its Applications Volume 3, Number 3, September 2009.

[14] Rashid L. Bashshur, Timothy G. Reardon and Gary W. Shannon, “Telemedicine: A New Health Care Delivery System”, Annu. Rev. Public Health. Volume 21, pages 613-37, 2000.

[15] Shengnan Chen, BS, Alice Cheng, BS, and Khanjan Mehta, MS, “A Review of Telemedicine Business Models”, Mary Ann Libent, Inc. Volume. 19, No. 4, April 2013.

[16] Sapal Tachakra, X.H. Wang, Robert S.H. Istepanian and Y.H. Song, “Mobile e-Health: The Unwired Evolution of Telemedicine”, Telemedicine Journal and e-Health, Volume 9, Number 3, 2003.

[17] PhD Anna Zvikhachevskaya, Prof. Garik Markarian and Dr. Lyudmila Mihaylova, “Quality of Service consideration for the wireless telemedicine and e-health services”, Reviewed at the direction of IEEE Communications Society subject matter experts for publication in the WCNC 2009 proceedings.

New Approach for Encryption Private key for Sender by using Hill Cipher with GGH Cryptography

Salah AL Bermany

University of Kufa

Faculty of Computer and Mathematics, Computer Science

Iraq,Kufa

salah.albermany@uokufa.edu.iq

Majeed Ismael Sameer

University of Kufa

Faculty of Computer and Mathematics, Computer Science

Iraq,Kufa

rxrx22446688@yahoo.com

Abstract—One of the important issues in the encryption used in networks is the Hill encryption method, but it is not practical in economic matters or the Internet, It is very difficult to send the private key to the receive in order to decrypt the message, due to the high exposure to third-party attacks, and therefore it is recommended that the private key must be encrypted before sending it to the receive and the receive will try to decrypt the private key by the way GGH algorithm in order to obtain the real key for decrypting the message Hill's method.

In this case, one of the Lattice algorithms was used to provide a strong bond for the Hill cipher .One of these important algorithms is GGH cryptosystem.

Keywords-component; encryption ;GGH, Hill cipher; Lattice

I. INTRODUCTION

Hill Cipher is a symmetric block cipher technique invented by mathematician Lester Hill (1891-1961) in 1929[1]. It is a multi-line encryption based on linear transformation. Hill cipher is a block cipher algorithm where the plain text is split into blocks of the same size[2,3].

In Hill cipher, the key is block size of with a size of $n \times n$ where n =block size is a non-singular matrix [1]. Both the sender and receiver must share and use the same key of matrix for encryption and description[4].

Each letter is represented on a scale of the number 26. Although this is not a primary feature of encryption , this simple scheme is often used [5].

Letter	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z
Number	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25

To encryption a message, each block of n characters (considered a vector n component) is multiplied by an inverted $n \times n$ matrix, against the modulus of parameter 26. To decrypt of the message, each block is multiplied by the inverse of the matrix used in the encryption [6,7].

The matrix used for encryption is the encryption key, and should be randomly selected from the set of inverse $n \times n$ matrices (scale 26). The code, of course, can be adapted to the alphabet with any number of characters [8].All math operations only need to be performed on a character count rather than on a scale of 26 .

II. ENCRYPTION BY HILL CIPHER

Encrypts n plaintext letters to n cipher text letters[9,10]

• For $n=3$, let the plaintext be $P = (P_1, P_2, P_3)$ and the cipher text be $C = (C_1, C_2, C_3)$

• For encryption

• $C = K P \text{ mod } 26$, where C is the cipher text matrix, K is the key matrix and P is the plaintext matrix

• Decryption uses the inverse of K : Then

• $P = K^{-1}C \text{ mod } 26$ (where $KK^{-1} = I$ the identity matrix I)

• The system can be described as a set of linear equations

•Decoding using frequency analysis is challenging, especially with an increase in the size of n . this is

•The encryption hides the single-character frequencies, as well as the digram, trigram, etc., even $(n-1)$ - grams, for length n to any chosen block .

• Hence, the Hill cipher is powerful against text only attack.

• However, it falls easily (in most cases) into a well-known plain text attack [11].

III. GGH cryptosystem

The GGH encoder system is designed to be a new encoding and decoding mechanism based on the hardness of the CVP solution[12].

It always motivates us to enter encryption systems based on many difficult mathematical problems, thus highly confidential information encoded by more than one algorithm remains safe even if part of it is broken. Network-based encryption systems are born with many advantages, for example, they offer encryption and decoding much faster than encryption systems based on separate logarithms and large number factors. Besides, the matrix operations feature makes GGH coding system easier to implement in hardware and software of modems compared to RSA and ElGamal [13].

A. BASIC DEFINITION

The Goldreich - Goldwasser - Halevi (GGH) coding system takes advantage of the fact that the closest vector problem can be a challenging one. This system was published in 1997 by Oded Goldreich, Shafi Goldwasser, and Shai Halevi, and it uses a one-way trapdoor function that relies on the difficulty of reducing the network. The idea embedded in this Trapdoor function is that, in light of any network foundation, it is easy to create a vector close to a lattice point, for example taking a lattice point and adding a small error vector. But to return from this faulty vector to the original network point, a special basis is needed [13,14].

To start the GGH cryptosystem, Alice creates a private key as shown an equation (1), which will be kept secret throughout the entire information exchange. In order to achieve this, you choose an integer matrix for an entire column:

$$V = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n] (v_i \in \mathbb{Z}^n, 1 \leq i \leq n) \dots \dots (1)$$

The columns in V are reasonably orthogonal to each other, which can be verified by calculating Hadamard's ratio of matrix V. Alice then chooses this matrix V as her private key[15].

Suppose L is the lattice generated by the columns of matrix V. Then Alice randomly generates an n-by-n integer of the un modular matrix U, which checks $\det(U) = \pm 1$

To create the single-modular U matrix, Alice can randomly generate a series of prime matrices and multiply them together. Then a new matrix W can be constructed by computing $W = VU$, and W^{-1} It is easy to discover. Continue to Alice a file account Matrix an integer W iteratively until Hadamard's ratio to W is small enough. Then the correct matrix W can be selected as the public key and published to the public. According to W is another generator matrix of the lattice L.

B. ENCRYPTION PROCESS

Plain text m of GGH is an integer vector with the same dimension, and that agrees Lattice L. Bob encodes the plain text m with the public key W. A small perturbation integer vector r called an ephemeral key will be added to the encoder Vector at the same time as shown an equation (2). Geometrically, the Euclidean length of r should be less From half of the shortest distance to any two adjacent points in L. Thus, Plain text m is then encoded into an unencrypted integer ciphertext vector Belong to the Lattice of Lattice[14,16].

$$e = W m + r \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

For some chosen m, the message space consists of the (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n) , r is vector noise W public key of basis lattice.

C. DECRYPTION PROCESS

Decoding the cipher text e is straightforward. Alice uses her private key V to find the closest v vector to the cipher text vector e by the BABAI algorithm. To discover the original m plain text by equations (3) and (4), Alice can simply compute it using the public key W in the formula below.

$$e = t_1 v_1 + t_2 v_2 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Now find t_1, t_2 parameters as a round operation $\text{Round}(t_1) * v_1 + \text{round}(t_2) * v_2 =$ encryption before add r vector noise

Encryption before add r vector noise

$$= m_1 W_1 + m_2 W_2 \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

And by the equation (4) to find plain text $m = (m_1, m_2, \dots)$

IV. Algorithm Research

Step 1 : : ENCRYPTION PROCESS

Start

INPUT: 1. Public key w_1, w_2, \dots for GGH

2. $r =$ vector noise $-10 \leq r_x, r_y \dots \leq 10$

3. private key k for sender to Hill Cipher

Begin

For two dimension example:

$$Dp1 = \text{key private } k(1) * w_1 + \text{key private } k(1) * w_2;$$

$$Dp2 = \text{key private } k(2) * w_1 + \text{key private } k(2) * w_2;$$

$$\text{encryption foe private key for hill cipher} = c_1 = Dp1 + r; c_2 = Dp2 + r;$$

end

output

encryption for private key for Hill cipher

end

Step 2 : : DECRYPTION PROCESS

Start

INPUT: 1. Public key w_1, w_2, \dots for GGH

2. Private key v_1, v_2, \dots for GGH

3. Encryption for private key from Sender by Hill cipher and GGH

Begin
 $V=[v1;v2];$
 $W=[w1;w2];$
 $tnew1 = c1*Inverse \text{ for } V$
 $Gg1=tnew1(1)*v1+tnew1(2)*v1;$
 $Ggh1 =round(Gg1* inv(W));$
 $tnew2 = c2*Inverse \text{ for } V$
 $Gg2=tnew2(1)*v1+tnew2(2)*v2;$
 $Ggh2 =round(Gg2*inv(W));$
 decryption for private key from the sender for Hill cipher
 ::Ggh1 ,Ggh2
 Output
 decryption for private key from the sender for Hill cipher
 end

V. MEASUREMENT AND CALCULATION

First :Hill Cipher

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 2 & 5 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det(K) = 9$$

$$P = SU, \text{ this is represented by } \begin{bmatrix} S \\ U \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 18 \\ 20 \end{bmatrix}$$

To encrypt t ,compute

$$C = KP = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 2 & 5 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 18 \\ 20 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 114 \\ 130 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 10 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \pmod{26} = \begin{bmatrix} K \\ G \end{bmatrix}$$

To decrypt, find

$$\det(K)^{-1} =$$

$$9^{-1} = 3 \pmod{26}$$

$$K^{-1} = \det(K)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 5 & -3 \\ -2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} = 3 \begin{bmatrix} 5 & 23 \\ 24 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 10 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \pmod{26}$$

Finally,

$$\text{compute } P = K^{-1}C = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 188 \\ 3 & 238 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 364 \\ 774 \end{bmatrix} \pmod{26} = \begin{bmatrix} S \\ U \end{bmatrix}$$

Second: Sender

We have a private key:

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 2 & 5 \end{bmatrix}$$

We will make this key in two parts as follows:

$$M1=[3 \ 3], M2=[2 \ 5]$$

Using an algorithm GGH , we will encrypt the private key and send it to the recipient, as follows :

Public key : $w1=[226 \ 40], w2=[1853 \ 319]$, and vector noise is
 $r=(r_x , r_y)=[-9 \ 2]$

Provided condition that it values between: $-10 \leq r_x , r_y \leq 10$

$$Dp1=3w1+3w1$$

$$Dp2=2w1+5w2$$

The add $dp1 , dp2$ with r

$$C1=Dp1+r , C2=Dp2+r$$

And the first operation was done by encrypting the private key, and we have the new key:

$$Knew = \begin{bmatrix} C1 \\ C2 \end{bmatrix};$$

Which is supposed to be sent to the receiver because even if this encrypted key is stolen, the third party attacker must decrypt the key and do not have the complete information for an algorithm GGH to decipher the encrypted key.

Third : Receiver

The Receiver recipient the encrypted private key from the sender ,and the receiver must decode the encrypted key, and in this case, use an algorithm GGH.

$$C1=[6228 \ 1097]; C2=[9708 \ 1677]$$

But the Receiver have a private key $v1=[1 \ 45]; v2=[45 \ -1];$

and also public key

$$w1=[226 \ 40]; w2=[1853 \ 319];$$

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} v1 \\ v2 \end{bmatrix}; W = \begin{bmatrix} w1 \\ w2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Use the Babai's algorithm to compute the decrypt.

$$[tnew1(1) \ tnew1(2)] = tnew1 = c1*inv(V);$$

$$Gg1 = tnew1(1)*v1 + tnew1(2)*v2$$

$$Ggh1 = Gg1* inv(W)$$

$$[tnew2(1) \ tnew2(2)] = tnew2 = c2*inv(V);$$

$$Gg2 = tnew2(1)*v1 + tnew2(2)*v2$$

$$Ggh2 = Gg2*inv(W)$$

Result of decipher of the private key encryption

$$Ggh = \begin{bmatrix} Ggh1 \\ Ggh2 \end{bmatrix}$$

VI . PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Encryption of the important requirements of the system performance of the system speed after a safety investigation, the table (1) Includes average time it takes Windows 7 environment within Matlab R2008a to encrypt and decrypt images standard listed in the table using a program 6GB RAM processor 1.8 Ghz and Intel core quickly on a personal calculator has the following specifications in table(1).

TABLE(1)THE AVERAGE TIME TAKEN TO IMPLEMENT ENCRYPTION ALGORITHM AND DECRYPTION

Plain text	Time of encryption (sec)	Cipher text	Time of Decryption (sec)
SUPPLYFOOD	0.022179	KGMBBMFCZR	0.040974
SUPPLYFOODINLOCATION	0.022628	KGMBBMFCZRLDXOGEDADP	0.043565
SUPPLYFOODINLOCATIONILIKETHESE	0.029182	KGMBBMFCZRLDXOGEDADPFTCORZHIOE	0.045817
SUPPLYFOODINLOCATIONILIKETHESEBUTITSWELL	0.029222	KGMBBMFCZRLDXOGEDADPFTCORZHIOELYDAHYZAMZ	0.053410

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Most of the problems in the encryption and decryption are the third-party attack to steal keys, but in this paper present the bests solution to put all obstacles to the attacking party.

First, the attacker must decode the sender's encrypted private key, and then use the program Hill Cipher to decrypt the message, secondly.

But the power of the algorithm GGH became working within the algorithm Hill Cipher, and this combination of the two algorithm gave power to encrypt text messages.

We also conclude that the time required to encryption messages and decryption text messages is acceptable within real time standards. This combination of algorithm GGH and Hill Cipher are gave excellent performance, less cost and less time in executing encryption and decryption operations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adinarayana Reddy K., Vishnuvardhan B, Madhuviswanatham, Krishna A.V.N. 2012. A Modified Hill Cipher Based on Circulant Matrices. *Procedia Technology* 4 (2012) 114–118. 2212-0173 © 2012 Published by Elsevier Ltd. doi: 10.1016/j.protcy.2012.05.016
- [2] Hill, L.S. 1929. Cryptography in an algebraic alphabet. *The American Mathematical Monthly*, Vol. 36, No 6. (Jun.-Jul., 1929), pp.306-312, <http://links.jstor3S>.
- [3] Rosen., K.H. 2005. *Elementary Number Theory and Its Applications* Fifth Edition, Massachusetts: Addison-Wasley.
- [4] Dawahdeh, Z.E., Yaakob, S.N., and Razif, R. 2017. A new image encryption technique combining Elliptic Curve Cryptosystem with Hill Cipher. *Journal of King Saud University Computer and Information Sciences* (2017), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2017.06.004>..
- [5] M.G.Vara Prasad, P.Pari Purna Chari, K.Pydi Satyam," AFFINE HILL CIPHER KEY GENERATION MATRIX OF ORDER 3 BY USING REFLECTS IN AN ARBITRARY LINE $y=ax+b$ ", *IJSTM*,Vol.No.5,Issue No.08, August 2016.
- [6] Acharya, Bibhudendra, Thomas, Nikhil, Arasu, Kavin D R, and Prasad, N Vishnu. 2011. Encryption and Decryption of Informative Image by Key Image Using Modified Hill Cipher Technique Based on Non-Invertible Matrices. *ICCCS'11*, February 12–14, 2011, Rourkela, Odisha, India. Copyright © 2011 ACM 978-1-4503-0464-1/11/02...\$10.00.
- [7] Sastry, V. Umakanta; Shankar, N. Ravi; and Bhavani, S. Durga. 2010. A Modified Hill Cipher Involving Interweaving and Iteration. *International Journal of Network Security*, Vol.11, No.1, PP.11-16, July 2010
- [8] Mahmoud, Ahmed Y., and Chefranov, Alexander G. 2014. A Hill Cipher Modification Based on Eigenvalues Extension with Dynamic Key Size HCM-EXDKS. *I.J. Computer Network and Information Security*, 014, 5, 57-65 Published Online April 2014 in MECS (<http://www.mecspress.org/>) DOI: 10.5815/ijcnis.2014.05.08
- [9] M. R. C. O. E. & T. Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Information Security, Telangana State, India : Malla Reddy College of Engineering & Technology , 2018
- [10] . A. Bibhudendra, "Novel Methods of Generating Self-Invertible Matrix for Hill Cipher Algorithm", *International Journal of Security*, vol. 1, no. 1, (2006), pp. 14-21.
- [11] A. H. Rushdi and F. Mousa, "Design of a Robust Cryptosystem Algorithm for NonInvertible Matrices Based on Hill Cipher", *Int'l Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, vol. 9, no. 5, (2009), pp. 11-16.
- [12] O. Goldreich, S. Goldwasser, and S. Halevi. Public-key cryptosystems from lattice reduction problems. Technical report, Cambridge, MA, USA, 1996

- [13] J. Hoffstein, J.C. Pipher, and J.H. Silverman. An introduction to mathematical cryptography. Undergraduate texts in mathematics. Springer, 2008.
- [14] L. Babai. On lovasz lattice reduction and the nearest lattice point problem. *Combinatorica*, 6:1-13, 1986. 10.1007/BF02579403.
- [15] Daewan Han, Myung-Hwan Kim, and Yongjin Yeom. Cryptanalysis of the Paeng- Jung-Ha cryptosystem from PKC 2003. In *Proceedings of the 10th international conference on Practice and theory in public-key cryptography, PKC'07*, pages 107-117, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2007. Springer-Verlag.
- [16] C. P. Schnorr. A hierarchy of polynomial time lattice basis reduction algorithms. *Theor. Comput. Sci.*, 53:201-224, August 1987.

First Author: Prof.DR. Salah AL Bermay University of Kufa

Academic certificates awarding body specialization year

1 Postdoctoral University of Bedford Shar / UK Computer Science 2012/2013 in the field of Information and Communication Security, which resulted in the RADG method.

2 Ph.D. from El-Neelain University / Sudan Computer Science 2003/2004 in information security and cryptology

3 Master of Al-Nahrain University Mathematics and computer applications 1995/1996 in processing algorithms and numerical analysis.

4 BA in University of Technology Applied Mathematics 1992/1993

I have many published papers, some of them mentioned

Search:

A secure MAC protocol for Cognitive Radio Networks (SMCRN

2013 - Science and Information Conference (SAI), 2013

Keyless Security in Wireless Networks

2014 - Science - Wireless Personal Communications Journal

Second Author: Majeed Ismael Sameer was born in Iraq, Baghdad City, in 1964. He received the B.S. degrees in computer Sciences from the University of Baghdad in 2005, and the M.S degree in computer Sciences from Mustansiriyah University in 2018.

From 1986 to 1992, he was a Research Assistant with the Atomic energy research .he has research interests include computer Sciences and applications about encryption and decryption of the images and information security.

Mr. Author was a publish of the International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security for peer –reviewed paper entitled " Image Encryption Using 3D-CHEN's Map and 3D-Henon Map for Secure Transmission "October 2017,also ,he was a publish of the International Journal of Computer Application Technology and Research peer – reviewed paper entitled " A New Approach of Color Image Encryption Based on RC4 algorithm and Chaotic Map " September 2017.

Portfolio optimization modeling through real time reports and analytics.

PhD (C.) Erarda Vuka ¹

University of Tirana, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Albania

Erarda.vuka@yahoo.com

Dr Julian Fejzaj ²

University of Tirana, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Albania

julian.fejzaj@fshn.edu.al

Abstract

The volume and complexity of information in enterprises are increasing at the same time that businesses are looking to take advantage of that information to gain a competitive edge. Companies look for a compromise between the timeliness of information and cost impact. In this competitive environment, there is an increased need for automatic decision-making. These decisions are realized through real-time business intelligence (RTBI), real-time reporting and real time analytics (RTA). Giving the fact that bank industries are rich with data and the decisions are time-sensitive, real time solutions will help improve customer experiences and operational productivity. This paper will give an overview on the importance and challenges of real-time reporting, RTBI and RTA. In addition to the analysis in this area, the article presents a portfolio modeling optimization for banking through real time analytics. This model will reduce time consumption, improve customer performance, and data quality.

Keywords: Real Time Reports, Real Time BI, Real Time Analytics, cross selling

INTRODUCTION

Data warehousing has been one of the key implementation practices which was followed in many industries. With the rapid change in customer buying habits and frequently changing markets every business needs more insight into all the available data that is in the database. A successful company needs to take better business decision based on the most recent data. Hence if we have a real time reporting it can provide the business insights based on the real time data available and it will definitely help the organizations to understand the business in real time and take better decision on the fly.

A real-time reporting system is based on a real-time ETL and a real-time data warehouse. Also known as active data warehouse, real time data warehouse is a combination of fast technologies and fast business processes. One of the most challenging parts of building any data warehouse is the process of extracting, transforming and loading (ETL) the data from the sources. Talking about real-time data warehouse, additional challenges like data modeling, scalability, OLAP (Online Analytics Processing), query tools and cost implementation. However considering the problems of the traditional approach real time DW is a new technology that responds to business demands. Traditional business reporting is built and packaged in batches. It doesn't allow for high velocity or a high volume data. It also has significant performance problems with large data sets. Most traditional business intelligence expects arbitrary query extracts before users can visualize data. Getting that initial query and dealing with the changes can take forever and frustrate users. Although IT experts try to address this issue by extracting data periodically from big data systems and transforming it in batches such that it becomes more consumable, the approach is not continuous. Today, more types of data are springing up, therefore, it's important to have more resources to manage data transformation. Alternatives, such as reporting directly against Online Transactional Processing systems, real time BI tools or real time reporting which are called real time analytics, have been studied and proposed over the years.

1. REPORTING IN A TRADITIONAL DATA WAREHOUSE SYSTEM

The goal of any data warehouse system is to provide analytic reporting based on the historical data available in the cubes that were loaded from multiple source systems. A source system can be of any kind like Customer relationship Management (CRM), Excel based flat files, Logistics and finance application data. An organization which has many legacy systems will use a data warehouse system to consolidate the data from multiple source and cleanse the data within the business intelligence system and store the data with the business intelligence systems in a common format.[1]

In our case study the main focus is on CRM system which is a system to store the various transaction data related to customer relation management. The data from the CRM system can be used to produce analytical reports and help to understand the customer behavior.

In the traditionally data warehouse data consolidation layer captures data from multiple source systems and integrates it into a single persistent target data store, such as a data warehouse. Target data-stores contain high-latency data that is typically used for strategic and tactical BI processing. These stores are built using batch data integration applications that pull data from the source systems at predefined scheduled intervals. In our case Real Time Data Warehouse is the target data store. During data consolidation, data-transform techniques may be used to transform and cleanse the data. As data changes occur in source systems, change data capture techniques may be used to stream the updates to a target data store. [2] From what we said above it seems that traditional DW has some limitations. Precisely the reports provided from this structure are mostly based on historical data. But the current business markets are changing, the customer habits are changing henceforth a business need to have analytical report that provides data about the business in right time. Therefore the right decision makes a business more effective, so many environments are using the approach to real time reporting, and remember *the value of data diminishes over time*.

2. Previous work on Real Time BI

Real-time report is a business intelligence feature, the process of providing appropriate information about business operations as they occur, with minimum latency.

Sometimes right-time is a better term to use than real time. This because “Right-time implies that different business situations and events require different response or action times. When planning a right-time processing environment, it is important to match technology requirements to the actual action times required by the business - some situations require close to a real-time action, whereas with others, a delay of a few minutes or hours is acceptable.” [3]

All business intelligence systems have some latency, but the goal is to minimize the time from the business event happening and maximizing the value of business. So if we consider the **total time between the happening of the event business and the distribution of information to the end user**, it can be divide into three different components, which concern “Fig 1”:

1. **Data (data latency)**- represents the preparatory phase in which they are acquired, transformed memorized and made available for BI analysis. Data Latency also depends on the context of the business where it is applied, for example in medicine or monitoring systems, it is a matter of milliseconds. While for the banking systems which we will treat below, a higher latency data can be tolerated. Besides data latency, data unavailability is another impediment to efficient real-time business intelligence.
2. **Analysis (analysis latency)** - is consequential to the time necessary to analyze process and present data.
3. **Decisions (decision latency)** - is the final stage in which, in front of information extracted and knowledge of the business, are decided the actions to be taken.

The sum of this three latency periods is called the **BI reaction time** which represents the goal of real-time BI techniques that are called to minimize it. The more time is needed to process the cognitive event the greater is the loss of information.

Figure 1. RTBI latency [4]

Giving the fact that business are dependent on real-time business intelligence, the unavailability of this intelligence due to a failed system could stop the operations. Great availability of the real-time business intelligence services is important. RTBI provides almost the same functionality as the traditional business intelligence, but operates on data that is extracted from operational data sources with zero latency, and provides means to spread actions back into business processes in real-time [5]. While traditional business intelligence gifts historical data for manual analysis, real-time business intelligence relates current business events with historical patterns to detect problems or opportunities automatically. This automated analysis capability enables corrective actions to be initiated and or business rules to be adjusted to optimize business processes [6]. Obviously real-time business intelligence system is based on a real-time ETL and a real-time data warehouse. Also known as active data warehouse, real-time data warehouse is a combination of fast technologies and fast-paced business processes. One of the most challenging parts of building any data warehouse is the process of extracting, transforming and loading (ETL) the data from the sources. Talking about real-time data warehouse, additional challenges are being introduced. The traditional ETL process involves downtime of the data warehouse while data is loading, but when we are performing real-time data loading, there cannot be any downtime of the system. For some applications, increasing the frequency of the current data load may be a solution. Nearby the raised costs, real-time data warehouse brings up some important issues like data modeling, scalability and query [7]. Storing real-time data along with the historical data, in the same fact tables, can be a good idea from the data modeling perspective because a real-time data warehouse is modeled just like a traditional data warehouse. Part of BI are also real time report or query analysis which we will treat in our model through real time data warehouses processes.

3. The demand for real time reporting

In contrast to the traditional data warehouses, which provide a historical snapshot of data at a past point in time, real-time data warehouses allow decision makers to analyze current transactions and trends as they occur. The demand for the migration from a traditional to real-time data warehousing derive from the need for decision makers to incorporate current data from multiple data sources into the decision making. Real time data warehousing is faster, allowing the business to make quicker informative decisions based on the real-time and historical data present in the data warehouse. Businesses find this extremely attractive because the quicker they are able to respond to certain trends in the market the more successful they will be. The business strategy is always based on the analytical reports or the business data available. In the era of the historical system reporting if the organization were able to understand the customer behavior in the past, now to make the business effective the organizations have to understand the business and customer market in real time that is while the business is running. For example a retail store should be able to get the information of which products is currently moving better and this can be achieved only if the organization have business intelligence systems that provide real time data. The movement to real-time is the latest development in

business intelligence (BI) and data warehousing. Real-time data warehousing provides the data that is required to implement real time reporting. By moving to real-time, companies can use business analytics to affect current decision-making and business processes. This capability is especially important for customer-facing applications. The purpose of real-time analytics is to increase revenues, decrease costs, and improve supply cable management. Companies that successfully implement real-time reporting or real-time BI can dramatically improve their profitability, of course all this is achieved at extra cost in infrastructure.

3.1 Real time reporting and analytics in banking

In an increasingly competitive world financial organizations such as banks, credit unions, insurance companies and etc. must focus on data analytics, and moreover, investments in this ground are necessary in order to maintain a competitive edge. For this in upcoming year's big data and analytics are considered as the top investment priority of banks. The main reason for this investment focus is to better understand and target customers. For the uninitiated, data analytics is the process that focuses on the processing and performing statistical analysis on existing business data to describe, predict, and improve business performance. There are different areas where real time analytics has the max effect: consumer and marketing analytics, risk, fraud and portfolio optimization modeling.

In today's data-driven world it is not so simple, and by using traditional methods it is even impossible to store and process the massive amount of data. Several studies have been done on the impact that a real-time decision-making has on some banking functionalities, based on the findings shown in the Accenture Banking Technology Vision 2019 [9]:

- 87% of banking executives have acknowledged that the union between customization and real-time will set the tone of competitive advantage in the future.
- The same report states that only 38% of these banking executives have seen their organizations prioritizing customization.
- Further, only 9% are focusing on on-demand delivery.

Based on these above indicators, banks should think as soon as possible of solutions based on real time reports or analytics to gain a competitive advantage. For this we can rely on new technologies as real time data warehouse gives an opportunity to do real-time analysis with minimum data loss, which means also using real time analytics such as real time reporting to make informed decisions while events are happening. As we now traditionally reporting is the basic version of analytics solution that focused on giving information about a current situation. Whereas real time reporting is recording and reporting an event at the moment it occurs. In the past, most companies gathered their financial data reports during quarterly or monthly intervals, but with real time reporting, companies can now view and access their financial and other data right as it is happening – in real time!

4. Portfolio optimization modeling

In general a real time reporting needs the data to be fetched from the source system in real time. When the transaction is completed in the system it should be made available in the business intelligence system. To build a real-time reporting system you need to build a good plan regarding what kind of data should be retrieved, who is allowed to retrieve it and what's the appropriate dimensional model to use. We will introduce a real-time reporting model as "Fig 2" for banks related to the customer portfolio. This model proposes increasing sales through the cross-selling technique based on real time analytics. The system will generate a real time alert using real time data processing. Alerts are essential for indicating a specific action to be taken from the end user perspective. In business intelligence systems for a report when there is a specific alert maintained for a set of data the real time analytical reports upon finding the specific value will show alerts to the report generated by end user.

Figure 2. Flow chart for the proposed model

The most complex task in RTDW is ETL process .The main challenges of ETL lie on performance degradation at data sources during data extraction, and on performing complex operations on large data volumes in short time frames. The ideal solution has two conflicting goals: (1) cause no impact on data sources and (2) process data in real-time as they are generated or updated. Ideal solutions should handle high-volume input data rates and perform complex operations in short time frames while extracting data with no operational overhead [8].

In our case study all data are extracted in real time from the source which is a traditional database through constantly updated job “Fig 3”. Then the data are held in star schemas in the target Real Time DW (tested on 500Mb), from which data will be taken to SQL Server Reporting.

Figure 3. Real-Time architecture for the proposed model

The tables in a star-schema are divided into two categories: facts and dimensions. Every star-schema has a single fact table and one or more dimensions:

- *Fact tables* contain individual rows for every occurrence of a fact in the source system. Fact tables contain columns called measures. It is these columns that are aggregated to calculate key performance indicators (KPIs).
- *Dimension tables* are used to share the facts in different ways. For example, the star schema above “Fig 3” would allow users to share the financial fact by the customer on the 6 dimensions linked to it.

The extract processes are extracting operational data and performing some transformation activities. A separate extract process is used for every distinct fact and dimension.

Figure 3. Real time Reporting Star Schema

By doing an analysis together with the business department in the bank we have identified 6 different types of products that can be sold through real time analytics improving customer portfolio. Based on the customer data as well as the actions he performs in the bank we manage to analyze and identify these Alert for Sale and in Real Time.

Product1	Offer E-banking
Product2	Offer Payroll account
Product3	Offer Fixed Time Deposit
Product4	Offer Debit Card
Product5	Offer Junior Deposit
Product6	Offer Consumer Loan

We enter the client ID number and after clicking View Report the report is executed on the target RTDW, through query processing. Which is presented in the previous works [10]. Once the report is generated, depending on the customer data that match the definded conditions, will be suggested through a real time alert the sale of one of the above products "Fig 3". Based on what we said above, the client can change the personal data while performing a banking service and they will be reflected in the RTDW. Next RTDW will display the changes in the final report, suggesting sales with the current user data.

Figure 4. Cross Selling technique through real-time report

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have dealt with real-time BI and real-time reports and real time analytics, both of them provide insights into the business operation and future decisions, but it comes down to the differences into how they do it and what information exactly do they provide. In my opinion RTBI is needed to understand the business while RTA are needed to change the business, also RTBI use multiple source of data whereas RTA use specific set of data. Nevertheless over the years these two approaches are being used more and more to make effective business decisions and to provide business insights in real-time. Furthermore, real-time business intelligence already has a massive impact on revenue globally. With access to key performance indicators and advanced analytics models, managers and executives can get a clearer picture of their business, make better decisions and diagnose problems properly. Therefore, in this paper, we have paid attention to real-time reporting by proposing a model based on the real-time data warehouse for the bank industry. This model will have a significant impact on customer portfolio, deriving. Apart from what we said above, generally, real-time reporting brings flexibility, as many real-time reporting solutions allow decision-makers to design reports and customize data displayed to meet their specific needs, and accuracy, as the probability of errors is reduced.

References

- [1] Baboo, S Santhosh, and J Prabhu. 2013. "Designing Real Time Business Intelligence Reporting for Better Business Insights." *International Journal of Computer Applications* 76 (14):7- 19.
- [2] Colin White, BI research, July 2006 "The Next Generation of Business Intelligence: Operational BI", <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/read/5850235/the-next-generation-of-business-intelligence-operational-bi>
- [3] Colin White, "Now is the Right Time for Real-Time BI", *Information Management Magazine*, September, 2004
- [4] Judith R. Davis, "Right-Time Business Intelligence: Optimizing the Business Decision Cycle", Sybase, 2006
- [5] B Azvine, Z Cui, D D Nauck, B Majeed, "Real Time Business Intelligence for the Adaptive Enterprise," cec-eee, pp.29, The 8th IEEE International Conference on ECommerce Technology and The 3rd IEEE International Conference on Enterprise Computing, E-Commerce, and E-Services (CEC/EEE'06), 2006, http://bingo.crema.unimi.it/turing/MATERIA_LE/admin/allegati/architetturaBT.pdf
- [6] Wikipedia, "Real-time business intelligence", https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Real-time_business_intelligence
- [7] Popeangă, Janina and Ion Lungu. "Real-Time Business Intelligence for the Utilities Industry." *Database Systems Journal* 3 (2012): 15-24.
- [8] Machado, G.V., Cunha, Í., Pereira, A.C.M. *et al.* DOD-ETL: distributed on-demand ETL for near real-time business intelligence. *J Internet Serv Appl* 10, 21 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13174-019-0121-z>
- [9] <https://blog.knoldus.com/real-time-analytics-in-banking/>
- [10] Vuka.E, Fejzaj.L, "The benefits of real time data for financial market: a proposal model for banking in Albania", Proceedings of The 5th International Conference on Applied Research in Science, Technology and Knowledge(2021): 77-85pp, <https://www.dpublication.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/17-8027.pdf>

Analysis of Engineering Students' Mindset Using Data Mining and Pre-Processing Techniques

Safira Begum,
Dept. of Master of Computer Applications,
Visvesvarya Technological University – RRC,
Belagavi, Karnataka, India.
safirabgm@gmail.com

Dr.Sunita S Padmannavar,
Dept. of Master of Computer Applications,
Gogte Institute of Technology,
Belagavi, Karnataka, India.
sunitapdm@gmail.com

Abstract -A student's academic performance is influenced by several factors. Students with a fixed mindset believe that their abilities are fixed, they avoid taking risks thinking that it may lead to failure. While, Students with a growth mindset believe that their abilities can be developed, they are more likely to see failure, as something they can learn from. In order to find if there exists any relationship between the mindset of the students to the region they live or study, a descriptive survey research design was done and a group of undergraduate engineering students with rural and urban backgrounds were chosen as respondents. The data was collected using self-administered questionnaire and further analyzed using data science and engineering techniques, primarily using the Orange data mining tool. This study envisions helping parents and teachers to provide customized support to students who fall under fixed mindset category. This analysis could further help in identifying the related problems of such youth who are unable to reach their full potential and thus providing the necessary training for the students to overcome challenges and succeed..

Keywords— Data Mining, Normalization, Data Visualization, Mindset Analysis, Orange tool.

I. INTRODUCTION

Researchers willing to develop solutions based on the challenges and open research issues have new horizon. It is understood that every big data platform has its individual focus, a few of them are designed for real-time analytics processing and others for batch processing. Each big data platform also has specific functionality[1]. Different techniques used for the analysis include statistical analysis, machine learning, data mining, intelligent analysis, cloud computing, quantum computing, and data stream processing [2].

There has been dire need for solutions which can extract information and knowledge from the incredibly increased

datasets[3]. The processing of such varied and rapidly changing data including the social network data, customer interactions and transactions could yield valuable insights for decision makers. The application of advanced analytics techniques on big data is known as big data analytics. Applying different analytics methods on big data creates opportunities in various decision domains [4]

Big data analytics using the tools is very effective, less time consuming and provides interesting insights [5]

Various methods of big data analytics has the potential to provide insights ranging from better education to cutting-edge research[6].

Data Mining has become a significant component in the process of knowledge discovery from large amount of data. As the quantum of data related to each student is increasing, it becomes more compelling to uncover the hidden information in this sea of data. In such cases where there is a need to uncover the hidden data, Data mining techniques play a key role[7]. For extracting such informative knowledge from the large amount of data, Data mining techniques focus on diverse methodologies. Further, such extracted knowledge can help the educational systems in taking better decisions in improvising the quality of education and for identifying the trends in students [8]. The businesses striving to stand-out from their competition rely on the insights gathered from data mining [9].

Educational Data Mining (EDM) is an upcoming theme, in which various data mining techniques help in extracting information and uncovering hidden knowledge from the large datasets collected within educational environments [10], and this information is used by the academic institutions for taking various actions such as for making decisions, for predicting the students' performance, for designing course curriculum, etc.,

Educational data mining also aims to understand learning behaviors, and identifying influential factors that affect the learning process of the students. This helps the institutions to

identify academic at-risk students in early stages and come up with necessary precautions[11].

Data mining techniques are applied on the rich educational datasets to extract the hidden knowledge. This information can be used not only to identify the students who require special attention and dropouts early on, but can also enable the teachers to take corrective measures and counseling such individuals well in advance [12].

While exploring big data, the prime task of data mining is to classify the data appropriately, summarize it and finally provide diverse standpoints. As iterated earlier, large amounts of data set is necessary for extracting the knowledge in data mining. Allowing the user to study the data is the main goal of any data mining software [13].

Data Visualization is an important method to have a comprehensive perspective of the data and discover data values to make better sense of big data. Visualization techniques are often used to accomplish various tasks at different points in time, to offer diverse level of understanding[14]. Since there are many visualization techniques available, such as Histogram, Chart, Box-plot, Heat-map [15], it can be hard to determine which suitable technique to use for visualizing the data. The ultimate objective of visual representation of data is to deduce the insights the data can provide without difficulties [16] and also helps in understanding the most relevant and important patterns [17].

Pattern recognition, human-computer interface, high-performance computing and multimedia systems are related to visual data mining which is an integration of data visualization and data mining [18]

Data mining on educational datasets such as scores from tests, assignments, homeworks and quiz [19] as well as CGPA or internal assessment marks could be used to predict the student's academic performance, but the final grade of students are affected by the methodology adopted by the schools and the time dedicated for studies [20].

Predicting the elements that may influence the student performance is precisely helpful for both the teachers in adjusting the teaching methods and for trainees in their learning methods [21].

Better achievement of students across perplexing school transitions as well as attain better course completion percentage in hard courses of math was possible by students, who believed they can learn intellectual abilities. Similarly, aggression in adolescents and stress developed in response to peer oppression or being felt left out is reduced in pupils who were taught or in the ones who believed that, they can learn social attributes. Hence, such mindset would result in superior performance of schools [22].

Fixed mindset belief is harmful to specific students and girls hence contributing to the disparity in education causing largely low participation and accomplishments. There is an urgent need to encourage growth mindset belief by Schools. Encouraging the growth mindset culture needs the schools to

transition towards group practicing as to not generalize or tag students nor drive negative messaging and lean towards teaching methodologies that value the thoughtfulness, efforts and diverse learning paths of the entire student community [23].

There exist many different data mining tools that have specific strong points and limitations, it is important to choose the tools that fulfill the need based on the application[24].

Orange Software provides better exploratory data analysis and visualization capabilities. Orange Tool is an Open-Source data mining software. It is a good platform for performing various functions such as selection, predictive modeling and analysis. Orange is a desired choice while innovation, consistency and quality are involved [25].

II. RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

The study sample comprised of undergraduate technology students who undertook the survey. The data was collected and further analysed using data mining tool.

The students are categorized into two groups, growth mindset and fixed mindset. Interesting patterns were observed, majority of the rural students showed fixed mindset whereas, in urban students both fixed and growth mindset was observed.

In this paper, the pattern was extracted after the data transformation was done by min-max normalization. It was further represented in histogram and scatter plot.

III. OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this research study was to determine if there is a relationship between the mindset of students and their regional backgrounds. In order to achieve the aforesaid purpose the following objectives were established:

- To determine the rural and urban affiliation of students under study.
- To determine the mindset of students under study.
- To evaluate the usefulness of data visualization tools for analyzing the data and arriving at the relationship between the mindset and region of students.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this study, a group of undergraduate engineering students from different regions of Karnataka participated in a self-administered questionnaire for mindset analysis. Data Transformation was performed on the data set through normalization. Orange tool was used for processing the data set and for visualization.

Data Collection: The data set was collected through a survey from engineering undergraduate students were captured in a CSV file which was further processed and analyzed. The data was initially reviewed and then the discrepancies, mistakes and duplicates were cleaned.

Data Preparation: The responses from the survey were converted into appropriate numeric value based on the

weight of each question. The values of responses for all the questions for every student were added and then averaged to arrive at the score which was further normalized.

Data Transformation: Min-Max Normalization technique, a form of data transformation method was applied on the data set. In this technique, the data is scaled for all the values to fall between 0.0 to 1.0. It is used when the Data set has values less than Zero, i.e., negative values, the min-max normalization converts such negative values to positive. The dataset was imported into the orange tool using the 'File' widget. The data was further configured for numerical and categorical values and roles were set as feature and target. The 'File' widget was then connected to the 'Data Table' widget for reviewing the data accuracy. The 'Data Table' widget was then connected to the 'Preprocess' widget as shown in Fig.1. The 'Preprocess' widget in Orange tool was used to normalize the data between the values 0 to 1. The Settings for selecting the min-max normalization is as shown in Fig.2. The normalized data was then saved as a new file using the 'Save Data' widget.

Fig. 1 Data connection for Normalization and Histogram in Orange tool

Fig. 2 Normalization Setting to Min-Max technique in Orange tool

Data Visualization: The normalized dataset was then imported into the Orange tool by using the 'File' widget. 'Distributions' widget which plots the Histogram as shown in Fig.3. The Average value for all the respondents from each

city was imported along with the Value assigned to each city using the 'File' widget, which was then connected to 'Data Table' widget, which was in turn connected to the 'Scatter Plot' widget as shown in Fig.4 for determining pattern and relationships.

Fig. 3 Data Connection for Histogram in Orange tool

Fig. 4 Data Connection for Scatter Plot in Orange tool

V. FINDINGS

The survey comprised of 25 questions to uncover the mindset of respondents studying in technology institutions located in urban and rural settings. The respondents indicated their responses as Agree, Strongly Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree based on the scores the Growth Mindset and Fixed Mindset were observed.

A. Histogram

The dataset represented in a Histogram as shown in Fig.5, demonstrates that 81% of respondents were between the value range 0.0 to 0.5, hence inferred they had Fixed mindset. And 19% of the respondents had Growth mindset who were in the value range between 0.5 to 1.0.

B. Scatter Plot

Average value for all the respondents from each city were calculated and represented on the Scatter Plot with x-axis as geographic values starting from 1= Urban to 40= Rural and average scores for each city in y-axis as shown in the Fig.6.

It was noted during analysis, that on an average Students from Urban Cities or closer to Urban cities had Growth Mindset with their values falling above 0.5. Whereas the

respondents from rural setting i.e., distant places from Metro City (Bangalore with CityID as 1) had Fixed Mindset.

Fig. 5 Histogram of Normalized score showing 81% of the overall students fall in Fixed Mindset category, i.e., in the value range of 0.0 to 0.5

Fig. 6 Scatter plot of average values of all respondents from each City

C. Line Graph

The graph in Fig.7, illustrates the number of respondents

with Fixed Mindset is the least in Urban /Metro City at the beginning of the graph and as the distance increases from the city, there is a rise in the number of respondents with Fixed Mindset. Alternatively, the number of respondents with Growth Mindset is highest at the Urban / Metro City and decreases as the distance increases.

Fig. 7 Line Graph displaying the relationship between the Fixed / Growth Mindset and Region of respondents

VI. TABLE I

QUESTIONS USED IN THE SURVEY

Sl. No.	Questions
1	Were you praised by your parents and / or educators, while growing up?
2	Did your parents and / or educators focused on how hard you worked or did they mention you were 'smart'?
3	Being smarter than everyone else is more important for you, as you have fixed mindset?
4	You are happy to interact with your peers to make use of the learning opportunities, they provide?
5	Because of challenging situations in your life, you have no confidence that you can achieve anything and have acquired fixed mindset?
6	Is there anything in the past that restrained you? An examination score? A dis-honest or insensitive action?
7	You tend to evade your responsibility by giving excuses or blame others, when a come across a problem or due to fear of failure?
8	You do nothing when you feel bad? You stop trying if you face disappointment or are thwarted, cheated, or disheartened?
9	Do you act stupid or let-go-off intelligence when in certain situations?
10	You always respond to constructive criticism?
11	While studying do you like to have noisy or calm

	environment?
12	Do you have preference of working on floor, desk or on a Computer while finishing assignments?
13	In the event, you are not able to finish a task, do you think it was due to the reason - You forgot?
14	In the event, you are not able to finish a task, do you think it was due to the reason - It's boring?
15	In the event, you are not able to finish a task, do you think it was due to the reason - You got distracted?
16	In the event, you are not able to finish a task, do you think it was due to the reason -You need help?
17	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is - Near the door?
18	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is - In the front?
19	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is -In the back?
20	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is - By a wall
21	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is -By a window
22	You like working, when you have a partner?
23	Does the most active time for you is - In the afternoon?
24	Does the most active time for you is - In the morning?
25	Does the most active time for you is - In the evening?

VII. CONCLUSIONS

As part of the study, a group of undergraduate engineering students from rural and urban regions participated in a survey with an intention to analyze their mindset being growth mindset and fixed mindset. The respondents' data values were normalized using min-max normalization in the Orange tool. After normalization we observed that students under the range 0 to 0.5 were 81% who has fixed mindset and in the range of 0.5 to 1 were 19% who has growth mindset. And it is observed that undergraduate students with urban regional background, closer to Bangalore were majorly found in 0.5 to 1 category. Whereas, undergraduate students with rural regional background and away from the metro city were majorly found in the range 0.0 to 0.5. This could be possible because of the exposure of students to the industry, events and opportunities available in the urban/metro setting and being closer to it. As students from around the metro cities are able to access without much efforts and travel. Which is not accessible for students far away from such settings. However, this needs to be further researched.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to express heartfelt thanks to Mr.

Rahul Anand, Senior Software Engineer, SLK Software, Mr. Nayaz Ahmed, Chief Operating Officer, Jain University Incubation Centre, Dr. T. Munikenche Gowda, Director, BGS R & D, SJCIT, Dr. R Hanif Sab, Ex-District Health Officer, Govt. of Karnataka, Ms. Gowri Mahesh, Co-Founder, Learning Matters and to <http://orange.biolab.si/> for providing Orange tool, an open source data mining and visualization tool and all the related internet sources from where some of the information is taken.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gogri, M. H., Shaikh, S. A., & Iyengar, V. V., "Evaluation of Students Performance based on Formative Assessment using Data Mining", International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) , Vol. 67, No.2, 2013.
- [2] K.Schmidt,"The Web-Enhanced Classroom", Journal of Industrial Technology, Vol.18, no.2, pp. 2-6, 2002 .
- [3] D.Gopika, & B. Azhagusundari, "An Analysis on Ensemble Methods in Classification Tasks". International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering, Vol. 3, Issue 7, 2014.
- [4] F.Castro, A.Vellido, A.Nebot, F.Mugica, "Applying Data Mining Techniques to e-Learning Problems" Studies in Computational Intelligence (SCI), Vol.62, ISBN 978-3-540-71973-1, pp.183–221, 2007 .
- [5] B. K Baradwaj, S.Pal, "Mining Educational Data to Analyze Students Performance", International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol. 2, no. 6, 2011.
- [6] C.Rajeswari, D.Basu, N.Maurya, "Comparative Study of Big data Analytics Tools: R and Tableau", IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, Vol. 263, Issue 4, 2017 .
- [7] Narvekar, A., Menezes, V., Angle, O. P., Lotlekar, M., Naik, S., & Purohit, A. "Students Performance Prediction using Data Mining Techniques", International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology , Volume 8 Issue VI, 2020.
- [8] S.L.Yadav,A.Sohal, "Review Paper on Big Data Analytics in Cloud Computing", International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology (IJCTT) , Vol. 49, no.3, ISSN: 2231-2803, 2017 .
- [9] Kohavi, R. Data Mining and Visualization. National Academy of Engineering (NAE), 2000 .
- [10] JothiLakshmi, S., & Thangaraj, "Recommender System for Student Performance Using EDM", Asian Journal of Computer Science and Technology, ISSN: 2249-0701 Vol.7 No.3, pp. 53-57, 2018.
- [11] Romero, J. R. Romero, & S. Ventura, " A Survey on Pre-Processing Educational Data", Studies in Computational Intelligence (p. 36), 2013.
- [12] U.K.Pandey, S.Pal, "Data Mining : A prediction of performer or underperformer using classification", International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, Vol.2(2), ISSN: 0975-9646, pp. 686-690, 2011 .
- [13] E.G.Kulkarni, "WEKA Powerful Tool in Data Mining", International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol.2, no.2, ISSN: 0975 – 8887, pp.10-15, 2016 .
- [14] http://lib.ugent.be/fulltxt/RUG01/000/842/101/RUG01-000842101_2010_0001_AC.pdf
- [15] Data Visualization Techniques, Tools and Concepts (mygreatlearning.com)
- [16] S.S.Ajibade, A.Adeiran, "An Overview of Big Data Visualization Techniques in Data Mining", International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology Research, Vol. 4, ISSN 2348-120X, pp: 105-113, 2016 .
- [17] Gama, S., & Gonçalves, D." Visualizing Educational Data Mining Patterns". Eurographics Conference on Visualization (EuroVis) , 2014.
- [18] Viktor, H. L., & Paquet, E." Visualization Techniques for Data Mining". Encyclopedia of Data Warehousing and Mining , DOI: 10.4018/9781591405573.ch224, pp. 1190-1195, 2005.
- [19] Vishal, "Data Mining Tools And Techniques", International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Vol. 5, Issue 4, ISSN 2229-5518, 2014.

- [20] R.Obeidat, R.Duwairi, A.Al-Aiad, "A Collaborative Recommendation System for Online Courses Recommendations", International Conference on Deep Learning and Machine Learning in Emerging Applications (Deep-ML), DOI: 10.1109/Deep-ML.2019.00018, 2019 .
- [21] Y.K.Salal, S.M. Abdullaev, M.Kumar, "Educational Data Mining: Student Performance Prediction in Academic", International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology(IJEAT), Vol.8, Issue-4C, ISSN: 2249-8958, 2019 .
- [22] J.BOALER, "Ability and Mathematics: the mindset revolution that is reshaping education", FORUM Vol.55, no.1, DOI:10.2304/forum.2013.55.1.143, 2013 .
- [23] C. S. Dweck, D. S. Yeager, "Mindsets That Promote Resilience: When Students Believe That Personal Characteristics Can Be Developed", Educational Psychologist ,Vol.47(4), ISSN: 0046-1520, pp. 302–314, 2012 .
- [24] C.Chinmayee, M.Manohar, S.Bhavana, S. Anjum, "Analysis on factors affecting student academic performance using data mining techniques", IJARIE, Vol-1, Issue-5, - ISSN (O)-2395-4396 , 2016 .
- [25] S.Kodati, D. R. Vivekanandam, "Analysis of Heart Disease using in Data Mining Tools Orange and Weka", Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology: C Software & Data Engineering,Vol.18 Issue - 1 ISSN: 0975-4350, 2018 .

Forecasting Peak and appliance level demand using Smart meter data

Bhavya M R
bhavyamr.scs19@rvce.edu.in
+91 97394 61099
Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Rashtreeya Vidyalaya College of Engineering,
Bangalore, Karnataka, India -560069

Vasuprada U
vasupradau.scs19@rvce.edu.in
+91 99168 90807

Dr. Azra Nasreen
azranasreen@rvce.edu.in
+91 98869 23829

Abstract:

The smart grid is an important component of smart technology. Smart grid technology enables two-way communication between the energy consumer and the energy distributor. Smart meters which are installed at the consumer side acts as the bridge between the consumer and the grid. Data analytics can be applied to the data collected by the smart meter to forecast electricity consumption. The forecast will help the energy providers to manage energy distribution effectively as the demand is known in advance. Appliance level data analytics can predict the usage of electricity at the level of appliance consumption. With this prediction, users can decide on the usage of appliances to manage electricity consumption and hence reduce the bill. In this paper, a machine learning model using the support vector machine is used to predict consumer's electricity peak demand usage, and a hybrid model comprising multilayer perceptron with k-means is built to predict maximum electricity consumption at the appliance level.

The proposed SVM model performs better than the univariate ARIMA model by considering external features that affect electricity consumption. The hybrid MLP model with k-means clustering performs at accuracy in the range 84-99%.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the early 2000, many countries are moving towards smart energy management technology. Digitization and decarbonization are the pathways for future energy and power systems. Smart grid is a cyber-physical-social system that enables to couple power, customers, and distributors [1-3]. Smart grids have revolutionized smart energy management systems which can be seen by the increase in the deployment of smart meters across the globe over the past decade. Smart meters alongside communication network and data management system forms the advanced metering infrastructure (AMI), which helps the power delivery system by recording the consumer load profiles and facilitates the bi-directional flow of data. There are 5 main players in the smart power system: retailers, aggregators, distributors, consumers and, data service providers. In the future market, individual load forecasting inputs the electricity usage from the home energy management systems and provides forecasting that not only helps in contributing to transactive energy among consumers, but also to reduce the electricity bills. A lot of research is going on load forecasting using smart meter data in recent days to contribute to efficient power management systems[4]. Many Countries have started the transformation from energy to smart energy. The "Grid 2030" strategy is implemented by the US Department of Energy for the American electrical system. Statistical tools and machine learning models are gaining a lot of popularity to obtain real-time predictions. Power companies are switching from

reactive to proactive maintenance on the smart meter data by applying Machine learning algorithms to predict the MTTF/MTBF [5].

Load forecasting is crucial for electricity management (generation, transmission, and distribution). Load forecasting is done not only at different scales like meter level, integrated load level, and commercial buildings level but also at different horizons such as very short term, short term, medium-term, and long term[6]. The need for short-term load forecasting at low voltage levels is gaining a lot of importance because the electricity network is moving towards a low carbon future. Stephan et al. compare the different methods like kernel density method, linear regression, and autoregressive methods used for load forecasting on low voltage feeders with and without the impact of climatic conditions like temperature [7].

Load forecasting is also affected by structural and behavioral determinants which affect electricity consumption. Weather, location of the building, and flood area are considered as the important determinants, and income level, building age, and ownership are considered as the least significant determinants [8]. A non-linear mixed-effects model is proposed in [9] to capture the impact of additional variables which may influence energy usage.

Demand forecasting is the most important component of the supply chain as it can estimate the consumer demands for the future. If the demand management is not done by the organization the whole supply chain is affected. An ensemble model is proposed in [10] with minimal variation inaccuracy. Even though several methods have evolved to forecast the smart meter data not all consider the inherent uncertainty on the demand side. The load forecast must be coherent in the sense the aggregated series should be the sum of individual disaggregated series [11-13]. A hierarchical probabilistic forecasting method is proposed in [14] which uses random sampling and a mean forecasting approach for coherent forecast distribution.

Algorithms built for power demand forecasting must not only be able to predict the load variations with less error rate but must also capture sudden changes in the power pattern. Machine learning algorithms are applied to the smart meter data not only for load forecasting but also to inspect the power theft and predicting the prices for the electricity for the next day.

Load forecasting is done mostly using algorithms like SVM, ANN, and statistical models like ARIMA[15,16]. The machine learning algorithms built for power demand forecasting must not only be able to predict the load variations with less error rate but also capture the sudden changes in the power pattern. A deep CNN model with LSTM load forecasting is proposed in [17] which enables automatic controlling of appliances and avoids energy wastage that occurs because of the lifestyle of the home users. Nivethitha et al. proposed an energy forecasting model using long-short term memory networks with improved sine and cosine optimization algorithms for forecasting energy consumptions of buildings smart meter data [18]. Building characteristics are also important to make policies and decisions on electricity consumption as the impact of certain characteristics may increase or decrease electricity consumption. A mixed-effect model which can capture the correlation between the identified parameters on the population is proposed in [19]. Machine learning models like Extreme Gradient boosting (XGBoost), Categorical boosting, and light gradient boosting are applied on smart meter data to inspect the power theft problems which can cause a huge financial loss for the utility providers [20]. ANN models can also be applied to the price profiles for the electricity to identify the market price patterns which can help the retailers increase their profits [21].

In order to benefit energy management, we propose an Artificial intelligence-based model which monitors the energy consumption at the appliance level and also forecasts peak electricity demand of individual home by considering the history of consumption and external factors.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed artificial intelligent model forecasts peak electric energy consumption and predicts appliances that consume maximum electricity. The models are built using machine learning algorithm support vector machine for forecasting peak consumer demand and a hybrid model comprising MLP with K-means to predict appliance level consumption. The model is given with inputs which are time-series data of electricity consumption and external factors such as temperature and day of the week. The data is collected from a smart meter which is installed at the consumer side.

A. Support Vector Machine(SVM)

SVM is a simple, flexible machine learning model which supports supervised learning. SVM supports solutions to both regression and classification problems. SVM that supports regression will have the below features.

Kernel: This function transforms linearly inseparable input features to separable high dimensional feature space. The transformed space is separable by a plane.

Hyperplane: It is a best-fit plane that fits the input data.

Decision boundary: This determines the vectors that are close to the hyperplane.

Support Vectors: feature vectors that are very close to the hyperplane.

SVM model can be defined mathematically as in equation (1)

$$G(t) = W^T\phi(t) + b \quad (1)$$

Where,

$G(t)$: Predicted output value.

W^T : Vector of Weights.

$\phi(t)$: High dimensional feature space derived from input space.

b : Bias.

SVM supports different kernel functions such as linear, polynomial, and radial kernels to form a best fit hyperplane. Weights and bias are adjusted to maximize the hyperplane.

The proposed forecasting system takes combined input features that include electric usage, weather data, and day of the week. All the input features are of integer data. Before training the model a window of historical consumption is formed. This window contains previous consumption values for a period of 12 hours. The input is divided into a training set and validation set. Using the training set the SVM model is trained to predict future consumption. A validation set is used to verify the fitness of the SVM model using the R2 score.

Input: Input Dataset(D) with input features and numeric target values.

- From the Input Dataset(D) add 12 new columns as a feature which is a window of previous electricity consumption for a period of the previous 12 hours.

- For each row in the Input Dataset(D), perform scaling of each column to have a standard deviation of one.
- Divide the Input Dataset(D) into two parts TrainSet(T) and ValidationSet(V)
- Select an SVM model with a specific kernel.
- Train the selected SVM model with TrainSet(T)
- Predict the peak electricity demand on the ValidationSet(V) using the previously built model.
- Evaluate the model using R2 score on predicted value and actual value.
- Retrain the SVM model if model performance is less than the ARIMA model.

B. Multi-layer Perceptron(MLP) with K-means

A Multilayer Perceptron is a class of artificial neural networks that has one or more hidden layers. The multilayer perceptron is an interconnection of neurons across the different layers. There are three main layers in a multilayer perceptron namely the input layer, hidden layer, and output layer. The input to the model is provided through the input layer, passed on through the hidden layers consisting of activation functions to perform the classification and the final output is seen at the output layer. Figure 1 shows the structure of a multilayer perceptron with many inputs and a single output.

Figure 1. Structure of perceptron [23]

Multilayer perceptron algorithm learns a function as shown in equation (2)

$$f(.) : R^m \rightarrow R^o \tag{2}$$

by training on a dataset, with ‘m’ dimensional input and an ‘o’ dimensional output with a feature set of the form $X = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m$ and a target function y . A non-linear activation function is used to capture the non-linearity in the input. The bias and weights are adjusted in the model for the feature extraction. The layers determine the precision of the model output.

Mathematically after including the weight and bias MLP can be represented as in equation (3)

$$f(.) = A(b^{(2)} + M^{(2)} (B(b^{(1)} + M^{(1)} x))) \tag{3}$$

Where,

f: Function that maps input to output ($R^m \rightarrow R^o$) size of input and output vector being m and o respectively.

A, B: Activation functions

$b^{(1)}$, $b^{(2)}$: Bias

$M^{(1)}$, $M^{(2)}$: Weight matrices

The hybrid model is constructed as a combination of k-means clustering which is an unsupervised algorithm. The data points with similar levels of electricity consumption are clustered which can thus narrow down the window for the prediction using the MLP algorithm. The model produces a parallel output of all the appliances. As the usage of an appliance in daily living is also correlated and not all the appliances run together, the clustering of the appliances determines the correlation between the daily usage of various appliances.

Input: Dataset(D) with features(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) representing appliance level consumptions.

Output: Target values($p(x_1), p(x_2), \dots, p(x_n)$) showing the predictions for all features.

- Cluster index(k) is set to 3.
- Determine the initial cluster means m_1 , m_2 , and m_3 .
- Until no change is observed,
 - For every value in the dataset
 - Find the Euclidean distance between the value and cluster mean.
 - Assign the value to the cluster with the minimum distance.
 - end for.
- end until
- For every value add a new feature indicating the cluster label
 - Pick a suitable cluster from the set of clusters created
 - New dataset(D) has data records corresponding to the selected cluster.
 - Build a historic window for 5 hours on the train set (X, y) and validation set (X', y').
 - Build the Multi-Layer Perceptron model with n-inputs, 1-Dense layer, and n-output layers for each input feature.
 - Select the loss function to evaluate the model and optimization the model parameters
 - for all the values in the train set(X, y):
 - Fit the previously built model.
- end for.
- Validate the model on the validation set(X', y').
- Model performance is evaluated using the loss function.

C. System Architecture and Design

The proposed system is fed with time series data which is captured by the smart meter. This input time series data has features comprising electricity consumption of different houses in an apartment, electricity consumption of individual appliances used at each house, and weather-related data which is specific to the apartment's geographical location.

Statistical algorithm Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) is used to forecast peak electricity consumption by the individual home. The ARIMA model is considered as a Null model on which SVM outperforms in the prediction of peak demand. Machine learning algorithm Support Vector Machine (SVM) is applied on the input data set for predicting peak electricity demand. R2 score [22] used as the metric to compare results from the two different models. R2 is a statistical evaluation metric that is used to find the goodness of fit of a model. The metric values range from 0 to 1. An R2 score of 1 implies the regression predictions perfectly fit the data. If the R2 score of SVM model is more than ARIMA model, then it is concluded that the proposed model performs better than the Null model. The hybrid Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) algorithm with k-means clustering is applied on the input dataset. This model forecasts electricity consumption of individual appliance for the coming.

The proposed system's process is divided into three major phases (Figure 2):

➤ **Dataset Loading:**

- Time series data set is fed to the model as input.
- The data set is taken from UMass Trace Repository. The Repository provides network, storage, and other traces to the research community for analysis.
- The UMass Smart Data set has two sub-datasets namely the Weather dataset and the Electrical dataset.
- Electrical data set is used to forecast peak demand of electricity. This data set consists of minute-wise electricity consumption from an apartment.
- Electrical data also consists of electricity consumption at the appliance level from each home captured at the rate of a minute. This data set is used for forecasting electricity consumption at the appliance level.
- The weather data set provides the seasonal weather conditions of the physical location where the apartment is situated.

➤ **Data Pre-processing:**

- Once the dataset is loaded in the Data load phase, it is important to pre-process the data before it is used for training models.
- In the pre-processing phase the whole data set is parsed through to find any missing values and anomalies that would bring down the model accuracy.
- Missing values observed in the electricity consumption column are filled with the average value of hourly electricity consumption.
- After the dataset is free from all the missing values all the data points are scaled-down. Scaling ensured that the range of feature values lies between 0 and 1.
- Before feeding the input to the model building phase, create a historical window of the previous consumption,

Figure 2. System architecture of the proposed system

➤ Model Training and Evaluation:

- After Pre-processing, the data is fed further to build the model.
- The SVM model is trained on the input dataset to forecast the user's peak electricity demand for the coming week.
- R2 score from SVM model is calculated and compared with the Null model. In case the R2 score is below the level of the Null model, SVM model parameters are tuned until the model performs better than the R2 score of the Null model.
- The hybrid model comprising MLP with K-means is applied to the input data to forecast the consumption level of the top five appliances for the coming week in a house.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SET UP AND DATA ANALYSIS:

Umass Trace repository provides a smart meter dataset intending to optimize electricity consumption at the home level. The time-series data set is collected from real scenarios and includes around 400 homes. This also provides information on the weather conditions such as temperature, humidity, etc. The electrical data set from the Smart meter of each house has a feature 'consumption' which captures usage of electricity with an interval of one minute. The length of the dataset is 503760. The weather data set includes weather conditions such as temperature, humidity, etc. captured every hour for a period of one year. To forecast electricity consumption using SVM model, the two datasets are combined by taking consumption and temperature features from the electrical data set and the

weather data set respectively. Appliance level data set is a time series dataset that includes electricity consumption by different appliances used in a home. This data set has 13 unique features and is of length 246639 captured at a rate of 1 minute. From this data set 5 top appliances are considered based on their energy consumption level for predicting the appliance level consumption model which is build using MLP with K-means algorithm. All the data set are preprocessed before using them for training the model. The huge data set is aggregated to hourly consumption. All the missing values are filled with the hourly mean. The models are validated using R2 score. The R2 score is a statistical measure that calculates the closeness of the predicted value by the model to the actual value. R2 score value lies in the range 0 and 1.

TABLE 1
COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF PROPOSED MODEL WITH SVM AND ARIMA

Algorithm	SVM kernel			ARIMA
Apartment ID	Radial kernel	Linear kernel	Polynomial kernel	
Apt1	88	87	80	83.5
Apt2	80	80	74	74
Apt3	73	72	73	70

The proposed SVM model forecasts electricity consumption for the coming week. The accuracy of the SVM model is found to be between 72-88%. The univariate model ARIMA has an accuracy in the range of 70-84%. The predicted values of SVM are better compared with the univariate ARIMA model. The SVM model has performed better by capturing the variation in electricity consumption with respect to the previous usage window as well as an external condition like temperature and day of the week.

Figure 3. Result plot of the proposed SVM system

The 7 days forecast value from the SVM model is plotted (Figure 3). X-axis represents the electricity usage and Y-axis represents the 7 days frame for which the values are predicted. Even though ARIMA and SVM capture the variation in electricity usage effectively, from the comparison of scores from both the models it can be inferred SVM forecasts better than ARIMA because that electricity consumption prediction depends not only on the history of consumption but also on external factors such as temperature and day of the week.

TABLE 2
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF MLP WITH K-MEANS

Method	Outlets	Furnace	DuctHeater	Washing Machine	DishWasher
MLP with clustering	99	84	99	98	91
MLP without clustering	89	79	88	92	96

MLP with clustering and without clustering is used to predict the top 5 appliances with maximum consumption for the next 7 days. The accuracy of the proposed hybrid MLP model with clustering and simple MLP model is captured in Table 2. In the hybrid model clustering enhances the accuracy by combining the appliances which are interrelated in their consumption level.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed machine learning model with the SVM algorithm is simple and effectively forecasts the electricity consumption of a home in an apartment for the next 7 days. The SVM model can produce better precision by considering external factors like temperature, day of the week which impact the electricity consumption. From the comparison of SVM and Null model's performance, it is concluded that electricity consumption is greatly affected by external factors as well as previous history of consumption. The proposed hybrid MLP with K-means clustering model can effectively be used to monitor and manage the electricity consumptions of individual electric appliances. Clustering determines the pattern of electricity consumption by different appliances thereby increases the performance of the MLP model. The proposed model can be enhanced by studying other factors that would cause variation in the electricity consumption and considering those features for forecasting. Some of the external factors which impact consumption are the number of residents, windspeed and humidity.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Alahakoon and X. Yu, Smart electricity meters data intelligence and future energy systems: A Survey, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, Vol. 12, pp. 425-436, Feb. 2016.
- [2] J. Zheng, D. W. Gao and L. Lin, Smart Meters in Smart Grid: An Overview, Denver: IEEE Conference. 2013 IEEE Green Technologies Conference (GreenTech), pp. 57-64, 2013.
- [3] B. Subhash and V Rajagopal, Overview of smart metering system in Smart Grid scenario. Bangalore: IEEE conference. 2014 Power and energy systems; Towards Sustainable energy, pp. 1-6, 2014.
- [4] Wang Yi, Chen Qixin, Kang Chongqing, Overview of Smart Meter Data Analytics, *Smart Meter Data Analytics: Electricity Consumer Behavior Modeling, Aggregation, and Forecasting*, Springer Singapore, 2020.
- [5] C. Rudin et al., Machine Learning for the New York City Power Grid, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, Vol. 34, no. 2, Feb 2012.
- [6] Elham M. Eskandarnia, Sameem Abdul Kareem, Hesham M. Al-Ammal, A Review of Smart Meter Load Forecasting Techniques: Scale and Horizon, *International Conference on Information Society and Smart Cities ICS2018At: Cambridge, UK, 2018.*

- [7] Haben, Stephen and Giasemidis, Georgios and Ziel, Florian and Arora, Siddharth, Short term load forecasting and the effect of temperature at the low voltage level, *International Journal of Forecasting*, Vol.35, pp. 1469–1484, 2019.
- [8] Amir Kavousian, Ram Rajagopal, Martin Fischer, Determinants of residential electricity consumption: Using smart meter data to examine the effect of climate, building characteristics, appliance stock, and occupants' behavior, *Energy*, Vol 55, pp. 184-194, 2013.
- [9] Cameron Roach, Rob Hyndman, Souhaib Ben Taieb, Non-linear mixed-effects models for time series forecasting of smart meter demand, research publication at Monash university, Oct 2020.
- [10] Adhikari N.C.D, Smys S, Bestak R, Chen JZ, Kotuliak I, An Intelligent Approach to Demand Forecasting, *International Conference on Computer Networks and Communication Technologies*, vol 15, pp 167-183, Springer, Singapore, 2018.
- [11] Cameron Roach, “Reconciled boosted models for GEFCom2017 hierarchical probabilistic load forecasting”, *International Journal of Forecasting*, vol.35,issue.4, pp.1439-1450, 2019.
- [12] P. Amin, L. Cherkasova, R. Aitken and V. Kache, Automating Energy Demand Modeling and Forecasting Using Smart Meter Data, 2019 IEEE International Congress on Internet of Things (ICIOT), Milan, Italy, 2019, pp. 133-137, 2019.
- [13] X. Sun et al., An Efficient Approach to Short-Term Load Forecasting at the Distribution Level, in *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 2526-2537, July 2016.
- [14] Taieb S.B., Taylor J.W., Hyndman R.J., Hierarchical Probabilistic Forecasting of Electricity Demand With Smart Meter Data, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 116 (533) , pp. 27-43, 2021.
- [15] Choi, Cho, and Kim, Power Demand Forecasting using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Deep-Learning Model for Monitoring Energy Sustainability, *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. 1109, Feb. 2020.
- [16] Dudek, G. Multilayer perceptron for short-term load forecasting: from global to local approach, *Neural Computer & Application*, vol.32, pp. 3695–3707, 2020.
- [17] M. Khan, J. Seo, and D. Kim, Towards Energy Efficient Home Automation: A Deep Learning Approach, *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 24, p. 7187, Dec. 2020.
- [18] Nivethitha Somu, Gauthama Raman M R, Krithi Ramamritham, “A hybrid model for building energy consumption forecasting using long short term memory networks”, *Applied Energy*, vol.261, pp.114-131,2020.
- [19] Cameron Roach, Estimating electricity impact profiles for building characteristics using smart meter data and mixed models, *Energy & Buildings*, vol.211,2019.
- [20] Prof. Rohit Bamane, Mervyn Vinod, Jahnavi Shah, Shweta Ahuja, Aditya Sahariya, Smart Meter for Power Theft Detection using Machine Learning, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Engineering Development*, vol.3, pp.526-528, 2020.
- [21] Ioannis P. Panapakidis, Athanasios S. Dagoumas, Day-ahead electricity price forecasting via the application of artificial neural network based models, *Applied Energy*, vol.172, pp.132-151, 2016.
- [22] S. Aman, Y. Simmhan and V. K. Prasanna, Holistic Measures for Evaluating Prediction Models in Smart Grids, *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, Vol.27. pp. 475-488, Feb 2015
- [23] Online resource : 1.17. Neural network models (supervised) — scikit-learn 0.24.1 documentation (scikit-learn.org) accessed on 24.03.2021

Machine Learning in identification and control of biological disasters

Chen Ling, Xingjian Lyu, Tian Zhenyu, Gabriela Mogos⁴

*School of Advanced Technology
Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University
Suzhou, China*

⁴ Gabriela.Mogos@xjtlu.edu.cn

Abstract— Biological invasion is a very common phenomenon. All alien species must have sites to grow and reproduce, which allows them to be called “colonizer” in a general sense. They would have adverse effects on the agricultural ecosystem by reducing the growth and output of the desired species [1].

In this case, the invasion of wasps caused serious potential adverse effects on bee populations in Europe, as well as on the other local biological populations. To reduce this adverse effect, avoiding invalid identify and reducing the possibility of the biological invasion, we construct model to identify wasps.

In this paper, we use Grey Forecast Model and Convolution Neural Network Model to improve the accuracy of identification and better control the disaster.

I. INTRODUCTION

Researchers and practitioners apply such algorithms to data for two main reasons: to predict new data and to better understand existing data. To predict something about new data, researchers collect data, apply an algorithm, and analyzes the resulting model to gain insights into the data.

In our study, firstly, we construct Grey Forecast Model to predict the tendency in November and December and evaluate it by posteriori test. Then we use the natural language processing in python to clean the data and leave the needed terms. After that, we use convolution neural network for image processing.

Finally, we find that variance has a positive correlation to the severity of the disaster and discuss the variance to evaluate the eradication of vespa mandarinia.

II. DETAILED ASSUMPTION AND NOTATIONS

A. Assumption

1. The number of reports in one year is not periodic.
2. The disaster about vespa mandarinia is short-term.
3. The number of reports has some relations with respect to time [i.e., it is not random].
4. The population distribution in the state is fixed for the recent several years.
5. The result of separating negative to Negative1 and Negative2 by NLP is accurate.

B. Notation

1. *Negative1*: It is bees but not vespa mandarinia while be negative.
2. *Negative2*: It is not a kind of bee while be negative.

III. GREY FORECAST MODEL

Since the harmful effect of vespa mandarinia is short-term, the relatively early data cannot well represent the current situation and predict the future situation. In this case, we only select the data of the last few months for prediction.

Simultaneously, due to the long interval between detection date and submission date, the data in November and December are not of reference significance. Therefore, we use the Grey Forecast Model to predict the development of the next two months, through the data of four months from July to October.

A. Principle of Grey Forecast Model

Let $X^{(0)}$ be a set:

$$\{x^{(0)}(1), x^{(0)}(2), \dots, x^{(0)}(N)\}$$

Let $X^{(1)}$ be a set:

$$\{x^{(0)}(1), x^{(0)}(1) + x^{(0)}(2), \dots, x^{(0)}(1) + x^{(0)}(2) + \dots + x^{(0)}(N)\}$$

If we write it as $x^{(1)} = \{\sum_{i=1}^n X^{(0)}(i) : n = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$,

Then $x^{(k)} = \{\sum_{i=1}^n X^{(k-1)}(i) : n = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$.

By building a differential equation to discrete sequences, it can be in the form:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} + ax = u$$

if we build a first-order differential equation.

By the definition of derivative:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{x(t+\Delta t) - x(t)}{\Delta t},$$

when $\Delta t \ll t$ let Δt be 1, approximately.

We have written it into the discrete form:

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = x(k+1) - x(k) = \Delta^{(1)}(x(k+1))$$

Since $\frac{\Delta x^{(1)}}{\Delta t}$ is with respect to the value of two times, let $x^{(i)}(i)$ be $\frac{1}{2}[x^{(i)}(i) + x^{(i)}(i-1)]$, where $i=2,3, \dots, N$.

$$x^{(i)} = \frac{1}{2}[x^{(i)}(i) + x^{(i)}(i-1)], (i = 2,3, \dots, N)$$

and

$$x^{(1)}(k+1) = \frac{1}{2}[x^{(1)}(k+1) + x^{(1)}(k)]$$

Solving

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = x(k+1) - x(k) = \Delta^{(1)}(x(k+1)) \\ \Delta^{(1)}(x^{(1)}(k+1)) = x^{(1)}(k+1) - x^{(1)}(k) = x^{(0)}(k+1) \\ x^{(1)}(k+1) = \frac{1}{2}[x^{(1)}(k+1) + x^{(1)}(k)] \\ \Delta^{(1)}(x^{(1)}(k+1)) + a(x(k+1)) = u \end{cases}$$

it follows that:

$$x^{(0)}(k+1) = a \left[-\frac{1}{2}(x^{(1)}(k) + x^{(1)}(k+1)) \right] + u.$$

Transform it into matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x^{(0)}(2) \\ x^{(0)}(3) \\ \vdots \\ x^{(0)}(N) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{2}[x^{(1)}(2) + x^{(1)}(1)] & 1 \\ -\frac{1}{2}[x^{(1)}(3) + x^{(1)}(2)] & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ -\frac{1}{2}[x^{(1)}(N) + x^{(1)}(N-1)] & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a \\ u \end{bmatrix}$$

Let $y = [x^{(0)}(2), x^{(0)}(3), \dots, x^{(0)}(N)]^T$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{2}[x^{(1)}(2) + x^{(1)}(1)] & 1 \\ -\frac{1}{2}[x^{(1)}(3) + x^{(1)}(2)] & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ -\frac{1}{2}[x^{(1)}(N) + x^{(1)}(N-1)] & 1 \end{bmatrix}, U = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ u \end{bmatrix}$$

We have $y=BU$ and

$$\hat{U} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{a} \\ \hat{u} \end{bmatrix} = (B^T B)^{-1} B^T y$$

B. Precision Test and Evaluation

We have the residual error:

$$e(k) = x^{(0)}(k) - \hat{x}^{(0)}(k), k = 1,2, \dots, n.$$

Let $x^{(0)}$ and $E = \{e(k)\}_{k=1}^n$ be two sequences,

we have the residual error respectively:

$$\begin{cases} S_1^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n [x^{(0)}(k) - \bar{x}]^2 \\ S_2^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n [e(k) - \bar{e}]^2 \end{cases}$$

where $\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n x^{(0)}(k)$ and $\bar{e} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n e(k)$

C. Evaluation

By calculating the posterior error, the posterior error ratio of pass the precision test. [Note: here we use code to examine the data and thereby no more explanation]

D. Results of the Model

In this graph, the blue line represents the origin data [i.e., total count by month from July 2020 to October 2020] and the orange one represents the data after fitting, which simultaneously predicts the number of reports in November and December.

E. Model Results

In this model, we utilize the data for four months from July to October in 2020 and forecast the trend for the latter two months.

The total count strictly decreases after August and the rate of decreasing tends to be smaller month by month.

Hence, we predict that in November the total count is 114 and in December is 44. Note that since Gray Forecast Model based on small number of data is not suitable to predict for a long-term tendency, it cannot be precise if forecasting the trend in 2021.

IV. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK MODEL

To calculate the likelihood of mistaken classification (mistake other hornets for Vespa mandarinia, defined as Negative1) and prioritize the investigation of the reports most likely to be positive sightings, we design a CNN deep learning model to do classification.

A. Data Cleaning

Drop All Data with Wrong Format Data in the Submission Date Column

```
raw["Detection Date"] = raw["Detection Date"].astype(str)
sorted_raw = raw.sort_values("Detection Date").reset_index(drop=True)

sorted_raw.head(5)

sorted_raw.drop(index=[i for i in range(10)],inplace=True)
```

Drop Rows with Null Value.

```
dataset = dataset.dropna().reset_index(drop=True)
```


C. Prepare for Model Input

Enhance Picture Labelled Positive

As can be seen below, the distributions of different labels are quite different, especially the positive label.

```
dataset["Lab Status"].value_counts()
Negative2    1800
Negative1    1394
Positive      14
Name: Lab Status, dtype: int64
```

Therefore, we use image enhancement technology to expand those positive images from 14 to 200.

Convert movies

Since people submitted files with different formats, we convert the movie formats to image formats by extracting key frame. We also ignore files with other formats because they are trivial to the consequence.

```
dataset["FileType"].value_counts()
image/jpg      3032
image/png       75
video/quicktime 76
video/mp4       5
application/pdf 5
application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.wordprocessingml.document 3
application/x-zip-compressed 3
application/octet-stream 1
Name: FileType, dtype: int64
```

D. Apply CNN model

The recognition ability of convolutional neural network is highly reliable and effective [3], so we choose this model to train our dataset.

Convert Image to Array Using Tensorflow

```
import tensorflow.compat.v1 as tf
for i in range(len(cnn_data)):
    img = tf.gfile.GFile(cnn_data['FileName'][i], 'rb').read()
    with tf.Session() as sess:
        X.append(tf.image.decode_jpeg(img).eval())
```

Build the Model

Model: "sequential_6"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d_12 (Conv2D)	(None, 256, 256, 16)	416
max_pooling2d_12 (MaxPooling)	(None, 128, 128, 16)	0
conv2d_13 (Conv2D)	(None, 128, 128, 36)	14436
max_pooling2d_13 (MaxPooling)	(None, 64, 64, 36)	0
dropout_12 (Dropout)	(None, 64, 64, 36)	0
flatten_6 (Flatten)	(None, 147456)	0
dense_12 (Dense)	(None, 128)	18874496
dense_13 (Dense)	(None, 3)	397
Total params: 18,889,735		
Trainable params: 18,889,735		
Non-trainable params: 0		
None		

conv2d: in convolutional networks, neural networks that use convolution in place of general matrix multiplication in at least one of their layers.

For a specific kind of weight matrix W .

$$h = \sigma(W^T x + b)$$

maxpooling2d : Pooling layer is used to progressively reduce the spatial size of the representation to reduce the amount of features and the computational complexity of the network.

dropout: used to avoid overfitting.

flatten: bridge convolutional layer to other layers.

E. Model Evaluation

It shows that the model performance is not satisfied our expectations, and the accuracy is around 45%.

It may be caused by the limited number of positive images since using image enhancement may not be enough.

Moreover, by focusing on the matrix, the chance for recognizing a positive image is comparably lower.

F. Model Results

The model output is a 3*1 matrix which represents the possibility of being classified to different classes.

The second parameter (Negative1) can display the possibility of a mistaken classification of the report.

The first parameter (Positive) can be used to prioritize reports when multiple reports come together to the institution.

0 – Positive
 1 – Negative1
 2 – Negative2

V. CONCLUSION

Although we devote a lot to the *CNN Model*, its accuracy is unsatisfied.

Therefore, other classification models are introduced to distinguish records between positive and negative. Those models are based on latitude, longitude, and detection month. We hope the *CNN model* could evolve and become more

accurate as the positive reports increases, however, those other models can be referred currently to prioritizing the investigation in addition to the *CNN*.

We can conclude that all classification models perform well on training set, but when it comes to the f1 score, they all get low marks. *RandomForest* has highest f1 score. It is because that *RandomForest* is good at dealing with unbalanced sample, which is consistent with the situation.

REFERENCES

- [1] FA Bazzaz, Life history of colonizing plants: some demographic, genetic and physiological features. In: Mooney HA, Drake JS (eds) *Ecology of biological invasions of North America and Hawaii*, Springer-Verlag, New York, pp 96–110, 1986.
- [2] M.E. Santholma, Marianne, Grammar sharing techniques for rule-based multilingual NLP systems. In: *Proceedings of the 16th Nordic Conference of Computational Linguistics (NODALIDA)*. Tartu (Estonia), 2007. <https://archive-ouverte.unige.ch/unige:3455>.
- [3] F. Takeda and S. Omatu, "High speed paper currency recognition by neural networks," in *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 73-77, Jan. 1995, doi: 10.1109/72.363448.
- [4] M. Matsuura, Ecological study on vespine wasps (Hymenoptera: Vespidae) attacking honeybee colonies. I. Seasonal changes in the frequency of visits to apiaries by vespine wasps and damage inflicted, especially in the absence of artificial protection. *Applied Entomology and Zoology*, 23(4): 428–440, 1988.

IJCSIS REVIEWERS' LIST

Assist Prof (Dr.) M. Emre Celebi, Louisiana State University in Shreveport, USA
Dr. Lam Hong Lee, Universiti Tunku Abdul Rahman, Malaysia
Dr. Shimon K. Modi, Director of Research BSPA Labs, Purdue University, USA
Dr. Jianguo Ding, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway
Assoc. Prof. N. Jaisankar, VIT University, Vellore, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. Amogh Kavimandan, The Mathworks Inc., USA
Dr. Ramasamy Mariappan, Vinayaka Missions University, India
Dr. Yong Li, School of Electronic and Information Engineering, Beijing Jiaotong University, P.R. China
Assist. Prof. Sugam Sharma, NIET, India / Iowa State University, USA
Dr. Jorge A. Ruiz-Vanoye, Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Morelos, Mexico
Dr. Neeraj Kumar, SMVD University, Katra (J&K), India
Dr Genge Bela, "Petru Maior" University of Targu Mures, Romania
Dr. Junjie Peng, Shanghai University, P. R. China
Dr. Ilhem LENGILIZ, HANA Group - CRISTAL Laboratory, Tunisia
Prof. Dr. Durgesh Kumar Mishra, Acropolis Institute of Technology and Research, Indore, MP, India
Dr. Jorge L. Hernández-Ardieta, University Carlos III of Madrid, Spain
Prof. Dr.C.Suresh Gnana Dhas, Anna University, India
Dr Li Fang, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore
Prof. Pijush Biswas, RCC Institute of Information Technology, India
Dr. Siddhivinayak Kulkarni, University of Ballarat, Ballarat, Victoria, Australia
Dr. A. Arul Lawrence, Royal College of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. Wongyos Keardsri, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand
Dr. Somesh Kumar Dewangan, CSVTU Bhilai (C.G.)/ Dimat Raipur, India
Dr. Hayder N. Jasem, University Putra Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. A.V.Senthil Kumar, C. M. S. College of Science and Commerce, India
Dr. R. S. Karthik, C. M. S. College of Science and Commerce, India
Dr. P. Vasant, University Technology Petronas, Malaysia
Dr. Wong Kok Seng, Soongsil University, Seoul, South Korea
Dr. Praveen Ranjan Srivastava, BITS PILANI, India
Dr. Kong Sang Kelvin, Leong, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong
Dr. Mohd Nazri Ismail, Universiti Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Dr. Rami J. Matarneh, Al-isra Private University, Amman, Jordan
Dr Ojesanmi Olusegun Ayodeji, Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Nigeria
Dr. Riktsh Srivastava, Skyline University, UAE
Dr. Oras F. Baker, UCSI University - Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Dr. Ahmed S. Ghiduk, Faculty of Science, Beni-Suef University, Egypt
and Department of Computer science, Taif University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Tirthankar Gayen, IIT Kharagpur, India
Dr. Huei-Ru Tseng, National Chiao Tung University, Taiwan
Prof. Ning Xu, Wuhan University of Technology, China
Dr Mohammed Salem Binwahlan, Hadhramout University of Science and Technology, Yemen
& Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia.
Dr. Aruna Ranganath, Bhoj Reddy Engineering College for Women, India
Dr. Hafeezullah Amin, Institute of Information Technology, KUST, Kohat, Pakistan

Prof. Syed S. Rizvi, University of Bridgeport, USA
Dr. Shahbaz Pervez Chattha, University of Engineering and Technology Taxila, Pakistan
Dr. Shishir Kumar, Jaypee University of Information Technology, Wakanaghat (HP), India
Dr. Shahid Mumtaz, Portugal Telecommunication, Instituto de Telecomunicações (IT) , Aveiro, Portugal
Dr. Rajesh K Shukla, Corporate Institute of Science & Technology Bhopal M P
Dr. Poonam Garg, Institute of Management Technology, India
Dr. S. Mehta, Inha University, Korea
Dr. Dilip Kumar S.M, Bangalore University, Bangalore
Prof. Malik Sikander Hayat Khiyal, Fatima Jinnah Women University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
Dr. Virendra Gomase , Department of Bioinformatics, Padmashree Dr. D.Y. Patil University
Dr. Irraivan Elamvazuthi, University Technology PETRONAS, Malaysia
Dr. Saqib Saeed, University of Siegen, Germany
Dr. Pavan Kumar Gorakavi, IPMA-USA [YC]
Dr. Ahmed Nabih Zaki Rashed, Menoufia University, Egypt
Prof. Shishir K. Shandilya, Rukmani Devi Institute of Science & Technology, India
Dr. J. Komala Lakshmi, SNR Sons College, Computer Science, India
Dr. Muhammad Sohail, KUST, Pakistan
Dr. Manjaiah D.H, Mangalore University, India
Dr. S Santhosh Baboo, D.G.Vaishnav College, Chennai, India
Prof. Dr. Mokhtar Beldjehem, Sainte-Anne University, Halifax, NS, Canada
Dr. Deepak Laxmi Narasimha, University of Malaya, Malaysia
Prof. Dr. Arunkumar Thangavelu, Vellore Institute Of Technology, India
Dr. M. Azath, Anna University, India
Dr. Md. Rabiul Islam, Rajshahi University of Engineering & Technology (RUET), Bangladesh
Dr. Aos Alaa Zaidan Ansaef, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Dr Suresh Jain, Devi Ahilya University, Indore (MP) India,
Dr. Mohammed M. Kadhum, Universiti Utara Malaysia
Dr. Hanumanthappa. J. University of Mysore, India
Dr. Syed Ishtiaque Ahmed, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET)
Dr Akinola Solomon Olalekan, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria
Dr. Santosh K. Pandey, The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India
Dr. P. Vasant, Power Control Optimization, Malaysia
Dr. Petr Ivankov, Automatika - S, Russian Federation
Dr. Utkarsh Seetha, Data Infosys Limited, India
Mrs. Priti Maheshwary, Maulana Azad National Institute of Technology, Bhopal
Dr. (Mrs) Padmavathi Ganapathi, Avinashilingam University for Women, Coimbatore
Assist. Prof. A. Neela madheswari, Anna university, India
Prof. Ganesan Ramachandra Rao, PSG College of Arts and Science, India
Mr. Kamanashis Biswas, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
Dr. Atul Gonsai, Saurashtra University, Gujarat, India
Mr. Angkoon Phinyomark, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand
Mrs. G. Nalini Priya, Anna University, Chennai
Dr. P. Subashini, Avinashilingam University for Women, India
Assoc. Prof. Vijay Kumar Chakka, Dhirubhai Ambani IICT, Gandhinagar ,Gujarat
Mr Jitendra Agrawal, : Rajiv Gandhi Proudlyogiki Vishwavidyalaya, Bhopal
Mr. Vishal Goyal, Department of Computer Science, Punjabi University, India
Dr. R. Baskaran, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Anna University, Chennai

Assist. Prof, Kanwalvir Singh Dhindsa, B.B.S.B.Engg.College, Fatehgarh Sahib (Punjab), India
Dr. Jamal Ahmad Dargham, School of Engineering and Information Technology, Universiti Malaysia Sabah
Mr. Nitin Bhatia, DAV College, India
Dr. Dhavachelvan Ponnurangam, Pondicherry Central University, India
Dr. Mohd Faizal Abdollah, University of Technical Malaysia, Malaysia
Assist. Prof. Sonal Chawla, Panjab University, India
Dr. Abdul Wahid, AKG Engg. College, Ghaziabad, India
Mr. Arash Habibi Lashkari, University of Malaya (UM), Malaysia
Mr. Md. Rajibul Islam, Ibnu Sina Institute, University Technology Malaysia
Professor Dr. Sabu M. Thampi, .B.S Institute of Technology for Women, Kerala University, India
Mr. Noor Muhammed Nayeem, Université Lumière Lyon 2, 69007 Lyon, France
Dr. Himanshu Aggarwal, Department of Computer Engineering, Punjabi University, India
Prof R. Naidoo, Dept of Mathematics/Center for Advanced Computer Modelling, Durban University of Technology,
Durban, South Africa
Prof. Mydhili K Nair, Visweswaraiah Technological University, Bangalore, India
M. Prabu, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering/Anna University, India
Mr. Swakkhar Shatabda, United International University, Bangladesh
Dr. Abdur Rashid Khan, ICIT, Gomal University, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan
Mr. H. Abdul Shabeer, I-Nautix Technologies, Chennai, India
Dr. M. Aramudhan, Perunthalaivar Kamarajar Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Dr. M. P. Thapliyal, Department of Computer Science, HNB Garhwal University (Central University), India
Dr. Shahaboddin Shamshirband, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Mr. Zeashan Hameed Khan, Université de Grenoble, France
Prof. Anil K Ahlawat, Ajay Kumar Garg Engineering College, Ghaziabad, UP Technical University, Lucknow
Mr. Longe Olumide Babatope, University Of Ibadan, Nigeria
Associate Prof. Raman Maini, University College of Engineering, Punjabi University, India
Dr. Maslin Masrom, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Sudipta Chattopadhyay, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, India
Dr. Dang Tuan NGUYEN, University of Information Technology, Vietnam National University - Ho Chi Minh City
Dr. Mary Lourde R., BITS-PILANI Dubai , UAE
Dr. Abdul Aziz, University of Central Punjab, Pakistan
Mr. Karan Singh, Gautam Budtha University, India
Mr. Avinash Pokhriyal, Uttar Pradesh Technical University, Lucknow, India
Associate Prof Dr Zuraini Ismail, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Assistant Prof. Yasser M. Alginahi, Taibah University, Madinah Munawwarah, KSA
Mr. Dakshina Ranjan Kisku, West Bengal University of Technology, India
Mr. Raman Kumar, Dr B R Ambedkar National Institute of Technology, Jalandhar, Punjab, India
Associate Prof. Samir B. Patel, Institute of Technology, Nirma University, India
Dr. M.Munir Ahamed Rabbani, B. S. Abdur Rahman University, India
Asst. Prof. Koushik Majumder, West Bengal University of Technology, India
Dr. Alex Pappachen James, Queensland Micro-nanotechnology center, Griffith University, Australia
Assistant Prof. S. Hariharan, B.S. Abdur Rahman University, India
Asst Prof. Jasmine. K. S, R.V.College of Engineering, India
Mr Naushad Ali Mamode Khan, Ministry of Education and Human Resources, Mauritius
Prof. Mahesh Goyani, G H Patel Collge of Engg. & Tech, V.V.N, Anand, Gujarat, India
Dr. Mana Mohammed, University of Tlemcen, Algeria
Prof. Jatinder Singh, Universal Institution of Engg. & Tech. CHD, India

Mrs. M. Anandhavalli Gauthaman, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Technology, Majitar, East Sikkim
Dr. Bin Guo, Institute Telecom SudParis, France
Mrs. Maleika Mehr Nigar Mohamed Heenaye-Mamode Khan, University of Mauritius
Prof. Pijush Biswas, RCC Institute of Information Technology, India
Mr. V. Bala Dhandayuthapani, Mekelle University, Ethiopia
Dr. Irfan Syamsuddin, State Polytechnic of Ujung Pandang, Indonesia
Mr. Kavi Kumar Khedo, University of Mauritius, Mauritius
Mr. Ravi Chandiran, Zagro Singapore Pte Ltd. Singapore
Mr. Milindkumar V. Sarode, Jawaharlal Darda Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Dr. Shamimul Qamar, KSJ Institute of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. C. Arun, Anna University, India
Assist. Prof. M.N.Birje, Basaveshwar Engineering College, India
Prof. Hamid Reza Naji, Department of Computer Enigneering, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran
Assist. Prof. Debasis Giri, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Haldia Institute of Technology
Subhabrata Barman, Haldia Institute of Technology, West Bengal
Mr. M. I. Lali, COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. Feroz Khan, Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, Lucknow, India
Mr. R. Nagendran, Institute of Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India
Mr. Amnach Khawne, King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang, Ladkrabang, Bangkok, Thailand
Dr. P. Chakrabarti, Sir Padampat Singhanian University, Udaipur, India
Mr. Nafiz Imtiaz Bin Hamid, Islamic University of Technology (IUT), Bangladesh.
Shahab-A. Shamshirband, Islamic Azad University, Chalous, Iran
Prof. B. Priestly Shan, Anna Univeristy, Tamilnadu, India
Venkatramreddy Velma, Dept. of Bioinformatics, University of Mississippi Medical Center, Jackson MS USA
Akshi Kumar, Dept. of Computer Engineering, Delhi Technological University, India
Dr. Umesh Kumar Singh, Vikram University, Ujjain, India
Mr. Serguei A. Mokhov, Concordia University, Canada
Mr. Lai Khin Wee, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Awadhesh Kumar Sharma, Madan Mohan Malviya Engineering College, India
Mr. Syed R. Rizvi, Analytical Services & Materials, Inc., USA
Dr. S. Karthik, SNS College of Technology, India
Mr. Syed Qasim Bukhari, CIMET (Universidad de Granada), Spain
Mr. A.D.Potgantwar, Pune University, India
Dr. Himanshu Aggarwal, Punjabi University, India
Mr. Rajesh Ramachandran, Naipunya Institute of Management and Information Technology, India
Dr. K.L. Shunmuganathan, R.M.K Engg College , Kavaraipettai ,Chennai
Dr. Prasant Kumar Pattnaik, KIST, India.
Dr. Ch. Aswani Kumar, VIT University, India
Mr. Ijaz Ali Shoukat, King Saud University, Riyadh KSA
Mr. Arun Kumar, Sir Padam Pat Singhanian University, Udaipur, Rajasthan
Mr. Muhammad Imran Khan, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Malaysia
Dr. Natarajan Meghanathan, Jackson State University, Jackson, MS, USA
Mr. Mohd Zaki Bin Mas'ud, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM), Malaysia
Prof. Dr. R. Geetharamani, Dept. of Computer Science and Eng., Rajalakshmi Engineering College, India
Dr. Smita Rajpal, Institute of Technology and Management, Gurgaon, India
Dr. S. Abdul Khader Jilani, University of Tabuk, Tabuk, Saudi Arabia
Mr. Syed Jamal Haider Zaidi, Bahria University, Pakistan

Dr. N. Devarajan, Government College of Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, INDIA
Mr. R. Jagadeesh Kannan, RMK Engineering College, India
Mr. Deo Prakash, Shri Mata Vaishno Devi University, India
Mr. Mohammad Abu Naser, Dept. of EEE, IUT, Gazipur, Bangladesh
Assist. Prof. Prasun Ghosal, Bengal Engineering and Science University, India
Mr. Md. Golam Kaosar, School of Engineering and Science, Victoria University, Melbourne City, Australia
Mr. R. Mohammad Shafi, Madanapalle Institute of Technology & Science, India
Dr. F. Sagayaraj Francis, Pondicherry Engineering College, India
Dr. Ajay Goel, HIET, Kaithal, India
Mr. Nayak Sunil Kashibarao, Bahirji Smarak Mahavidyalaya, India
Mr. Suhas J Manangi, Microsoft India
Dr. Kalyankar N. V., Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya, Nanded, India
Dr. K.D. Verma, S.V. College of Post graduate studies & Research, India
Dr. Amjad Rehman, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Rachit Garg, L K College, Jalandhar, Punjab
Mr. J. William, M.A.M college of Engineering, Trichy, Tamilnadu, India
Prof. Jue-Sam Chou, Nanhua University, College of Science and Technology, Taiwan
Dr. Thorat S.B., Institute of Technology and Management, India
Mr. Ajay Prasad, Sir Padampat Singhanian University, Udaipur, India
Dr. Kamaljit I. Lakhtaria, Atmiya Institute of Technology & Science, India
Mr. Syed Rafiul Hussain, Ahsanullah University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh
Mrs Fazeela Tunnisa, Najran University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Mrs Kavita Taneja, Maharishi Markandeshwar University, Haryana, India
Mr. Maniyar Shiraz Ahmed, Najran University, Najran, KSA
Mr. Anand Kumar, AMC Engineering College, Bangalore
Dr. Rakesh Chandra Gangwar, Beant College of Engg. & Tech., Gurdaspur (Punjab) India
Dr. V V Rama Prasad, Sree Vidyanikethan Engineering College, India
Assist. Prof. Neetesh Kumar Gupta, Technocrats Institute of Technology, Bhopal (M.P.), India
Mr. Ashish Seth, Uttar Pradesh Technical University, Lucknow, UP India
Dr. V V S S S Balam, Sreenidhi Institute of Science and Technology, India
Mr Rahul Bhatia, Lingaya's Institute of Management and Technology, India
Prof. Niranjana Reddy, P, KITS, Warangal, India
Prof. Rakesh. Lingappa, Vijetha Institute of Technology, Bangalore, India
Dr. Mohammed Ali Hussain, Nimra College of Engineering & Technology, Vijayawada, A.P., India
Dr. A. Srinivasan, MNM Jain Engineering College, Rajiv Gandhi Salai, Thorapakkam, Chennai
Mr. Rakesh Kumar, M.M. University, Mullana, Ambala, India
Dr. Lena Khaled, Zarqa Private University, Aman, Jordan
Ms. Supriya Kapoor, Patni/Lingaya's Institute of Management and Tech., India
Dr. Tossapon Boongoen, Aberystwyth University, UK
Dr. Bilal Alatas, Firat University, Turkey
Assist. Prof. Jyoti Praaksh Singh, Academy of Technology, India
Dr. Ritu Soni, GNG College, India
Dr. Mahendra Kumar, Sagar Institute of Research & Technology, Bhopal, India.
Dr. Binod Kumar, Lakshmi Narayan College of Tech. (LNCT) Bhopal India
Dr. Muzhir Shaban Al-Ani, Amman Arab University Amman – Jordan
Dr. T.C. Manjunath, ATRIA Institute of Tech, India
Mr. Muhammad Zakarya, COMSATS Institute of Information Technology (CIIT), Pakistan

Assist. Prof. Harmunish Taneja, M. M. University, India
Dr. Chitra Dhawale , SICSR, Model Colony, Pune, India
Mrs Sankari Muthukaruppan, Nehru Institute of Engineering and Technology, Anna University, India
Mr. Aaqif Afzaal Abbasi, National University Of Sciences And Technology, Islamabad
Prof. Ashutosh Kumar Dubey, Trinity Institute of Technology and Research Bhopal, India
Mr. G. Appasami, Dr. Pauls Engineering College, India
Mr. M Yasin, National University of Science and Tech, karachi (NUST), Pakistan
Mr. Yaser Miaji, University Utara Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Shah Ahsanul Haque, International Islamic University Chittagong (IIUC), Bangladesh
Prof. (Dr) Syed Abdul Sattar, Royal Institute of Technology & Science, India
Dr. S. Sasikumar, Roever Engineering College
Assist. Prof. Monit Kapoor, Maharishi Markandeshwar University, India
Mr. Nwaocha Vivian O, National Open University of Nigeria
Dr. M. S. Vijaya, GR Govindarajulu School of Applied Computer Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Chakresh Kumar, Manav Rachna International University, India
Mr. Kunal Chadha , R&D Software Engineer, Gemalto, Singapore
Mr. Mueen Uddin, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, UTM , Malaysia
Dr. Dhuha Basheer abdullah, Mosul university, Iraq
Mr. S. Audithan, Annamalai University, India
Prof. Vijay K Chaudhari, Technocrats Institute of Technology , India
Associate Prof. Mohd Ilyas Khan, Technocrats Institute of Technology , India
Dr. Vu Thanh Nguyen, University of Information Technology, HoChiMinh City, VietNam
Assist. Prof. Anand Sharma, MITS, Lakshmarangarh, Sikar, Rajasthan, India
Prof. T V Narayana Rao, HITAM Engineering college, Hyderabad
Mr. Deepak Gour, Sir Padampat Singhania University, India
Assist. Prof. Amutharaj Joyson, Kalasalingam University, India
Mr. Ali Balador, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Mr. Mohit Jain, Maharaja Surajmal Institute of Technology, India
Mr. Dilip Kumar Sharma, GLA Institute of Technology & Management, India
Dr. Debojyoti Mitra, Sir padampat Singhania University, India
Dr. Ali Dehghantanha, Asia-Pacific University College of Technology and Innovation, Malaysia
Mr. Zhao Zhang, City University of Hong Kong, China
Prof. S.P. Setty, A.U. College of Engineering, India
Prof. Patel Rakeshkumar Kantilal, Sankalchand Patel College of Engineering, India
Mr. Biswajit Bhowmik, Bengal College of Engineering & Technology, India
Mr. Manoj Gupta, Apex Institute of Engineering & Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Ajay Sharma, Raj Kumar Goel Institute Of Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Ramveer Singh, Raj Kumar Goel Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Hanan Elazhary, Electronics Research Institute, Egypt
Dr. Hosam I. Faiq, USM, Malaysia
Prof. Dipti D. Patil, MAEER's MIT College of Engg. & Tech, Pune, India
Assist. Prof. Devendra Chack, BCT Kumaon engineering College Dwarahat Almora, India
Prof. Manpreet Singh, M. M. Engg. College, M. M. University, India
Assist. Prof. M. Sadiq ali Khan, University of Karachi, Pakistan
Mr. Prasad S. Halgaonkar, MIT - College of Engineering, Pune, India
Dr. Imran Ghani, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia
Prof. Varun Kumar Kakar, Kumaon Engineering College, Dwarahat, India

Assist. Prof. Nisheeth Joshi, Apaji Institute, Banasthali University, Rajasthan, India
Associate Prof. Kunwar S. Vaisla, VCT Kumaon Engineering College, India
Prof Anupam Choudhary, Bhilai School Of Engg.,Bhilai (C.G.),India
Mr. Divya Prakash Shrivastava, Al Jabal Al garbi University, Zawya, Libya
Associate Prof. Dr. V. Radha, Avinashilingam Deemed university for women, Coimbatore.
Dr. Kasarapu Ramani, JNT University, Anantapur, India
Dr. Anuraag Awasthi, Jayoti Vidyapeeth Womens University, India
Dr. C G Ravichandran, R V S College of Engineering and Technology, India
Dr. Mohamed A. Deriche, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals, Saudi Arabia
Mr. Abbas Karimi, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Amit Kumar, Jaypee University of Engg. and Tech., India
Dr. Nikolai Stoianov, Defense Institute, Bulgaria
Assist. Prof. S. Ranichandra, KSR College of Arts and Science, Tiruchencode
Mr. T.K.P. Rajagopal, Diamond Horse International Pvt Ltd, India
Dr. Md. Ekramul Hamid, Rajshahi University, Bangladesh
Mr. Hemanta Kumar Kalita , TATA Consultancy Services (TCS), India
Dr. Messaouda Azzouzi, Ziane Achour University of Djelfa, Algeria
Prof. (Dr.) Juan Jose Martinez Castillo, "Gran Mariscal de Ayacucho" University and Acantelys research Group, Venezuela
Dr. Jatinderkumar R. Saini, Narmada College of Computer Application, India
Dr. Babak Bashari Rad, University Technology of Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Nighat Mir, Effat University, Saudi Arabia
Prof. (Dr.) G.M.Nasira, Sasurie College of Engineering, India
Mr. Varun Mittal, Gemalto Pte Ltd, Singapore
Assist. Prof. Mrs P. Banumathi, Kathir College Of Engineering, Coimbatore
Assist. Prof. Quan Yuan, University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point, US
Dr. Pranam Paul, Narula Institute of Technology, Agarpara, West Bengal, India
Assist. Prof. J. Ramkumar, V.L.B Janakiammal college of Arts & Science, India
Mr. P. Sivakumar, Anna university, Chennai, India
Mr. Md. Humayun Kabir Biswas, King Khalid University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Mr. Mayank Singh, J.P. Institute of Engg & Technology, Meerut, India
HJ. Kamaruzaman Jusoff, Universiti Putra Malaysia
Mr. Nikhil Patrick Lobo, CADES, India
Dr. Amit Wason, Rayat-Bahra Institute of Engineering & Boi-Technology, India
Dr. Rajesh Shrivastava, Govt. Benazir Science & Commerce College, Bhopal, India
Assist. Prof. Vishal Bharti, DCE, Gurgaon
Mrs. Sunita Bansal, Birla Institute of Technology & Science, India
Dr. R. Sudhakar, Dr.Mahalingam college of Engineering and Technology, India
Dr. Amit Kumar Garg, Shri Mata Vaishno Devi University, Katra(J&K), India
Assist. Prof. Raj Gaurang Tiwari, AZAD Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Hamed Taherdoost, Tehran, Iran
Mr. Amin Daneshmand Malayeri, YRC, IAU, Malayer Branch, Iran
Mr. Shantanu Pal, University of Calcutta, India
Dr. Terry H. Walcott, E-Promag Consultancy Group, United Kingdom
Dr. Ezekiel U OKIKE, University of Ibadan, Nigeria
Mr. P. Mahalingam, Caledonian College of Engineering, Oman
Dr. Mahmoud M. A. Abd Ellatif, Mansoura University, Egypt

Prof. Kunwar S. Vaisla, BCT Kumaon Engineering College, India
Prof. Mahesh H. Panchal, Kalol Institute of Technology & Research Centre, India
Mr. Muhammad Asad, Technical University of Munich, Germany
Mr. AliReza Shams Shafigh, Azad Islamic university, Iran
Prof. S. V. Nagaraj, RMK Engineering College, India
Mr. Ashikali M Hasan, Senior Researcher, CelNet security, India
Dr. Adnan Shahid Khan, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Prakash Gajanan Burade, Nagpur University/ITM college of engg, Nagpur, India
Dr. Jagdish B.Helonde, Nagpur University/ITM college of engg, Nagpur, India
Professor, Doctor BOUHORMA Mohammed, Univertsity Abdelmalek Essaadi, Morocco
Mr. K. Thirumalaivasan, Pondicherry Engg. College, India
Mr. Umbarkar Anantkumar Janardan, Walchand College of Engineering, India
Mr. Ashish Chaurasia, Gyan Ganga Institute of Technology & Sciences, India
Mr. Sunil Taneja, Kurukshetra University, India
Mr. Fauzi Adi Rafrastara, Dian Nuswantoro University, Indonesia
Dr. Yaduvir Singh, Thapar University, India
Dr. Ioannis V. Koskosas, University of Western Macedonia, Greece
Dr. Vasantha Kalyani David, Avinashilingam University for women, Coimbatore
Dr. Ahmed Mansour Manasrah, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Miss. Nazanin Sadat Kazazi, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Saeed Rasouli Heikalabad, Islamic Azad University - Tabriz Branch, Iran
Assoc. Prof. Dharendra Mishra, SVKM's NMIMS University, India
Prof. Shapoor Zarei, UAE Inventors Association, UAE
Prof. B.Raja Sarath Kumar, Lenora College of Engineering, India
Dr. Bashir Alam, Jamia millia Islamia, Delhi, India
Prof. Anant J Umbarkar, Walchand College of Engg., India
Assist. Prof. B. Bharathi, Sathyabama University, India
Dr. Fokrul Alom Mazarbhuiya, King Khalid University, Saudi Arabia
Prof. T.S.Jeyali Laseeth, Anna University of Technology, Tirunelveli, India
Dr. M. Balraju, Jawahar Lal Nehru Technological University Hyderabad, India
Dr. Vijayalakshmi M. N., R.V.College of Engineering, Bangalore
Prof. Walid Moudani, Lebanese University, Lebanon
Dr. Saurabh Pal, VBS Purvanchal University, Jaunpur, India
Associate Prof. Suneet Chaudhary, Dehradun Institute of Technology, India
Associate Prof. Dr. Manuj Darbari, BBD University, India
Ms. Prema Selvaraj, K.S.R College of Arts and Science, India
Assist. Prof. Ms.S.Sasikala, KSR College of Arts & Science, India
Mr. Sukhvinder Singh Deora, NC Institute of Computer Sciences, India
Dr. Abhay Bansal, Amity School of Engineering & Technology, India
Ms. Sumita Mishra, Amity School of Engineering and Technology, India
Professor S. Viswanadha Raju, JNT University Hyderabad, India
Mr. Asghar Shahrzad Khashandarag, Islamic Azad University Tabriz Branch, India
Mr. Manoj Sharma, Panipat Institute of Engg. & Technology, India
Mr. Shakeel Ahmed, King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Mohamed Ali Mahjoub, Institute of Engineer of Monastir, Tunisia
Mr. Adri Jovin J.J., SriGuru Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Sukumar Senthilkumar, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia

Mr. Rakesh Bharati, Dehradun Institute of Technology Dehradun, India
Mr. Shervan Fekri Ershad, Shiraz International University, Iran
Mr. Md. Safiqul Islam, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
Mr. Mahmudul Hasan, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
Prof. Mandakini Tayade, UIT, RGTU, Bhopal, India
Ms. Sarla More, UIT, RGTU, Bhopal, India
Mr. Tushar Hrishikesh Jaware, R.C. Patel Institute of Technology, Shirpur, India
Ms. C. Divya, Dr G R Damodaran College of Science, Coimbatore, India
Mr. Fahimuddin Shaik, Annamacharya Institute of Technology & Sciences, India
Dr. M. N. Giri Prasad, JNTUCE, Pulivendula, A.P., India
Assist. Prof. Chintan M Bhatt, Charotar University of Science And Technology, India
Prof. Sahista Machchhar, Marwadi Education Foundation's Group of institutions, India
Assist. Prof. Navnish Goel, S. D. College Of Engineering & Technology, India
Mr. Khaja Kamaluddin, Sirt University, Sirt, Libya
Mr. Mohammad Zaidul Karim, Daffodil International, Bangladesh
Mr. M. Vijayakumar, KSR College of Engineering, Tiruchengode, India
Mr. S. A. Ahsan Rajon, Khulna University, Bangladesh
Dr. Muhammad Mohsin Nazir, LCW University Lahore, Pakistan
Mr. Mohammad Asadul Hoque, University of Alabama, USA
Mr. P.V.Sarathchand, Indur Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Durgesh Samadhiya, Chung Hua University, Taiwan
Dr Venu Kuthadi, University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg, RSA
Dr. (Er) Jasvir Singh, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, Punjab, India
Mr. Jasmin Cosic, Min. of the Interior of Una-sana canton, B&H, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr S. Rajalakshmi, Botho College, South Africa
Dr. Mohamed Sarrab, De Montfort University, UK
Mr. Basappa B. Kodada, Canara Engineering College, India
Assist. Prof. K. Ramana, Annamacharya Institute of Technology and Sciences, India
Dr. Ashu Gupta, Apeejay Institute of Management, Jalandhar, India
Assist. Prof. Shaik Rasool, Shadan College of Engineering & Technology, India
Assist. Prof. K. Suresh, Annamacharya Institute of Tech & Sci. Rajampet, AP, India
Dr . G. Singaravel, K.S.R. College of Engineering, India
Dr B. G. Geetha, K.S.R. College of Engineering, India
Assist. Prof. Kavita Choudhary, ITM University, Gurgaon
Dr. Mehrdad Jalali, Azad University, Mashhad, Iran
Megha Goel, Shamli Institute of Engineering and Technology, Shamli, India
Mr. Chi-Hua Chen, Institute of Information Management, National Chiao-Tung University, Taiwan (R.O.C.)
Assoc. Prof. A. Rajendran, RVS College of Engineering and Technology, India
Assist. Prof. S. Jaganathan, RVS College of Engineering and Technology, India
Assoc. Prof. (Dr.) A S N Chakravarthy, JNTUK University College of Engineering Vizianagaram (State University)
Assist. Prof. Deepshikha Patel, Technocrat Institute of Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Maram Balajee, GMRIT, India
Assist. Prof. Monika Bhatnagar, TIT, India
Prof. Gaurang Panchal, Charotar University of Science & Technology, India
Prof. Anand K. Tripathi, Computer Society of India
Prof. Jyoti Chaudhary, High Performance Computing Research Lab, India
Assist. Prof. Supriya Raheja, ITM University, India

Dr. Pankaj Gupta, Microsoft Corporation, U.S.A.
Assist. Prof. Panchamukesh Chandaka, Hyderabad Institute of Tech. & Management, India
Prof. Mohan H.S, SJB Institute Of Technology, India
Mr. Hossein Malekinezhad, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Mr. Zatin Gupta, Universti Malaysia, Malaysia
Assist. Prof. Amit Chauhan, Phonics Group of Institutions, India
Assist. Prof. Ajal A. J., METS School Of Engineering, India
Mrs. Omowunmi Omobola Adeyemo, University of Ibadan, Nigeria
Dr. Bharat Bhushan Agarwal, I.F.T.M. University, India
Md. Nazrul Islam, University of Western Ontario, Canada
Tushar Kanti, L.N.C.T, Bhopal, India
Er. Aumreesh Kumar Saxena, SIRTs College Bhopal, India
Mr. Mohammad Monirul Islam, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
Dr. Kashif Nisar, University Utara Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Wei Zheng, Rutgers Univ/ A10 Networks, USA
Associate Prof. Rituraj Jain, Vyas Institute of Engg & Tech, Jodhpur – Rajasthan
Assist. Prof. Apoorvi Sood, I.T.M. University, India
Dr. Kayhan Zrar Ghafoor, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Swapnil Sonar, Truba Institute College of Engineering & Technology, Indore, India
Ms. Yogita Gigras, I.T.M. University, India
Associate Prof. Neelima Sadineni, Pydha Engineering College, India Pydha Engineering College
Assist. Prof. K. Deepika Rani, HITAM, Hyderabad
Ms. Shikha Maheshwari, Jaipur Engineering College & Research Centre, India
Prof. Dr V S Giridhar Akula, Avanthi's Scientific Tech. & Research Academy, Hyderabad
Prof. Dr.S.Saravanan, Muthayammal Engineering College, India
Mr. Mehdi Golsorkhatabar Amiri, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Prof. Amit Sadanand Savyanavar, MITCOE, Pune, India
Assist. Prof. P.Oliver Jayaprakash, Anna University, Chennai
Assist. Prof. Ms. Sujata, ITM University, Gurgaon, India
Dr. Asoke Nath, St. Xavier's College, India
Mr. Masoud Rafiqhi, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Assist. Prof. RamBabu Pemula, NIMRA College of Engineering & Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Ms Rita Chhikara, ITM University, Gurgaon, India
Mr. Sandeep Maan, Government Post Graduate College, India
Prof. Dr. S. Muralidharan, Mepco Schlenk Engineering College, India
Associate Prof. T.V.Sai Krishna, QIS College of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. R. Balu, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, India
Assist. Prof. Shekhar. R, Dr.SM College of Engineering, India
Prof. P. Senthilkumar, Vivekanandha Institue of Engineering and Technology for Woman, India
Mr. M. Kamarajan, PSNA College of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. Angajala Srinivasa Rao, Jawaharlal Nehru Technical University, India
Assist. Prof. C. Venkatesh, A.I.T.S, Rajampet, India
Mr. Afshin Rezakhani Roozbahani, Ayatollah Boroujerdi University, Iran
Mr. Laxmi chand, SCTL, Noida, India
Dr. Dr. Abdul Hannan, Vivekanand College, Aurangabad
Prof. Mahesh Panchal, KITRC, Gujarat
Dr. A. Subramani, K.S.R. College of Engineering, Tiruchengode

Assist. Prof. Prakash M, Rajalakshmi Engineering College, Chennai, India
Assist. Prof. Akhilesh K Sharma, Sir Padampat Singhanian University, India
Ms. Varsha Sahni, Guru Nanak Dev Engineering College, Ludhiana, India
Associate Prof. Trilochan Rout, NM Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Srikanta Kumar Mohapatra, NMIET, Orissa, India
Mr. Waqas Haider Bangyal, Iqra University Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. S. Vijayaragavan, Christ College of Engineering and Technology, Pondicherry, India
Prof. Elboukhari Mohamed, University Mohammed First, Oujda, Morocco
Dr. Muhammad Asif Khan, King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Nagy Ramadan Darwish Omran, Cairo University, Egypt.
Assistant Prof. Anand Nayyar, KCL Institute of Management and Technology, India
Mr. G. Premsankar, Ericsson, India
Assist. Prof. T. Hemalatha, VELS University, India
Prof. Tejaswini Apte, University of Pune, India
Dr. Edmund Ng Giap Weng, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Malaysia
Mr. Mahdi Nouri, Iran University of Science and Technology, Iran
Associate Prof. S. Asif Hussain, Annamacharya Institute of technology & Sciences, India
Mrs. Kavita Pabreja, Maharaja Surajmal Institute (an affiliate of GGSIP University), India
Mr. Vorugunti Chandra Sekhar, DA-IICT, India
Mr. Muhammad Najmi Ahmad Zabidi, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Aderemi A. Atayero, Covenant University, Nigeria
Assist. Prof. Osama Sohaib, Balochistan University of Information Technology, Pakistan
Assist. Prof. K. Suresh, Annamacharya Institute of Technology and Sciences, India
Mr. Hassen Mohammed Abdullaah Alsafi, International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM) Malaysia
Mr. Robail Yasrab, Virtual University of Pakistan, Pakistan
Mr. R. Balu, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, India
Prof. Anand Nayyar, KCL Institute of Management and Technology, Jalandhar
Assoc. Prof. Vivek S Deshpande, MIT College of Engineering, India
Prof. K. Saravanan, Anna university Coimbatore, India
Dr. Ravendra Singh, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, India
Mr. V. Mathivanan, IBRA College of Technology, Sultanate of OMAN
Assoc. Prof. S. Asif Hussain, AITS, India
Assist. Prof. C. Venkatesh, AITS, India
Mr. Sami Ulhaq, SZABIST Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. B. Justus Rabi, Institute of Science & Technology, India
Mr. Anuj Kumar Yadav, Dehradun Institute of technology, India
Mr. Alejandro Mosquera, University of Alicante, Spain
Assist. Prof. Arjun Singh, Sir Padampat Singhanian University (SPSU), Udaipur, India
Dr. Smriti Agrawal, JB Institute of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad
Assist. Prof. Swathi Sambangi, Visakha Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Ms. Prabhjot Kaur, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, India
Mrs. Samaher AL-Hothali, Yanbu University College, Saudi Arabia
Prof. Rajneeshkaur Bedi, MIT College of Engineering, Pune, India
Mr. Hassen Mohammed Abdullaah Alsafi, International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM)
Dr. Wei Zhang, Amazon.com, Seattle, WA, USA
Mr. B. Santhosh Kumar, C S I College of Engineering, Tamil Nadu
Dr. K. Reji Kumar, N S S College, Pandalam, India

Assoc. Prof. K. Seshadri Sastry, EILM University, India
Mr. Kai Pan, UNC Charlotte, USA
Mr. Ruikar Sachin, SGGSIET, India
Prof. (Dr.) Vinodani Katiyar, Sri Ramswaroop Memorial University, India
Assoc. Prof., M. Giri, Sreenivasa Institute of Technology and Management Studies, India
Assoc. Prof. Labib Francis Gergis, Misr Academy for Engineering and Technology (MET), Egypt
Assist. Prof. Amanpreet Kaur, ITM University, India
Assist. Prof. Anand Singh Rajawat, Shri Vaishnav Institute of Technology & Science, Indore
Mrs. Hadeel Saleh Haj Aliwi, Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM), Malaysia
Dr. Abhay Bansal, Amity University, India
Dr. Mohammad A. Mezher, Fahad Bin Sultan University, KSA
Assist. Prof. Nidhi Arora, M.C.A. Institute, India
Prof. Dr. P. Suresh, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India
Dr. Kannan Balasubramanian, Mepco Schlenk Engineering College, India
Dr. S. Sankara Gomathi, Panimalar Engineering college, India
Prof. Anil kumar Suthar, Gujarat Technological University, L.C. Institute of Technology, India
Assist. Prof. R. Hubert Rajan, NOORUL ISLAM UNIVERSITY, India
Assist. Prof. Dr. Jyoti Mahajan, College of Engineering & Technology
Assist. Prof. Homam Reda El-Taj, College of Network Engineering, Saudi Arabia & Malaysia
Mr. Bijan Paul, Shahjalal University of Science & Technology, Bangladesh
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ch V Phani Krishna, KL University, India
Dr. Vishal Bhatnagar, Ambedkar Institute of Advanced Communication Technologies & Research, India
Dr. Lamir LAOUAMER, Al Qassim University, Dept. Info. Systems & European University of Brittany, Dept. Computer Science, UBO, Brest, France
Prof. Ashish Babanrao Sasankar, G.H.Raisoni Institute Of Information Technology, India
Prof. Pawan Kumar Goel, Shamli Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Ram Kumar Singh, S.V Subharti University, India
Assistant Prof. Sunish Kumar O S, Amalijothei College of Engineering, India
Dr Sanjay Bhargava, Banasthali University, India
Mr. Pankaj S. Kulkarni, AVEW's Shatabdi Institute of Technology, India
Mr. Roohollah Etemadi, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Mr. Oloruntoyin Sefiu Taiwo, Emmanuel Alayande College Of Education, Nigeria
Mr. Sumit Goyal, National Dairy Research Institute, India
Mr Jaswinder Singh Dilawari, Geeta Engineering College, India
Prof. Raghuraj Singh, Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur
Dr. S.K. Mahendran, Anna University, Chennai, India
Dr. Amit Wason, Hindustan Institute of Technology & Management, Punjab
Dr. Ashu Gupta, Apeejay Institute of Management, India
Assist. Prof. D. Asir Antony Gnana Singh, M.I.E.T Engineering College, India
Mrs Mina Farmanbar, Eastern Mediterranean University, Famagusta, North Cyprus
Mr. Maram Balajee, GMR Institute of Technology, India
Mr. Moiz S. Ansari, Isra University, Hyderabad, Pakistan
Mr. Adebayo, Olawale Surajudeen, Federal University of Technology Minna, Nigeria
Mr. Jasvir Singh, University College Of Engg., India
Mr. Vivek Tiwari, MANIT, Bhopal, India
Assoc. Prof. R. Navaneethakrishnan, Bharathiyar College of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Somdip Dey, St. Xavier's College, Kolkata, India

Mr. Souleymane Balla-Arabé, Xi'an University of Electronic Science and Technology, China
Mr. Mahabub Alam, Rajshahi University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh
Mr. Sathyapraksh P., S.K.P Engineering College, India
Dr. N. Karthikeyan, SNS College of Engineering, Anna University, India
Dr. Binod Kumar, JSPM's, Jayawant Technical Campus, Pune, India
Assoc. Prof. Dinesh Goyal, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, India
Mr. Md. Abdul Ahad, K L University, India
Mr. Vikas Bajpai, The LNM IIT, India
Dr. Manish Kumar Anand, Salesforce (R & D Analytics), San Francisco, USA
Assist. Prof. Dheeraj Murari, Kumaon Engineering College, India
Assoc. Prof. Dr. A. Muthukumaravel, VELS University, Chennai
Mr. A. Siles Balasingh, St. Joseph University in Tanzania, Tanzania
Mr. Ravindra Daga Badgujar, R C Patel Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Preeti Khanna, SVKM's NMIMS, School of Business Management, India
Mr. Kumar Dayanand, Cambridge Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Syed Asif Ali, SMI University Karachi, Pakistan
Prof. Pallvi Pandit, Himachal Pradesh University, India
Mr. Ricardo Verschueren, University of Gloucestershire, UK
Assist. Prof. Mamta Juneja, University Institute of Engineering and Technology, Panjab University, India
Assoc. Prof. P. Surendra Varma, NRI Institute of Technology, JNTU Kakinada, India
Assist. Prof. Gaurav Shrivastava, RGPV / SVITS Indore, India
Dr. S. Sumathi, Anna University, India
Assist. Prof. Ankita M. Kapadia, Charotar University of Science and Technology, India
Mr. Deepak Kumar, Indian Institute of Technology (BHU), India
Dr. Dr. Rajan Gupta, GGSIP University, New Delhi, India
Assist. Prof. M. Anand Kumar, Karpagam University, Coimbatore, India
Mr. Mr Arshad Mansoor, Pakistan Aeronautical Complex
Mr. Kapil Kumar Gupta, Ansal Institute of Technology and Management, India
Dr. Neeraj Tomer, SINE International Institute of Technology, Jaipur, India
Assist. Prof. Trunal J. Patel, C.G.Patel Institute of Technology, Uka Tarsadia University, Bardoli, Surat
Mr. Sivakumar, Codework solutions, India
Mr. Mohammad Sadegh Mirzaei, PGNR Company, Iran
Dr. Gerard G. Dumancas, Oklahoma Medical Research Foundation, USA
Mr. Varadala Sridhar, Varadhman College Engineering College, Affiliated To JNTU, Hyderabad
Assist. Prof. Manoj Dhawan, SVITS, Indore
Assoc. Prof. Chitreshh Banerjee, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur, India
Dr. S. Santhi, SCSVMV University, India
Mr. Davood Mohammadi Souran, Ministry of Energy of Iran, Iran
Mr. Shamim Ahmed, Bangladesh University of Business and Technology, Bangladesh
Mr. Sandeep Reddivari, Mississippi State University, USA
Assoc. Prof. Ousmane Thiare, Gaston Berger University, Senegal
Dr. Hazra Imran, Athabasca University, Canada
Dr. Setu Kumar Chaturvedi, Technocrats Institute of Technology, Bhopal, India
Mr. Mohd Dilshad Ansari, Jaypee University of Information Technology, India
Ms. Jaspreet Kaur, Distance Education LPU, India
Dr. D. Nagarajan, Salalah College of Technology, Sultanate of Oman
Dr. K.V.N.R.Sai Krishna, S.V.R.M. College, India

Mr. Himanshu Pareek, Center for Development of Advanced Computing (CDAC), India
Mr. Khaldi Amine, Badji Mokhtar University, Algeria
Mr. Mohammad Sadegh Mirzaei, Scientific Applied University, Iran
Assist. Prof. Khyati Chaudhary, Ram-eesh Institute of Engg. & Technology, India
Mr. Sanjay Agal, Pacific College of Engineering Udaipur, India
Mr. Abdul Mateen Ansari, King Khalid University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. H.S. Behera, Veer Surendra Sai University of Technology (VSSUT), India
Dr. Shrikant Tiwari, Shri Shankaracharya Group of Institutions (SSGI), India
Prof. Ganesh B. Regulwar, Shri Shankarprasad Agnihotri College of Engg, India
Prof. Pinnamaneni Bhanu Prasad, Matrix vision GmbH, Germany
Dr. Shrikant Tiwari, Shri Shankaracharya Technical Campus (SSTC), India
Dr. Siddesh G.K., : Dayananada Sagar College of Engineering, Bangalore, India
Dr. Nadir Bouchama, CERIST Research Center, Algeria
Dr. R. Sathishkumar, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering, India
Assistant Prof (Dr.) Mohamed Moussaoui, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Morocco
Dr. S. Malathi, Panimalar Engineering College, Chennai, India
Dr. V. Subedha, Panimalar Institute of Technology, Chennai, India
Dr. Prashant Panse, Swami Vivekanand College of Engineering, Indore, India
Dr. Hamza Aldabbas, Al-Balqa'a Applied University, Jordan
Dr. G. Rasitha Banu, Vel's University, Chennai
Dr. V. D. Ambeth Kumar, Panimalar Engineering College, Chennai
Prof. Anuranjan Misra, Bhagwant Institute of Technology, Ghaziabad, India
Ms. U. Sinthuja, PSG college of arts & science, India
Dr. Ehsan Saradar Torshizi, Urmia University, Iran
Dr. Shamneesh Sharma, APG Shimla University, Shimla (H.P.), India
Assistant Prof. A. S. Syed Navaz, Muthayammal College of Arts & Science, India
Assistant Prof. Ranjit Panigrahi, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Technology, Majitar, Sikkim
Dr. Khaled Eskaf, Arab Academy for Science ,Technology & Maritime Transportation, Egypt
Dr. Nishant Gupta, University of Jammu, India
Assistant Prof. Nagarajan Sankaran, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, India
Assistant Prof. Tribikram Pradhan, Manipal Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Nasser Lotfi, Eastern Mediterranean University, Northern Cyprus
Dr. R. Manavalan, K S Rangasamy college of Arts and Science, Tamilnadu, India
Assistant Prof. P. Krishna Sankar, K S Rangasamy college of Arts and Science, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. Rahul Malik, Cisco Systems, USA
Dr. S. C. Lingareddy, ALPHA College of Engineering, India
Assistant Prof. Mohammed Shuaib, Interat University, Lucknow, India
Dr. Sachin Yele, Sanghvi Institute of Management & Science, India
Dr. T. Thambidurai, Sun Univercell, Singapore
Prof. Anandkumar Telang, BKIT, India
Assistant Prof. R. Poorvadevi, SCSVMV University, India
Dr Uttam Mande, Gitam University, India
Dr. Poornima Girish Naik, Shahu Institute of Business Education and Research (SIBER), India
Prof. Md. Abu Kausar, Jaipur National University, Jaipur, India
Dr. Mohammed Zuber, AISECT University, India
Prof. Kalum Priyanath Udagepola, King Abdulaziz University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. K. R. Ananth, Velalar College of Engineering and Technology, India

Assistant Prof. Sanjay Sharma, Roorkee Engineering & Management Institute Shamli (U.P), India
Assistant Prof. Panem Charan Arur, Priyadarshini Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Ashwak Mahmood muhsen alabaichi, Karbala University / College of Science, Iraq
Dr. Urmila Shrawankar, G H Raison College of Engineering, Nagpur (MS), India
Dr. Krishan Kumar Paliwal, Panipat Institute of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. Mukesh Negi, Tech Mahindra, India
Dr. Anuj Kumar Singh, Amity University Gurgaon, India
Dr. Babar Shah, Gyeongsang National University, South Korea
Assistant Prof. Jayprakash Upadhyay, SRI-TECH Jabalpur, India
Assistant Prof. Varadala Sridhar, Vidya Jyothi Institute of Technology, India
Assistant Prof. Parameshachari B D, KSIT, Bangalore, India
Assistant Prof. Ankit Garg, Amity University, Haryana, India
Assistant Prof. Rajashe Karappa, SDMCET, Karnataka, India
Assistant Prof. Varun Jasuja, GNIT, India
Assistant Prof. Sonal Honale, Abha Gaikwad Patil College of Engineering Nagpur, India
Dr. Pooja Choudhary, CT Group of Institutions, NIT Jalandhar, India
Dr. Faouzi Hidoussi, UHL Batna, Algeria
Dr. Naseer Ali Hussein, Wasit University, Iraq
Assistant Prof. Vinod Kumar Shukla, Amity University, Dubai
Dr. Ahmed Farouk Metwaly, K L University
Mr. Mohammed Noaman Murad, Cihan University, Iraq
Dr. Suxing Liu, Arkansas State University, USA
Dr. M. Gomathi, Velalar College of Engineering and Technology, India
Assistant Prof. Sumardiono, College PGRI Blitar, Indonesia
Dr. Latika Kharb, Jagan Institute of Management Studies (JIMS), Delhi, India
Associate Prof. S. Raja, Pauls College of Engineering and Technology, Tamilnadu, India
Assistant Prof. Seyed Reza Pakize, Shahid Sani High School, Iran
Dr. Thiyagu Nagaraj, University-INO, India
Assistant Prof. Noreen Sarai, Harare Institute of Technology, Zimbabwe
Assistant Prof. Gajanand Sharma, Suresh Gyan Vihar University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India
Assistant Prof. Mapari Vikas Prakash, Siddhant COE, Sudumbare, Pune, India
Dr. Devesh Katiyar, Shri Ramswaroop Memorial University, India
Dr. Shenshen Liang, University of California, Santa Cruz, US
Assistant Prof. Mohammad Abu Omar, Limkokwing University of Creative Technology- Malaysia
Mr. Snehasis Banerjee, Tata Consultancy Services, India
Assistant Prof. Kibona Lusekelo, Ruaha Catholic University (RUCU), Tanzania
Assistant Prof. Adib Kabir Chowdhury, University College Technology Sarawak, Malaysia
Dr. Ying Yang, Computer Science Department, Yale University, USA
Dr. Vinay Shukla, Institute Of Technology & Management, India
Dr. Liviu Octavian Maftciu-Scai, West University of Timisoara, Romania
Assistant Prof. Rana Khudhair Abbas Ahmed, Al-Rafidain University College, Iraq
Assistant Prof. Nitin A. Naik, S.R.T.M. University, India
Dr. Timothy Powers, University of Hertfordshire, UK
Dr. S. Prasath, Bharathiar University, Erode, India
Dr. Ritu Shrivastava, SIRTIS Bhopal, India
Prof. Rohit Shrivastava, Mittal Institute of Technology, Bhopal, India
Dr. Gianina Mihai, Dunarea de Jos" University of Galati, Romania

Assistant Prof. Ms. T. Kalai Selvi, Erode Sengunthar Engineering College, India
Assistant Prof. Ms. C. Kavitha, Erode Sengunthar Engineering College, India
Assistant Prof. K. Sinivasamoorthi, Erode Sengunthar Engineering College, India
Assistant Prof. Mallikarjun C Sarsamba Bheemna Khandre Institute Technology, Bhalki, India
Assistant Prof. Vishwanath Chikaraddi, Veermata Jijabai technological Institute (Central Technological Institute), India
Assistant Prof. Dr. Ikvinderpal Singh, Trai Shatabdi GGS Khalsa College, India
Assistant Prof. Mohammed Noaman Murad, Cihan University, Iraq
Professor Yousef Farhaoui, Moulay Ismail University, Errachidia, Morocco
Dr. Parul Verma, Amity University, India
Professor Yousef Farhaoui, Moulay Ismail University, Errachidia, Morocco
Assistant Prof. Madhavi Dhingra, Amity University, Madhya Pradesh, India
Assistant Prof.. G. Selvavinayagam, SNS College of Technology, Coimbatore, India
Assistant Prof. Madhavi Dhingra, Amity University, MP, India
Professor Kartheesan Log, Anna University, Chennai
Professor Vasudeva Acharya, Shri Madhwa vadiraja Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Asif Iqbal Hajamydeen, Management & Science University, Malaysia
Assistant Prof., Mahendra Singh Meena, Amity University Haryana
Assistant Professor Manjeet Kaur, Amity University Haryana
Dr. Mohamed Abd El-Basset Matwalli, Zagazig University, Egypt
Dr. Ramani Kannan, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Malaysia
Assistant Prof. S. Jagadeesan Subramaniam, Anna University, India
Assistant Prof. Dharmendra Choudhary, Tripura University, India
Assistant Prof. Deepika Vodnala, SR Engineering College, India
Dr. Kai Cong, Intel Corporation & Computer Science Department, Portland State University, USA
Dr. Kailas R Patil, Vishwakarma Institute of Information Technology (VIIT), India
Dr. Omar A. Alzubi, Faculty of IT / Al-Balqa Applied University, Jordan
Assistant Prof. Kareemullah Shaik, Nimra Institute of Science and Technology, India
Assistant Prof. Chirag Modi, NIT Goa
Dr. R. Ramkumar, Nandha Arts And Science College, India
Dr. Priyadarshini Vydhialingam, Harathiar University, India
Dr. P. S. Jagadeesh Kumar, DBIT, Bangalore, Karnataka
Dr. Vikas Thada, AMITY University, Pachgaon
Dr. T. A. Ashok Kumar, Institute of Management, Christ University, Bangalore
Dr. Shaheera Rashwan, Informatics Research Institute
Dr. S. Preetha Gunasekar, Bharathiyar University, India
Asst Professor Sameer Dev Sharma, Uttaranchal University, Dehradun
Dr. Zhihan Iv, Chinese Academy of Science, China
Dr. Ikvinderpal Singh, Trai Shatabdi GGS Khalsa College, Amritsar
Dr. Umar Ruhi, University of Ottawa, Canada
Dr. Jasmin Cosic, University of Bihac, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Homam Reda El-Taj, University of Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Dr. Mostafa Ghobaei Arani, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Dr. Ayyasamy Ayyanar, Annamalai University, India
Dr. Selvakumar Manickam, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Murali Krishna Namana, GITAM University, India
Dr. Smriti Agrawal, Chaitanya Bharathi Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, India
Professor Vimalathithan Rathinasabapathy, Karpagam College Of Engineering, India

Dr. Sushil Chandra Dimri, Graphic Era University, India
Dr. Dinh-Sinh Mai, Le Quy Don Technical University, Vietnam
Dr. S. Rama Sree, Aditya Engg. College, India
Dr. Ehab T. Alnfrawy, Sadat Academy, Egypt
Dr. Patrick D. Cerna, Haramaya University, Ethiopia
Dr. Vishal Jain, Bharati Vidyapeeth's Institute of Computer Applications and Management (BVICAM), India
Associate Prof. Dr. Jiliang Zhang, North Eastern University, China
Dr. Sharefa Murad, Middle East University, Jordan
Dr. Ajeet Singh Poonia, Govt. College of Engineering & technology, Rajasthan, India
Dr. Vahid Esmaeaelzadeh, University of Science and Technology, Iran
Dr. Jacek M. Czerniak, Casimir the Great University in Bydgoszcz, Institute of Technology, Poland
Associate Prof. Anisur Rehman Nasir, Jamia Millia Islamia University
Assistant Prof. Imran Ahmad, COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Pakistan
Professor Ghulam Qasim, Preston University, Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. Parameshachari B D, GSSS Institute of Engineering and Technology for Women
Dr. Wencan Luo, University of Pittsburgh, US
Dr. Musa PEKER, Faculty of Technology, Mugla Sitki Kocman University, Turkey
Dr. Gunasekaran Shanmugam, Anna University, India
Dr. Binh P. Nguyen, National University of Singapore, Singapore
Dr. Rajkumar Jain, Indian Institute of Technology Indore, India
Dr. Imtiaz Ali Halepoto, QUEST Nawabshah, Pakistan
Dr. Shaligram Prajapat, Devi Ahilya University Indore India
Dr. Sunita Singhal, Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani, India
Dr. Ijaz Ali Shoukat, King Saud University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Anuj Gupta, IKG Punjab Technical University, India
Dr. Sonali Saini, IES-IPS Academy, India
Dr. Krishan Kumar, Moti Lal Nehru National Institute of Technology, Allahabad, India
Dr. Z. Faizal Khan, College of Engineering, Shaqra University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Prof. M. Padmavathamma, S.V. University Tirupati, India
Prof. A. Velayudham, Cape Institute of Technology, India
Prof. Seifeidne Kadry, American University of the Middle East
Dr. J. Durga Prasad Rao, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur
Assistant Prof. Najam Hasan, Dhofar University
Dr. G. Suseendran, Vels University, Pallavaram, Chennai
Prof. Ankit Faldu, Gujarat Technological University- Atmiya Institute of Technology and Science
Dr. Ali Habiboghli, Islamic Azad University
Dr. Deepak Dembla, JECRC University, Jaipur, India
Dr. Pankaj Rajan, Walmart Labs, USA
Assistant Prof. Radoslava Kraveva, South-West University "Neofit Rilski", Bulgaria
Assistant Prof. Medhavi Shriwas, Shri vaishnav institute of Technology, India
Associate Prof. Sedat Akleylek, Ondokuz Mayıs University, Turkey
Dr. U.V. Arivazhagu, Kingston Engineering College Affiliated To Anna University, India
Dr. Touseef Ali, University of Engineering and Technology, Taxila, Pakistan
Assistant Prof. Naren Jeeva, SASTRA University, India
Dr. Riccardo Colella, University of Salento, Italy
Dr. Enache Maria Cristina, University of Galati, Romania
Dr. Senthil P, Kurinji College of Arts & Science, India

Dr. Hasan Ashrafi-rizi, Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, Isfahan, Iran
Dr. Mazhar Malik, Institute of Southern Punjab, Pakistan
Dr. Yajie Miao, Carnegie Mellon University, USA
Dr. Kamran Shaukat, University of the Punjab, Pakistan
Dr. Sasikaladevi N., SASTRA University, India
Dr. Ali Asghar Rahmani Hosseinabadi, Islamic Azad University Ayatollah Amoli Branch, Amol, Iran
Dr. Velin Kralev, South-West University "Neofit Rilski", Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria
Dr. Marius Iulian Mihailescu, LUMINA - The University of South-East Europe
Dr. Sriramula Nagaprasad, S.R.R.Govt.Arts & Science College, Karimnagar, India
Prof (Dr.) Namrata Dhanda, Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam Technical University, Lucknow, India
Dr. Javed Ahmed Mahar, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur Mir's, Pakistan
Dr. B. Narendra Kumar Rao, Sree Vidyanikethan Engineering College, India
Dr. Shahzad Anwar, University of Engineering & Technology Peshawar, Pakistan
Dr. Basit Shahzad, King Saud University, Riyadh - Saudi Arabia
Dr. Nilamadhab Mishra, Chang Gung University
Dr. Sachin Kumar, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee
Dr. Santosh Nanda, Biju-Pattnaik University of Technology
Dr. Sherzod Turaev, International Islamic University Malaysia
Dr. Yilun Shang, Tongji University, Department of Mathematics, Shanghai, China
Dr. Nuzhat Shaikh, Modern Education society's College of Engineering, Pune, India
Dr. Parul Verma, Amity University, Lucknow campus, India
Dr. Rachid Alaoui, Agadir Ibn Zohr University, Agadir, Morocco
Dr. Dharmendra Patel, Charotar University of Science and Technology, India
Dr. Dong Zhang, University of Central Florida, USA
Dr. Kennedy Chinedu Okafor, Federal University of Technology Owerri, Nigeria
Prof. C Ram Kumar, Dr NGP Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Sandeep Gupta, GGS IP University, New Delhi, India
Dr. Shahanawaj Ahamad, University of Ha'il, Ha'il City, Ministry of Higher Education, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Dr. Najeed Ahmed Khan, NED University of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. Sajid Ullah Khan, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Malaysia
Dr. Muhammad Asif, National Textile University Faisalabad, Pakistan
Dr. Yu BI, University of Central Florida, Orlando, FL, USA
Dr. Brijendra Kumar Joshi, Research Center, Military College of Telecommunication Engineering, India
Prof. Dr. Nak Eun Cho, Pukyong National University, Korea
Prof. Wasim Ul-Haq, Faculty of Science, Majmaah University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Mohsan Raza, G.C University Faisalabad, Pakistan
Dr. Syed Zakar Hussain Bukhari, National Science and Technology Azad Jamu Kashmir, Pakistan
Dr. Ruksar Fatima, KBN College of Engineering, Gulbarga, Karnataka, India
Associate Professor S. Karpagavalli, Department of Computer Science, PSGR Krishnammal College for Women
Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. Bushra Mohamed Elamin Elhaim, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Shamik Tiwari, Department of CSE, CET, Mody University, Lakshmangarh
Dr. Rohit Raja, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Shri Shankaracharya Group of Institutions, India
Prof. Dr. Aqeel-ur-Rehman, Department of Computing, HIET, FEST, Hamdard University, Pakistan
Dr. Nageswara Rao Moparthi, Velagapudi Ramakrishna Siddhartha Engineering College, India
Dr. Mohd Muqem, Department of Computer Application, Integral University, Lucknow, India
Dr. Zeeshan Bhatti, Institute of Information and Communication Technology, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan

Dr. Emrah Irmak, Biomedical Engineering Department, Karabuk University, Turkey
Dr. Fouad Abdulameer salman, School of Informatics and Applied Mathematics, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu
Dr. N. Prasath, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, KPR Institute of Engineering and Technology, Arasur, Coimbatore
Dr. Hasan Ashrafi-rizi, Health Information Technology Research Center, Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, Hezar Jerib Avenue, Isfahan, Iran
Dr. N. Sasikaladevi, School of Computing, SASTRA University, Thirumalisamudram, Tamilnadu, India.
Dr. Anchit Bijalwan, Arba Minch University, Ethiopia
Dr. K. Sathishkumar, BlueCrest University College, Accra North, Ghana, West Africa
Dr. Dr. Parameshachari B D, GSSS Institute of Engineering and Technology for Women, Affiliated to Visvesvaraya Technological University, Belagavi
Dr. C. Shoba Bindu, Dept. of CSE, JNTUA College of Engineering, India
Dr. M. Inbavalli, ER. Perumal Manimekalai College of Engineering, Hosur, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. Vidya Sagar Ponnamp, Dept. of IT, Velagapudi Ramakrishna Siddhartha Engineering College, India
Dr. Kelvin LO M. F., The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong
Prof. Karimella Vikram, G.H. Rasoni College of Engineering & Management, Pune, India
Dr. Shajilin Loret J.B., VV College of Engineering, India
Dr. P. Sujatha, Department of Computer Science at Vels University, Chennai
Dr. Vaibhav Sundriyal, Old Dominion University Research Foundation, USA
Dr. Md Masud Rana, Khulna University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh
Dr. Gurcharan Singh, Khalsa College Amritsar, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, India
Dr. Richard Otieno Omollo, Department of Computer Science and Software Engineering, Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology, Kenya
Prof. (Dr) Amit Verma, Computer Science & Engineering, Chandigarh Engineering College, Landran, Mohali, India
Dr. Vidya Sagar Ponnamp, Velagapudi Ramakrishna Siddhartha Engineering College, India
Dr. Bohui Wang, School of Aerospace Science and Technology, Xidian University, P.R. China
Dr. M. Anjan Kumar, Department of Computer Science, Satavahana University, Karimnagar
Dr. Hanumanthappa J., DoS in CS, Uni of Mysuru, Karnataka, India
Dr. Pouya Derakhshan-Barjoei, Dept. of Telecommunication and Engineering, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Dr. Tanweer Alam, Islamic University of Madinah, Dept. of Computer Science, College of Computer and Information System, Al Madinah, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Kumar Keshamoni, Dept. of ECE, Vaagdevi Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India
Dr. G. Rajkumar, N.M.S.S.Vellaichamy Nadar College, Madurai, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. P. Mayil Vel Kumar, Karpagam Institute of Technology, Coimbatore, India
Dr. M. Yaswanth Bhanu Murthy, Vasireddy Venkatadri Institute of Technology, Guntur, A.P., India
Asst. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Barış TABAKCIOĞLU, Bursa Technical University, Turkey
Dr. Mohd. Muntjir, College of Computers and Information Technology, Taif University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Dr. Sanjay Agal, Aravali Institute of Technical Studies, Udaipur, India
Dr. Shanshan Tuo, xAd Inc., US
Dr. Subhadra Shaw, AKS University, Satna, India
Dr. Piyush Anand, Noida International University, Greater Noida, India
Dr. Brijendra Kumar Joshi, Research Center Military College of Telecommunication Engineering, India
Dr. V. Sreerama Murthy, GMRIT, Rajam, AP, India
Dr. S. Nagarajan, Annamalai University, India
Prof. Pramod Bhausaheb Deshmukh, D. Y. Patil College of Engineering, Akurdi, Pune, India

CALL FOR PAPERS
International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security

IJCSIS 2021-2022

ISSN: 1947-5500

<http://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>

International Journal Computer Science and Information Security, IJCSIS, is the premier scholarly venue in the areas of computer science and security issues. IJCSIS 2011 will provide a high profile, leading edge platform for researchers and engineers alike to publish state-of-the-art research in the respective fields of information technology and communication security. The journal will feature a diverse mixture of publication articles including core and applied computer science related topics.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the special issue by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to. Submissions may span a broad range of topics, e.g.:

Track A: Security

Access control, Anonymity, Audit and audit reduction & Authentication and authorization, Applied cryptography, Cryptanalysis, Digital Signatures, Biometric security, Boundary control devices, Certification and accreditation, Cross-layer design for security, Security & Network Management, Data and system integrity, Database security, Defensive information warfare, Denial of service protection, Intrusion Detection, Anti-malware, Distributed systems security, Electronic commerce, E-mail security, Spam, Phishing, E-mail fraud, Virus, worms, Trojan Protection, Grid security, Information hiding and watermarking & Information survivability, Insider threat protection, Integrity
Intellectual property protection, Internet/Intranet Security, Key management and key recovery, Language-based security, Mobile and wireless security, Mobile, Ad Hoc and Sensor Network Security, Monitoring and surveillance, Multimedia security ,Operating system security, Peer-to-peer security, Performance Evaluations of Protocols & Security Application, Privacy and data protection, Product evaluation criteria and compliance, Risk evaluation and security certification, Risk/vulnerability assessment, Security & Network Management, Security Models & protocols, Security threats & countermeasures (DDoS, MiM, Session Hijacking, Replay attack etc.), Trusted computing, Ubiquitous Computing Security, Virtualization security, VoIP security, Web 2.0 security, Submission Procedures, Active Defense Systems, Adaptive Defense Systems, Benchmark, Analysis and Evaluation of Security Systems, Distributed Access Control and Trust Management, Distributed Attack Systems and Mechanisms, Distributed Intrusion Detection/Prevention Systems, Denial-of-Service Attacks and Countermeasures, High Performance Security Systems, Identity Management and Authentication, Implementation, Deployment and Management of Security Systems, Intelligent Defense Systems, Internet and Network Forensics, Large-scale Attacks and Defense, RFID Security and Privacy, Security Architectures in Distributed Network Systems, Security for Critical Infrastructures, Security for P2P systems and Grid Systems, Security in E-Commerce, Security and Privacy in Wireless Networks, Secure Mobile Agents and Mobile Code, Security Protocols, Security Simulation and Tools, Security Theory and Tools, Standards and Assurance Methods, Trusted Computing, Viruses, Worms, and Other Malicious Code, World Wide Web Security, Novel and emerging secure architecture, Study of attack strategies, attack modeling, Case studies and analysis of actual attacks, Continuity of Operations during an attack, Key management, Trust management, Intrusion detection techniques, Intrusion response, alarm management, and correlation analysis, Study of tradeoffs between security and system performance, Intrusion tolerance systems, Secure protocols, Security in wireless networks (e.g. mesh networks, sensor networks, etc.), Cryptography and Secure Communications, Computer Forensics, Recovery and Healing, Security Visualization, Formal Methods in Security, Principles for Designing a Secure Computing System, Autonomic Security, Internet Security, Security in Health Care Systems, Security Solutions Using Reconfigurable Computing, Adaptive and Intelligent Defense Systems, Authentication and Access control, Denial of service attacks and countermeasures, Identity, Route and

Location Anonymity schemes, Intrusion detection and prevention techniques, Cryptography, encryption algorithms and Key management schemes, Secure routing schemes, Secure neighbor discovery and localization, Trust establishment and maintenance, Confidentiality and data integrity, Security architectures, deployments and solutions, Emerging threats to cloud-based services, Security model for new services, Cloud-aware web service security, Information hiding in Cloud Computing, Securing distributed data storage in cloud, Security, privacy and trust in mobile computing systems and applications, **Middleware security & Security features:** middleware software is an asset on its own and has to be protected, interaction between security-specific and other middleware features, e.g., context-awareness, **Middleware-level security monitoring and measurement:** metrics and mechanisms for quantification and evaluation of security enforced by the middleware, **Security co-design:** trade-off and co-design between application-based and middleware-based security, **Policy-based management:** innovative support for policy-based definition and enforcement of security concerns, **Identification and authentication mechanisms:** Means to capture application specific constraints in defining and enforcing access control rules, **Middleware-oriented security patterns:** identification of patterns for sound, reusable security, **Security in aspect-based middleware:** mechanisms for isolating and enforcing security aspects, **Security in agent-based platforms:** protection for mobile code and platforms, Smart Devices: Biometrics, National ID cards, Embedded Systems Security and TPMs, RFID Systems Security, Smart Card Security, Pervasive Systems: Digital Rights Management (DRM) in pervasive environments, Intrusion Detection and Information Filtering, Localization Systems Security (Tracking of People and Goods), Mobile Commerce Security, Privacy Enhancing Technologies, Security Protocols (for Identification and Authentication, Confidentiality and Privacy, and Integrity), Ubiquitous Networks: Ad Hoc Networks Security, Delay-Tolerant Network Security, Domestic Network Security, Peer-to-Peer Networks Security, Security Issues in Mobile and Ubiquitous Networks, Security of GSM/GPRS/UMTS Systems, Sensor Networks Security, Vehicular Network Security, Wireless Communication Security: Bluetooth, NFC, WiFi, WiMAX, WiMedia, others

This Track will emphasize the design, implementation, management and applications of computer communications, networks and services. Topics of mostly theoretical nature are also welcome, provided there is clear practical potential in applying the results of such work.

Track B: Computer Science

Broadband wireless technologies: LTE, WiMAX, WiRAN, HSDPA, HSUPA, Resource allocation and interference management, Quality of service and scheduling methods, Capacity planning and dimensioning, Cross-layer design and Physical layer based issue, Interworking architecture and interoperability, Relay assisted and cooperative communications, Location and provisioning and mobility management, Call admission and flow/congestion control, Performance optimization, Channel capacity modeling and analysis, Middleware Issues: Event-based, publish/subscribe, and message-oriented middleware, Reconfigurable, adaptable, and reflective middleware approaches, Middleware solutions for reliability, fault tolerance, and quality-of-service, Scalability of middleware, Context-aware middleware, Autonomic and self-managing middleware, Evaluation techniques for middleware solutions, Formal methods and tools for designing, verifying, and evaluating, middleware, Software engineering techniques for middleware, Service oriented middleware, Agent-based middleware, Security middleware, Network Applications: Network-based automation, Cloud applications, Ubiquitous and pervasive applications, Collaborative applications, RFID and sensor network applications, Mobile applications, Smart home applications, Infrastructure monitoring and control applications, Remote health monitoring, GPS and location-based applications, Networked vehicles applications, Alert applications, Embedded Computer System, Advanced Control Systems, and Intelligent Control : Advanced control and measurement, computer and microprocessor-based control, signal processing, estimation and identification techniques, application specific IC's, nonlinear and adaptive control, optimal and robot control, intelligent control, evolutionary computing, and intelligent systems, instrumentation subject to critical conditions, automotive, marine and aero-space control and all other control applications, Intelligent Control System, Wiring/Wireless Sensor, Signal Control System. Sensors, Actuators and Systems Integration : Intelligent sensors and actuators, multisensor fusion, sensor array and multi-channel processing, micro/nano technology, microsensors and microactuators, instrumentation electronics, MEMS and system integration, wireless sensor, Network Sensor, Hybrid

Sensor, Distributed Sensor Networks. Signal and Image Processing : Digital signal processing theory, methods, DSP implementation, speech processing, image and multidimensional signal processing, Image analysis and processing, Image and Multimedia applications, Real-time multimedia signal processing, Computer vision, Emerging signal processing areas, Remote Sensing, Signal processing in education. Industrial Informatics: Industrial applications of neural networks, fuzzy algorithms, Neuro-Fuzzy application, bioInformatics, real-time computer control, real-time information systems, human-machine interfaces, CAD/CAM/CAT/CIM, virtual reality, industrial communications, flexible manufacturing systems, industrial automated process, Data Storage Management, Harddisk control, Supply Chain Management, Logistics applications, Power plant automation, Drives automation. Information Technology, Management of Information System : Management information systems, Information Management, Nursing information management, Information System, Information Technology and their application, Data retrieval, Data Base Management, Decision analysis methods, Information processing, Operations research, E-Business, E-Commerce, E-Government, Computer Business, Security and risk management, Medical imaging, Biotechnology, Bio-Medicine, Computer-based information systems in health care, Changing Access to Patient Information, Healthcare Management Information Technology. Communication/Computer Network, Transportation Application : On-board diagnostics, Active safety systems, Communication systems, Wireless technology, Communication application, Navigation and Guidance, Vision-based applications, Speech interface, Sensor fusion, Networking theory and technologies, Transportation information, Autonomous vehicle, Vehicle application of affective computing, Advance Computing technology and their application : Broadband and intelligent networks, Data Mining, Data fusion, Computational intelligence, Information and data security, Information indexing and retrieval, Information processing, Information systems and applications, Internet applications and performances, Knowledge based systems, Knowledge management, Software Engineering, Decision making, Mobile networks and services, Network management and services, Neural Network, Fuzzy logics, Neuro-Fuzzy, Expert approaches, Innovation Technology and Management : Innovation and product development, Emerging advances in business and its applications, Creativity in Internet management and retailing, B2B and B2C management, Electronic transceiver device for Retail Marketing Industries, Facilities planning and management, Innovative pervasive computing applications, Programming paradigms for pervasive systems, Software evolution and maintenance in pervasive systems, Middleware services and agent technologies, Adaptive, autonomic and context-aware computing, Mobile/Wireless computing systems and services in pervasive computing, Energy-efficient and green pervasive computing, Communication architectures for pervasive computing, Ad hoc networks for pervasive communications, Pervasive opportunistic communications and applications, Enabling technologies for pervasive systems (e.g., wireless BAN, PAN), Positioning and tracking technologies, Sensors and RFID in pervasive systems, Multimodal sensing and context for pervasive applications, Pervasive sensing, perception and semantic interpretation, Smart devices and intelligent environments, Trust, security and privacy issues in pervasive systems, User interfaces and interaction models, Virtual immersive communications, Wearable computers, Standards and interfaces for pervasive computing environments, Social and economic models for pervasive systems, Active and Programmable Networks, Ad Hoc & Sensor Network, Congestion and/or Flow Control, Content Distribution, Grid Networking, High-speed Network Architectures, Internet Services and Applications, Optical Networks, Mobile and Wireless Networks, Network Modeling and Simulation, Multicast, Multimedia Communications, Network Control and Management, Network Protocols, Network Performance, Network Measurement, Peer to Peer and Overlay Networks, Quality of Service and Quality of Experience, Ubiquitous Networks, Crosscutting Themes – Internet Technologies, Infrastructure, Services and Applications; Open Source Tools, Open Models and Architectures; Security, Privacy and Trust; Navigation Systems, Location Based Services; Social Networks and Online Communities; ICT Convergence, Digital Economy and Digital Divide, Neural Networks, Pattern Recognition, Computer Vision, Advanced Computing Architectures and New Programming Models, Visualization and Virtual Reality as Applied to Computational Science, Computer Architecture and Embedded Systems, Technology in Education, Theoretical Computer Science, Computing Ethics, Computing Practices & Applications

Authors are invited to submit papers through e-mail ijcsiseditor@gmail.com. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated by IJCSIS. Before submission authors should carefully read over the journal's Author Guidelines, which are located at <http://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/authors-notes> .

© IJCSIS PUBLICATION 2021

ISSN 1947 5500

<http://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>